

Intelligent Trust and Security Orchestration for 6G Distributed Cloud Environments

Deliverable 5.1

Primary Report on Orchestration Framework
for Secure and Trustworthy 6G Networks

April 2025

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15975590](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15975590)

Contractual Date of Delivery:	January 31, 2025
Actual Date of Delivery:	April 1, 2025
Editor(s):	Cataldo Basile (POLITO)
Author(s)/Contributor(s):	Maxime Compastié, Saber Mhiri, Shuaib Siddiqui (I2CAT) Sheeba Backia Mary Baskaran, Souvik Paul, Andreas Kunz, Razvan Andrei Stoica, Apostolis Salkintzis (LEN) Luis Ribeiro, Paulo Correia (PDM) Stylianos Klados, Konstantinos Kyriakou, Anapliotis Petros (ADR) Afroditi Blika, Giannis Xidias, George Doukas (NTUA) Cataldo Basile, Gabriele Gatti, Francesco Settanni (POLITO) Pablo Serrano, Juan Manuel (UC3M) Rhys Miller, Mir Ghoraishi (GIGASYS)
Work Package	WP5
Target Dissemination Level	Public

This work is supported by the Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101139198, iTrust6G project. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or SNS-JU. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Revision History

Revision	Date	Editor / Commentator	Description of Edits
0.1	2024-11-19	Cataldo Basile (POLITO)	Deliverable structure sketched
0.2	2025-02-04	All the involved partners	Independent sections available
		Paulo Correia (PDMFC)	Draft version of SIEM and related contributions
0.3	2025-02-10	Cataldo Basile (POLITO)	First merged draft
0.4	2025-02-11	Cataldo Basile (POLITO)	Versions ready for the reviewers
0.5	2025-02-20	Cataldo Basile (POLITO)	Version addressing Reviewer's 1 comments
0.6	2025-02-24	Cataldo Basile (POLITO)	Version addressing Reviewer's 2 comments
0.7	2025-02-24	Cataldo Basile (POLITO)	Full version made ready
0.8	2025-03-15	Cataldo Basile (POLITO)	Further revisions
0.9	2025-03-20	Shuaib Siddiqui (I2CAT) Rhys Miller (GIGASYS)	Review and proof-reading
1.0	2025-03-28	Mir Ghoraishi (GIGASYS)	Final review and amendments, proof-reading, and submission

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List of Acronyms

3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project
5GC	5G Core
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AM/MA	Alert Manager/Monitoring Agents
API	Application Programming Interface
APT	Advanced Persistent Threats
AQL	Arango Query Language
ATT&CK	Adversarial Tactics, Techniques, and Common Knowledge
CACAO	Collaborative Automated Course of Action Operations
CAPEC	Common Attack Pattern Enumeration and Classification
CMR	Counter-Measure Recommender
CNF	Cloud-native Network Function (CNF)
CPE	Common Platform Enumeration
CSP	Constraint Satisfaction Problem
CTI	Cyber Threat Intelligence
CVE	Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures
CWE	Common Weakness Enumeration
DoA	Description of Action
eBPF	extended Berkeley Packet Filter
ECA	Evaluate-Condition-Action
ETB	External Threat Database
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
FastAPI	Web framework for building APIs with Python
GAT	Graph Attention Network
GCN	Graph Convolutional Network
GNN	Graph Neural Network
GraphSAGE	Graph Sample and Aggregated Network
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
IoC	Indicator of Compromise
LCM	Life Cycle Manager
LLM	Large Language Model
MANO	MANagement & Orchestration
MIME	Multipurpose Internet Mail Extensions
MITRE	Mentioned as an organization (e.g., MITRE CWE, CAPEC, ATT&CK) but not expanded as an acronym.
N2VC	Network Service to Virtualization Container
NBI	North Bound Interfaces
NFVO	NFV Orchestrator
NSF	Network Security Function
NVD	National Vulnerability Database
OCI	Open Container Initiative
OpenCTI	Open Cyber Threat Intelligence Platform
OS	Operating System
PDP	Policy Decision Point
PEP	Policy Enforcement Point

PSM	Programable Security Mechanism
PVF	Policy Verification Function
PyCTI	Official OpenCTI Python client
PyG	PyTorch Geometric
RA	Remote Attestation (Section 6.3)
RETE	Rete algorithm
RM	Remediation Manager
RL	Reinforcement Learning
RO	Resource Orchestrator
SAT	Satisfiability problem
SDI	Software-Defined Infrastructure
SDSec	Software-Defined Security
SGX	Software Guard Extensions
SIEM	Security Information and Event Management
SIGMA	Sigma rules are vendor-agnostic detection rules for log events that can be converted to various SIEM formats
SMPD	Security Monitoring and Pre-detection
SNORT	Snort rules are network intrusion detection signatures that monitor network traffic for suspicious activity
SOAR	Security orchestration, automation, and response
STIX	Structured Threat Information eXpression
SVM	Support Vector Machine
TAXII	Trusted Automated Exchange of Intelligence Information
TEE	Trusted Execution Environment
TGNN	Temporal Graph Neural Network
TOSCA	Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications
TTP	Tactics, Techniques, and Procedures
VA	Vulnerability Assessment
VCA	Virtualized Network Function Configuration and Abstraction
VM	Virtual Machine
VIM	Virtual Infrastructure Manager
VNF	Virtualized Network Function
VNFM	Virtualized Network Function Manager
WAF	Web Application Firewall
WP	Work Package
YARA	Yara rules are pattern-matching rules used to identify and classify malware samples

Executive Summary

This document, **iTrust6G** D5.1, reports the progress on Work Package 5 (WP5) tasks on the following topics.

The initial version of the Vulnerability Assessment Tool is designed and produced. This component provides vulnerability detection and mitigation capabilities tailored to the complex nature of beyond-5G/6G networks. The tool uses a modular, extensible, and scalable microservices architecture, where each performs a specific service detection and vulnerability scanning function. All components are containerized using Docker to increase consistency and portability across different environments. The tool is designed to support 6G network functions, including the Radio Access Network (RAN) and Core Network (CN) nodes. The output is a STIX JSON with the discovered data, including devices, services, vulnerabilities, and mitigation recommendations. Moreover, this task has produced an Improved Metadon-based Security Information and Event Management (SIEM), a log management solution designed for handling large volumes of information and implementing security incident handling functionalities at the local/edge level, and Chimera, a Golang-based security monitoring tool, a comprehensive data collection and processing solution capable of gathering system logs and metrics and transforming them into semi-structured formats.

The Cyber Threat Intelligence (CTI) data aggregated, correlated, and enriched from all the other project sources to make them semantically richer and more beneficial for the rest of the infrastructure. It designed and developed the AI Correlation Engine, which correlates Cyber Threat Intelligence, enhancing real-time threat detection. The AI Correlation Engine integrates OpenCTI's automated playbooks with Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) to streamline threat intelligence processing and enhance cyber defence. It uses automated playbooks, like STIX/TAXII and MITRE ATT&CK frameworks, to process and correlate threat data autonomously, facilitating quick detection and response. The playbooks enable real-time analysis and action by linking threat entities such as Indicators of Compromise (IoCs), malware, Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures (CVEs), and attack techniques. Moreover, it produced the Orchestration Engine, which serves as the AI-driven core of the security automation framework, integrating OpenCTI, Graph Neural Networks (GNNs), and external threat intelligence sources. It automates the correlation of threat intelligence, ensuring that cybersecurity entities such as IoCs, vulnerabilities, threat actors, and attack techniques are efficiently analysed and linked.

The architecture and the initial isolated versions of the components are produced for managing the remediation of security incidents and the cases where the risks are considered unacceptable. For this purpose, the Remediation Manager is the key component. It receives Cyber Threat Intelligence data enriched by the AI-based Security Orchestrator service, identifies strategies on how to react, and selects the best way to remediate the problem. It enforces the remediations at the security policy enforcement and network levels. Policy Enforcement requires an ad hoc component, the Policy Tool, which identifies how to enforce security requirements in a networked environment using models of the NSFs that are managed through the Security Capability Manager. At the network level, it uses a Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications (TOSCA)-based abstract representation of the network to protect. It uses the Service Orchestrator to deploy configurations and implement network changes at node (e.g., adding NSFs) or topology level (e.g., moving nodes).

Project efforts on enhancement of the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) OSM MANO service orchestrator are reported. It improves it with additional functionalities for a robust and secure orchestration process. To this end, it designed and is developing the Life Cycle Manager, the key component in any orchestration process. From the OSM MANO perspective, it is a Lightweight Build Life Cycle Management for OSM that interacts with the Resource Orchestrator module for resource orchestration and Network Service to Virtualization Container (N2VC) for Virtualized Network Function (VN)F configuration. Moreover, it developed the Policy Verification Function (PVF), which makes OSM MANO able to detect anomalous policies, checking that parameters are correct using a Machine Learning (ML) approach. This is a

module triggered for any CRUD operation or security configurations and mechanisms.

Finally, defining models to enact network service enablers' composition are presented. It produced programmability models based on the evaluation of the virtualisation model, offering a suitable trade-off between security and management flexibility, as well as current system architecture for a virtualised environment. operating system (OS)-level virtualisation (regular operating system containers) and hybrid OS-level virtualisation in virtual machines have been considered. Moreover, these programmability models cover the modality of payload injection, either at resource design time or operation time, impacting the security guarantee and metrics and their operation. Furthermore, it designed the Resource Generator, which produces a programmable network service with security enablers. An initial functional and technical architecture has been proposed for this component, including a first set of technical interfaces stemming from an initial analysis of the state-of-the-art network and infrastructure programmability and resource composition. This component is also responsible for crafting and injecting an agent, exposing the resource intervals to be monitored and managed by the service orchestrator and security orchestrator.

1 Introduction

iTrust6G WP5, “AI-Enabled Security Component Orchestration and Programmability”, is about investigating, designing, and tooling the cyber-threat detection and remediation affecting the 6G platform. Results will be achieved by exploiting security programmability models and leveraging AI.

In the iTrust6G ecosystem, one essential pillar is maintaining the risks at an acceptable level. iTrust6G WP5 provides the needed models, methods, and tools for achieving this goal. Indeed, WP5 provides methods for monitoring the infrastructure and detecting anomalies. These anomalies are first classified, and then Cyber Threat Intelligence data are enriched using artificial intelligence (AI)-based techniques also based on information obtained by algorithms and methods from WP3 and WP4. AI-enriched Cyber Threat Intelligence (CTI) data are used to find and enforce proper remediations by producing configurations for security control and the Network Security Function (NSF)s and proposing changes to the network to protect them. To ensure the correct enforcement, a service orchestrator abstracting the networked layer will be produced. This component, able to coordinate the activities in a highly virtualized network, uses different types of enablers, from elements operating at the security control level to remediate security issues to programmable security mechanisms.

Based on iTrust6G Description of Action (DoA), WP5 objectives are:

- **05.1.** To design and implement security programmability models covering the integration and operation of 6G services. These models must leverage security monitoring and policy enforcement at service, runtime and data-plane levels;
- **05.2.** To design a programmability interface that allows extracting relevant security metrics to identify and classify the security events;
- **05.3.** To leverage artificial intelligence to detect and classify threats. Moreover, AI will also serve to identify appropriate remediation measures and help select the best one. AI must provide explainability; all the decisions made must be properly explained and justified with the available data;
- **05.4.** To deliver a recommender for countermeasures able to pinpoint context-aware security mechanisms supporting the mitigation actions and explain the decision made;
- **05.5.** To design and implement a security orchestrator that can manage the entire lifecycle of programmable security mechanisms covering the services, the infrastructure runtime and the data plane;
- **05.6.** To extend the service orchestrator to support trustable placement of services, slice management and cooperation with the security orchestrator.

iTrust6G WP5 is composed of 5 tasks as follows:

- **T5.1** will allow the secure design and development of network services operated in 6G networks by selecting and integrating adequate security enablers in resources to protect. It defines the interfaces to program and configure security enablers, service orchestrator and runtime to enforce requirements, and analyse the security posture of a resource.
- **T5.2** will develop multi-modal metrics to better comprehend and optimise system components. Metrics will cover the programmability interface, the runtime of the compute resources, and any other context-specific data. Forensic data will be used with other metrics, such as system vulnerabilities, to monitor and assess the security context of the system and identify risks, and the module will also propose strategies and technologies to defend against 6G-specific attacks. Examining the metrics can shed light on the system’s functionality and security.

- **T5.3** will integrate decentralized, highly distributed AI techniques into the security orchestrator module. This module serves real-time detection, classification, and mitigation of cyber threats based on metrics from T5.2. It will integrate AI algorithms for identifying, classifying, and mitigating cyber threats as well as optimal decision-making from WP3. Moreover, it will integrate the trust intelligent management services of WP4.
- **T5.4** will develop a comprehensive framework to improve the security posture of the managed network via both proactive measures and reactive responses. Based on CTI from WP3 and AI-enriched data from T5.3, it will propose and coordinate, with the security orchestrator, the enforcement of remediation to security incidents or any change to the overall security posture. It will also provide all the models for representing the networked environments to protect and the security requirements at different levels of abstraction.
- **T5.5** will develop the security orchestrator that addresses the challenges associated with this framework. It is responsible for managing, coordinating, and automating the deployment, configuration, and operation of network services and resources securely across the entire network, from edge to cloud. It will implement the key aspects: multi-level orchestration, Secure Virtualized Network Function (VNF) and NSF placement, secure deployment methods for service images, and isolation of resources via suited virtualization.

These tasks are very related with each other to allow reaching the WP objectives. Moreover, they show major relations with the other technical work packages, namely WP3 and WP4, and, of course, with the use cases where iTrust6G results will be verified, i.e., WP6. All WP and task inter-relations are highlighted in Section 1.2.

1.1 WP5 structure

Figure 1-1 introduces high-level functional architecture of the main components developed in WP5, and the interactions with other WPs.

Figure 1-1 iTrust6G architecture for AI-enabled security component orchestration and programmability [1]

The Counter-measure Recommender and Resource Generator, developed in T5.1, is the component that helps select security modules, like VNF or Cloud-native Network Function (CNF), to satisfy security requirements or construct resources embedding them. Moreover, the same task defines Programmable Security Mechanisms, which are the components that add security-relevant features needed to implement the iTrust6G services, like specific detection and mitigation capabilities.

The Vulnerability Assessment Tool is the component that can acquire, store, and correlate data to monitor the performance and security posture of the iTrust6G-protected system. These data are processed by Metadon – SIEM, which is a log management solution designed for handling large volumes of information and implementing security incident handling functionalities at the local/edge level. Moreover, these components are coupled with an External Threat Database that aggregates all the CTI from project-internal and external sources.

The AI Module for Service Orchestration is the module that aggregates and makes available all the AI services integrated by T5.3.

T5.4 proposes the Remediation Manager and all the other components that are needed for security policy enforcement (Policy Tool), as well as the components for managing the abstract models of NSFs (Security Capability Manager) and the abstract models for representing the networking infrastructure (Network Description Manager).

Finally, the Security Orchestrator, in T5.5, is responsible for managing, coordinating and automating the deployment, configuration, and operation of network services and resources securely across the entire network, from edge to cloud.

The main outcomes of WP5 are the components listed here, and all the other models needed to make them work properly. More details on the outcomes will be presented in the next sections dedicated to individual tasks.

The WP5 components interact with or require services from other work packages:

- WP3: CTI information is needed to decide remediations and to assess the risks and the effectiveness of remediations; moreover, the AI algorithms developed to enrich the CTI platform will be used in T5.3.
- WP4: the policy decision point produces information to identify entities exchanging threat intelligence.
- WP6: provides access to the physical infrastructure of the system to protect with the iTrust6G framework.

It is worth noting that the current information flows align perfectly with what has been already described in iTrust6G D2.2 [1]. We refer to this document for further details and for the complete list of sequence diagrams. Minor deviations are expected when the components are integrated into a single framework. Nonetheless, the risk of major deviations that may impact the architecture has been evaluated as irrelevant.

All the details about the workflows and the corresponding information flows will be presented in detail in the next sections.

1.2 Inter-relations with other WPs and tasks

iTrust6G objectives require collaboration among the technical iTrust6G WPs. Hence, precisely defining the potential interfaces can facilitate the development and the integration of the components. This subsection details the relationship among WP5 tasks and other tasks and WPs.

T5.1 manifests several strict dependencies to achieve its delivery:

- The metrics obtained from programmable mechanisms are transferred to the SIEM and vulnerability section tool provided by T5.2. Collaborating with this task will be needed for the assessment.
- The security configuration and selection of mechanisms for the program shall be selected upon the decision of the remediation recommender in T5.4.
- As security mechanisms are to be deployed on the infrastructure, they shall have to be supervised by the secure service orchestrator, acting as a communication channel between their instances and the security orchestrator. It will also facilitate the change of security enablers as part of the multi-level security orchestration.

Moreover, additional gathered metrics by the mechanisms will also indirectly impact components in WP3 and WP4 by increasing the quality of the metrics used for CTI generation and trust evaluation.

The two T5.2 components show different dependencies with the rest of the project's work items:

- **Vulnerability Assessment Tool:**
 - This component will receive metrics and monitoring data from the Service Orchestrator (T5.5). These metrics will include the network topology and asset inventory information such as IP, Device Hostname, MAC, and Open Ports.
 - This component may receive remote attestation logs from the Remote Attestation (RA) Engine containing remote attestation results and integrity measurements.
 - The output of this task will feed the Security threat detection & classification component (T3.2) and Trust Inference (T3.4) with detection metrics and security events containing real-time security alerts and incidents. The output will be a STIX v2.1 JSON report containing:
 - Detected vulnerabilities and associated remediation recommendations.
 - Threat intelligence reports and indicators of compromise (IoCs).
 - Security posture assessments and risk scores.
 - Compliance and audit reports.
 - The External Threat Database developed under this task will be utilized by the Security Threat Detection & classification component (T3.2) to get information about threats.
- **Metadon-SIEM**
 - Task 3.4 will provide inputs and agents on monitored machines;
 - Task 3.2 will consume the alerts and receive requests for classifications from detected threats;
 - Task 4.2 will receive alert indicators to help the AI Trust Evaluator modulate trust scores;
 - Task 4.4 will request a dynamic collection of forensic artefacts, disk dumps, memory dumps, and network dumps;
 - Task 5.2 provides an External Treat Database where a set of public CTI information will be available for internal consumption;
 - Task 4.3 will provide programmable security mechanisms and Policy Enforcement Points.

T5.3 is closely connected to multiple tasks to improve threat intelligence correlation and response:

- T5.3 will receive CTI data from the CTI Platform developed in WP3. This includes up-to-date threat indicators, relevant threat actor profiles, and any contextual intelligence about vulnerabilities,

attacks, and exploits observed across the network.

- T5.3 will also leverage the External Threat Database provided in T5.2. This database hosts public CTI, IoCs, and additional open-source intelligence (OSINT).
- T5.3 will provide the Remediation Manager (T5.4) with prioritized threat findings, correlated alerts, and recommended courses of action.
- T4.3: The authentication mechanisms embedded within the Orchestration Engine ensure secure access control, verifying the integrity of entities exchanging threat intelligence.
- T5.3 might request or receive forensic artifacts from T4.4 to bolster correlation with additional evidence. If T5.3 detects suspicious activity, it can prompt T4.4 for deeper forensic analysis.

T5.4 depends on the following WPs and Tasks for its correct implementation and design.

- It relies on the Cyber Threat Intelligence data received from components developed in T3.2 and T4.3 to make decisions on the proper remediations. These T3.2 CTI data will be enriched with AI techniques in T5.3 and made available in T5.2.
- The possibility to make decisions relies on the possibility of estimating the effectiveness of the proposed remediation. To this purpose, T5.4 relies on the evaluation Risk Assessment component developed in T3.3.
- This Task also relies on the services provided in T6.2 for the actual enforcement of remediations, like enforcing changes in the infrastructure or deploying new configurations into NSFs. These interactions will be mediated by the Service Orchestration in T5.5.

The development of the secure service orchestrator in T5.5 can be mapped to the other tasks as represented in Figure 1-2. The Secure Service Orchestrator interacts with the following components:

- *Remediation Manager (T5.4)*: Based on the event in the network, the RM sends instructions to the SSO in the form of commands or playbook for operations over the network elements.
- *Policy Decision Point (T4.3)*: The PEP at the SSO enables service verification raised by the user based on policy intent on interaction with the PDP.
- *Programmable Security Mechanism (T5.1)*: The Policy Verifier Module interacts with the PSM for low-level security metrics.
- *Infrastructure orchestrator (T6.2)*: The LCM interacts with the Infrastructure Orchestrator to deploy Day 0 operation in the cloud environment as cloud-native VNFs.

Figure 1-2 Relationship of the internal components of the secure service orchestrator with the other components

- *AI Trust Evaluator (T4.2)*: The LCM interacts with this component to fetch the trust score of a component, domain and service image before deployment for a trust-aware placement of services.
- *Security Monitoring and Pre-detection (T5.2), Static Trust Assessment (T4.1), RA Engine (4.2)*: The reporting and monitoring module of the service orchestrator reports any anomaly and dictates the current security posture as well as the topology of the network to these three tasks.

1.3 Project objectives and KPIs mapping

iTrust6G technical objectives and related KPI mappings are presented in Table 1-1.

Table 1-1 iTrust6G Technical Objectives

Technical Objective	Associated WP	Associated KPIs
Tech Objective 1	WP2 (T2.1, T2.2 and T2.3)	KPI-O1.1, KPI-O1.2, KPI-O1.3
Tech Objective 2	WP3 (T3.1, T3.2, T3.3 T3.4)	KPI-O2-1, KPI-O2-2, KPI-O2-3, KPI-O2-4, KPI-O2-5
Tech Objective 3	WP4 (T4.1, T4.2, T4.3, T4.4)	KPI-O3.1, KPI-O3.2, KPI-O3.3, KPI-O3.4
Tech Objective 4	WP5 (T5.1, T5.2, T5.3, T5.4)	KPI-O4.1, KPI-O4.2, KPI-O4.3, KPI-O4.4, KPI-O4.5
Tech Objective 5	WP2 (T2.3), WP5 (T5.4, T5.5)	KPI-O5.1, KPI-O5.2
Tech Objective 6	WP5 (T5.4, T5.5)	KPI-O6.1, KPI-O6.2, KPI-O6.3, KPI-O6.4, KPI-O6.5, KPI-O6.6, KPI-O6.7, KPI-O6.8, KPI-O6.9, KPI-O6.10

1.4 Targeted audience

The content of this document is targeted to the project's technical partners (researchers, architects and developers), who will implement, validate, and integrate the WP5 features of the project. Moreover, it is of interest to other WP partners for the integration of the entire iTrust6G framework.

iTrust6G D5.1 is also intended for the dissemination and exploitation team in the project by aiding the identification of destination communities susceptible to interest in the project's results.

Finally, as iTrust6G D5.1 is public, it is also destined for an external audience of scientists and practitioners in service and network security willing to discover iTrust6G's results on AI-enabled security applied to incident detection and Cyber Threat Intelligence enrichment, Orchestration and programmability, security policy enforcement, and risk mitigation.

1.4.1 Objectives for the next reporting period

iTrust6G WP5 main objective for the next period is to provide the initial integration of the components produced in WP5 with the other components in WP3 and WP4, which must work on the infrastructures released in WP6.

1.5 Document Structure

iTrust6G D5.1 is structured in the following seven chapters and two appendices:

- Section 2 presents the achievement reached in T5.1 in terms of programmable resource generation and deployment.

- Section 3 introduces the services provided by iTrust6G for monitoring services and detecting security-relevant events, which are developed in T5.2.
- Section 4 presents the effort towards more usable and effective AI-based iTrust6G services, which coordinates the effort in T5.3 with WP3-developed AI methods.
- Section 5 presents the iTrust6G infrastructure to remediate security incidents and mitigate risks, as well as the methods to enforce them, which are the focus of T5.4.
- Section 6 presents the progress towards the Secured E2E Service Orchestration, developed in T5.5.
- Section 7 briefly summarizes the results and draws conclusions.
- Finally, the Appendix reports relevant listings.

2 Programmable Resource Generation and Deployment

The work conducted in to develop programmable resource generation and deployment endeavours to secure the conception and development of network services operated in 6G networks to create a smart security lifecycle for 6G network services. To that extent, this line of research aims to experiment with and implement methodologies to select and integrate adequate security enablers in network resources (e.g., network services). The final objective of this research activity is twofold:

- Achieve security-by-design, by integrating enforcement and monitoring capacities in the design of resources, before their operation,
- Achieve security-in-depth, by extending the management surface exposed to the security orchestrator in resources needing protection.

To attain this goal, it defines the interfaces needed to program (i.e. inject an active logic) and configure security enablers, the service orchestrator and runtime to cope with a variety of security requirements issued by the security orchestration (the remediation manager, more specifically) and inspect the security posture of a resource for security monitoring (pre-detection) and trust assessment. Achieving programmability requires investigating novel virtualisation models offering a trade-off between security by isolation, utilities (i.e. respect for demanding service-level obligation) and alterability of the virtual environment. This latter factor is needed to facilitate security programmability both at design time and operation time, while the second factor contributes to respecting the expected quality of service from protected resources. Towards this objective, several programmability models are defined, investigated and evaluated to alter different steps of the resource lifetime (design, deployment, and operation phases).

In addition, this research activity elaborates on a policy model to express those security requirements in a consistent form, extending TOSCA modelling language for this specific purpose. This specification will drive the inclusion of the enablers as per the characteristic of the resource to protect.

Finally, a resource generator will be conceived and developed for design-time programmable actions. The defined programmability interface will serve threat and risk monitoring, for enforcing security decisions, and for operating generated service images incorporating programmable security enablers. Towards these objectives, this research activity contributes to two of the WP5 objectives (Chapter 1) O5.1 and O5.2.

2.1 Summary of the outcomes

During the first period, this activity first focused on producing state-of-the-art and the design work of the components supporting this activity. The work primarily focuses on modelling approaches for enacting the composition of network service enablers. The outcome is twofold:

- The first design work is related to the definition of the programmability models to be defined. To that extent, we evaluated (i) which virtualisation model offered a suitable trade-off between security and management flexibility. We conducted a state-of-the-art analysis on the current system architecture for virtualised environment and selected several virtualisation models to experiment with: OS-level virtualisation (regular operating system containers) and hybrid OS-level virtualisation in virtual machines. Both have the benefits of being implemented according to similar standards, including Open Container Initiative (OCI) containers, permitting uniformising their generation with common tools and procedures. Another aspect of the programmability model covers the modality of payload injection, either at resource design time or operation time, impacting the security guarantee and metrics and their operation.
- A second result relates to the resource generator's design, which produces a programmable network service with security enablers. An initial functional and technical architecture has been proposed for

this component, including a first set of technical interfaces stemming from an initial analysis of the state-of-the-art on network and infrastructure programmability and resource composition. Beyond interfacing with pre-existing OCI-builders, this component is also responsible for crafting and injecting an agent, exposing the resource intervals to be monitored and managed by the service orchestrator and security orchestrator. This component is complemented by a decision module presented and extended in *iTrust6G*. Eventually, an initial integration analysis with the service orchestrator will be conducted to coordinate its integrability.

2.2 Objectives and expected outcomes for the next reporting period

In preparation for the next reporting period, the objective of this line of research will focus on the following:

- Completing the development work on the resource generator in charge of producing OCI containers from regular CNF to the agent. It should experiment with security enablers produced by the organisation, such as those from T4.3 and T5.4.
- A policy model extending TOSCA and aligning with initial work from T5.4 to express composability and instrumented with an adequate interpreter. This interpreter shall interface with the selection tool and facilitate the preparation of proactive images and possible instantiation.
- Completing the programmability models and their interface shall be reiterated as per the feedback on the architecture to be expressed in *iTrust6G* D2.2 and declared final.

2.3 Overall presentation and achievements

The result of our work contributes to the preparation of two components:

- **Counter-measure Recommender & Resource generator:** These oversee selecting security modules to enforce security requirements, which may also be because of a remediation task, and constructing a resource (typically a VNF & CNF) embedding them to satisfy the requests of the Remediation Manager
- **Programmable Security Mechanisms:** These components refer to the modules added to the mechanisms that can access the resource's internals needing protection to exert specific detection and mitigation capabilities.

In the following subsections, we review individually these two components.

2.4 Countermeasure recommender and resource generator

2.4.1 State-of-the-art

The design of Countermeasure Recommender & Resource Generators in security-oriented virtualization involves selecting appropriate virtualization models, defining image generation processes, and optimizing security enabler selection methodologies. This section reviews the current state-of-the-art in these areas, outlining relevant technologies and standards.

2.4.1.1 Virtualization models for secure countermeasures

Virtualization is critical in securing cloud and network infrastructures by isolating security components while ensuring flexible deployment. Several studies have analysed the advantages and challenges associated with different virtualization models.

Compastié et al. [2] provided a comprehensive analysis of system virtualization models and their impact on cloud security. The study outlines how traditional hypervisor-based virtualization (Type-I and Type-II) ensures strong isolation but incurs overhead, while OS-level virtualization (e.g., containerized environments)

offers efficiency at the cost of reduced security boundaries. The introduction of hybrid models, such as containers running within lightweight virtual machines (VMs), attempts to balance security and performance by leveraging tools like:

- *gVisor*, which introduces an additional user-space kernel layer for isolating applications.
- *Bubblewrap*¹, a sandboxing solution that restricts processes in minimal privilege environments [3].
- *runV*, a solution bridging containers and virtual machines.
- *Firecracker*, another solution permitting the execution of containers in virtual machines.
- *Unikraft*², a unikernel approach that minimizes the attack surfaces by reducing system complexity

These models are being explored to enhance the Countermeasure Recommender & Resource Generator by ensuring security enablers operate within isolated and optimized environments.

2.4.1.2 Image generation and standardization

Security-enforced virtualization requires well-defined image formats and execution environments to maintain compatibility and enforce security policies. The Open Container Initiative (OCI) defines critical standards for image runtime and management:

- *OCI-runtime* governs execution standards for containerized security mechanisms [4].
- *OCI-Images* standardizes image formats, ensuring interoperability across deployment environments [5].
- *Kata Containers*, a lightweight VM solution, enables security mechanisms to run in an isolated environment while maintaining container-like flexibility [6]. In this setting, Amazon Firecracker is an example of microVMs runtime (hypervisor) and integrable with Kata Container and Kubernetes.

Using OCI-compliant images ensures that Countermeasure Recommender & Resource Generator outputs are deployable across various orchestrators while maintaining security guarantees.

2.4.1.3 Security enabler selection and optimization

Automating the selection of security enablers is a key challenge in security orchestration. The PALANTIR project introduced a constraint-programming approach for selecting optimal security functions to solve a satisfiability problem (SAT) for threat mitigation [7]. This method ensures that:

- Security enablers are selected based on specific threat requirements;
- The selection process accounts for infrastructure constraints (e.g., resource availability, compatibility);
- Deployments align with a cost-performance trade-off, reducing overhead while maximizing security impact.

These advancements provide a foundation for extending security enabler selection methodologies in the Countermeasure Recommender & Resource Generator, allowing it to dynamically recommend and deploy tailored countermeasures.

¹ <https://github.com/containers/bubblewrap?tab=readme-ov-file>.

² <https://github.com/unikraft>

2.4.2 Design challenges

The preparation of the Countermeasure Recommender and Resource generator has followed the following design challenges.

2.4.2.1 Compatibility with legacy enablers and orchestrators

Although the work conveyed in this activity regards resource generation, it should ensure that the selected mechanisms and the generated resources are viable for deployment in existing, standardised and adopted VNF/CNF images and a service orchestrator. To that extent, the resource generator aims to produce OCI-compliant images that can be employed on the containerised service orchestrator but abstract different virtualisation models (e.g., OS-level virtualisation and container in VM).

2.4.2.2 Trade-off between security overhead and reconfiguration cost

Generating a resource that embeds an extra security logic lowers the protection overhead as the interactions between the logic and the resource require fewer computing and network capacities. However, updating this logic, for instance, to reflect a change in the security policy will require the generation and deployment of a new resource, which will be heavily costly. Therefore, the mechanism should be included when the security overhead is important and requires minimisation, but not systematically to avoid systems and overhead when enforcement requirements change.

2.4.3 Design approach

In this section, we detail the internal architecture of the Countermeasure Recommender & Resource generator, selecting enablers to be deployed and enacting it. In addition, we also provide a formalisation of the programmability model we are looking to use for the instrument via this framework.

The technical architecture illustrated in Figure 2-1 is composed of two planes: (i) the *knowledge plane* in charge of proactively collecting and exploiting the knowledge to be used at remediation time, and to several components in interaction, and (ii) the *events plane* enacting response to a security event. It comprises several components in interactions:

Figure 2-1 Counter-measure recommender technical architecture

- **Policy engines:** This component oversees interpreting a specification into security constraints serving the selection and/or construction of resources embedding the selected mechanisms.
- **Domain Manager:** The Domain Manager represents the current situation of an administered domain to serve the security decision process and translate security decisions into planned technical actions to be forwarded to the orchestrators implementing them. In practice, it provides information such as (i) deployed mechanisms in the different domains and (ii) monitoring metrics to do this. If a resource should be built before being deployed, it invokes the resource generator. During the integration, we will integrate the Domain Manager with other T5.4 tools, to ensure collaboration and separation of concerns.
- **Security Solver:** The security solver oversees analysing the current posture of a domain to be protected by a policy to issue a recommendation for security control deployment, possibly involving its inclusion in a resource. To that extent, this component builds constraint satisfaction problems (CSP). A constraint satisfaction problem models a mathematical problem searching addressing the affectation of values to a certain set of variables (e.g., enacting a certain configuration) while meeting a certain number of expressed constraints (e.g., representing the system states). This CSP is fitted to address identified situations from a pre-prepared specification obtained from policy interpretation, gathers contextual information to solve them, saves them, and interprets them into configuration deployment plans. CSP specifications and results can be stored to speed up the response when similar decisions are to be made in the future. Also in this case, the integration with T5.4 tools will guarantee a precise separation of concerns among the optimization performed here and the decisions made at the higher level by the Policy tools.
- **Resource Generator:** The Resource Generator supervises the building of network resources embedding security mechanisms. It interfaces with the catalogue to retrieve pieces of software and mechanism involved in the construction process, and the domain manager to specification of resources to build.
- **Catalogue:** This component indexes the different security enablers that can be enacted to reconcile the deployment of a distributed application and can be included in the resource able to be generated. This component describes their capabilities and properties used in CSP solving.

This work diverges from the responsibility taken by the remediation recommender by focusing on (i) the selection of the implementation of the security control in charge of enforcing a security constraint in collaboration with the remediation recommender, and (ii) supervising the generation of VNF/CNF images embedding the selected mechanism when found adequate to match the policy constraints. In practice, in Figure 2-1 the external component labelled “*External iTrust6G tool issuing security event*” is expected to be the remediation recommender.

iTrust6G formalised different programmability models defining the modalities of the enablers to be deployed. The main properties we retain to select the definition of the programmability model are:

- The component from a reference architecture that should receive the programmable enablers (where),
- The step of the resource lifecycle to receive the externally defined resource (when),
- The nature and objective of the logic to be injected (what).

Depending on those properties, several benefits can be anticipated in the security orchestration and resource operation, justifying the adoption of a model.

Figure 2-2 Virtualization reference architecture in software network environment

It should be noted that programmability is not equivalent to the configuration. While the latest aim at issuing specifications constraining the behaviour of assets (e.g., software) to reach a higher-end objective (typically supervised by a management layer), the programmability aims the injections of an arbitrary, active and externally defined logic to reach this goal [8]. For instance, software deployment and program injection are two forms of programmability.

Figure 2-2 represents a reference architecture representing different virtualisation models (type I and type II system virtualisation, OS-level visualisation, hybrid OS-level virtualisation in VM) in the software network environment, and illustrate different resources considered to be programmable, namely:

- **Containers**, via the alteration of their applications, configuration, or source code (e.g., Webassembly³ containers),
- **Virtual Machines**, via the alteration of their applications, configuration, and OS kernel,
- **Regular application**, via the alteration of their configuration and source code,
- **Operating system Kernel** is done via dedicated modules, alteration of the parameters, and injection of modules (e.g., regular Linux kernel module or extended Berkeley Packet Filter (eBPF) program) when this feature is supported.

Other elements depicted in the architecture (e.g., hardware accelerators, network appliances) can be deemed programmable in the literature but were discarded at an early stage of T5.1 investigation as less aligned with the anticipated needs of the project, such as the access of the internals of the resources to protect, which were later refined to be network services.

In this context, it is proposed to experiment with the programmability models defined in Table 2-1.

³ Webassembly has become popular to execute workload outside browser, typically in resource constrained environment. A quick reference is available at <https://www.docker.com/blog/wasm-vs-docker/>

Table 2-1 Proposition of Security Programmability Models

	Legacy	Pervasive
Type of programmable logic	OCI container images containing security control	Application acting as security control in OCI container images
Programmed resources	Infrastructure through Bare-metal container engine (Kubernetes and Containerd)	OCI Container images to be instantiated by In-VM container engine (Kubernetes and Kata container)
Impacted Lifecycle step	Operation (day-1 and day-2)	Design (day-0) and operation (day-1 & day-2)
Anticipated benefits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Higher compatibility Support for legacy appliance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Higher isolation In-situ actuation and monitoring of container instance Flexibility between reconfiguration options contributing to trade-off between security over-head and reconfiguration cost

2.4.4 Protocol description and alignment

Three configuration interfaces, illustrated in Figure 2-2, oversee interacting between the counter-measure recommender (CMR) and external iTrust6G components:

- **Int-Ev-Ss:** The interface shall convey a data structure from an iTrust6G component soliciting the deployment of a specific class of security enablers and contextual data (anticipated to be the remediation manager). The request is unidirectional and asynchronous.
- **Int-Dm-So:** This interface shall asynchronously convey information about the element to be deployed, either as a pointer when a pre-existing security control is available and to be instantiated directly by the security service orchestrator, or a blob containing the image of the resource to be immediately instantiated, in case an image had to be generated.
- **Int-So-Dm:** The interface shall periodically request the current network landscape and resource availability to gather information used by the CMR decisional process. The external iTrust6G component in interaction is anticipated to be the remediation recommender of the secure service orchestrator, depending on the further refinement of the security orchestrator architecture in WP5.

Conversely, the resource generator possesses the following interfaces to function:

- **Int-Ca-Rg:** This interface contains synchronous requests/responses between the resource generator and the catalogue to access descriptors of security mechanisms to be included in the resources.
- **Int-Dm-Rg:** The interface shall receive requests to build specific images enforcing certain security configurations by design and the list of modules to be integrated into the image to be instantiated.
- **Int-Rg-Dm:** The interface shall convey a descriptor of a generator image and the image of the container to be instantiated as a blob or a reference to it.

2.4.5 Specification alignment

The technical specifications alignments are described in Table 2-2.

Table 2-2 Specification Alignment for the Countermeasure Recommender and Resource Generator

Spec. ID	Description	Alignment
iTrust6G_FUN_GEN_010	Security control reconfigurations should not require downtime.	The pervasive security requirements featured by the resource generator offer the capacity to enforce security constraints during the design of the CNF to be protected or

		during its operations.
iTrust6G_FUN_GEN_009	Enable programmatic security orchestration across multiple domains in a 6G environment.	The security control to be deployed are programmed according to two different programmability models to satisfy the security orchestrator needs for enforcement.
iTrust6G_NOF_GEN_016	Apply a risk model to manage risks in security domains. Each resource in the network should be mapped into the model according to its characteristics and relation to other resources, pervasively integrating security mechanisms within the service design.	The catalogue identifies programmable enablers to be integrated into CNF images and the characteristics that drive the selection and image generation process.

2.4.6 Current implementation

As part of the current implementation, initial design and development work has been conducted on the CMR tool to proceed with the selection of adequate enablers to be deployed. The design currently enforces a static selection algorithm from the resource availability from the infrastructure to be protected, and from the characteristic from the security enablers to be implemented. This initial implementation work satisfies the needs of the legacy programmability models. Figure 2-3 presents an illustrative screenshot of the prototype. A more comprehensive design has been defined, to overcome several limitations of the initial prototype, such as (i) the hardcoded selection logic, and the (ii) support for resource generation to implement the pervasive generation framework. The initial prospective design has been conducted on the resource generator, which definition of the technical interface. To support this programmability model, a hybrid virtualisation model (OS-level virtualisation and system virtualisation) is to be implemented, using Kata container technology for resource operation.

```

Fichier  Édition  Affichage  Signets  Modules externes  Configuration  Aide

ssl.key.password = null
ssl.keymanager.algorithm = SunX509
ssl.keystore.certificate.chain = null
ssl.keystore.key = null
ssl.keystore.location = null
ssl.keystore.password = null
ssl.keystore.type = JKS
ssl.protocol = TLSv1.3
ssl.provider = null
ssl.secure.random.implementation = null
ssl.trustmanager.algorithm = PKIX
ssl.truststore.certificates = null
ssl.truststore.location = null
ssl.truststore.password = null
ssl.truststore.type = JKS
value.deserializer = class org.springframework.kafka.support.serializer.ErrorHandlingDeserializer

2025-02-22 14:58:58.736 INFO 56926 --- [          main] o.a.kafka.common.utils.AppInfoParser : Kafka version: 2.7.1
2025-02-22 14:58:58.737 INFO 56926 --- [          main] o.a.kafka.common.utils.AppInfoParser : Kafka commitId: 61dbce85d0d41457
2025-02-22 14:58:58.737 INFO 56926 --- [          main] o.a.kafka.common.utils.AppInfoParser : Kafka startTimeMs: 1740232738734
2025-02-22 14:58:58.741 INFO 56926 --- [          main] o.a.k.clients.consumer.KafkaConsumer : [Consumer clientId=consumer-CMR-1, groupId=CMR] Subscrib
ed to topic(s): cmr.requests
2025-02-22 14:58:58.768 INFO 56926 --- [ scheduling-1] n.i.c.o.iTrustGInfrastructureConnector : Retrieving the list of available SC from the catalogue .
...
2025-02-22 14:58:58.772 INFO 56926 --- [          main] net.i2cat.cmr.CmrApplication : Started CmrApplication in 6.148 seconds (JVM running for
6.907)
2025-02-22 14:58:58.775 INFO 56926 --- [          main] net.i2cat.cmr.CmrApplication : CMR init complete
2025-02-22 14:58:59.284 INFO 56926 --- [ scheduling-1] n.i.c.o.iTrustGInfrastructureConnector : ... done : read 5 registered security capabilities
2025-02-22 14:58:59.284 INFO 56926 --- [ scheduling-1] n.i.c.o.iTrustGInfrastructureConnector : Retrieving the list of available infrastructure configur
ations from the orchestrator ...
2025-02-22 14:58:59.317 INFO 56926 --- [ scheduling-1] n.i.c.o.iTrustGInfrastructureConnector : ... done : read 2 registered infrastructure configurati
ons
2025-02-22 14:58:59.453 INFO 56926 --- [ntainer#0-0-C-1] org.apache.kafka.clients.Metadata : [Consumer clientId=consumer-CMR-1, groupId=CMR] Cluster
ID: fYqh3W9eTPKdGI-x3n2SMA
2025-02-22 14:58:59.454 INFO 56926 --- [ntainer#0-0-C-1] o.a.k.c.c.internals.AbstractCoordinator : [Consumer clientId=consumer-CMR-1, groupId=CMR] Discover
ed group coordinator kafka:9092 (id: 2147483646 rack: null)
2025-02-22 14:58:59.458 INFO 56926 --- [ntainer#0-0-C-1] o.a.k.c.c.internals.AbstractCoordinator : [Consumer clientId=consumer-CMR-1, groupId=CMR] (Re-)joi
ning group
2025-02-22 14:58:59.480 INFO 56926 --- [ntainer#0-0-C-1] o.a.k.c.c.internals.AbstractCoordinator : [Consumer clientId=consumer-CMR-1, groupId=CMR] (Re-)joi
ning group
2025-02-22 14:58:59.484 INFO 56926 --- [ntainer#0-0-C-1] o.a.k.c.c.internals.AbstractCoordinator : [Consumer clientId=consumer-CMR-1, groupId=CMR] Successf
ully joined group with generation Generation{generationId=9, memberId='consumer-CMR-1-a880a60f-6f94-4f86-9659-55a55fbfa8df', protocol='range'}
2025-02-22 14:58:59.488 INFO 56926 --- [ntainer#0-0-C-1] o.a.k.c.c.internals.ConsumerCoordinator : [Consumer clientId=consumer-CMR-1, groupId=CMR] Finished
assignment for group at generation: 9: {consumer-CMR-1-a880a60f-6f94-4f86-9659-55a55fbfa8df=Assignment(partitions=[cmr.requests-0])}
2025-02-22 14:58:59.497 INFO 56926 --- [ntainer#0-0-C-1] o.a.k.c.c.internals.AbstractCoordinator : [Consumer clientId=consumer-CMR-1, groupId=CMR] Successf
ully synced group in generation Generation{generationId=9, memberId='consumer-CMR-1-a880a60f-6f94-4f86-9659-55a55fbfa8df', protocol='range'}
2025-02-22 14:58:59.498 INFO 56926 --- [ntainer#0-0-C-1] o.a.k.c.c.internals.ConsumerCoordinator : [Consumer clientId=consumer-CMR-1, groupId=CMR] Notifbyn
g assignor about the new Assignment(partitions=[cmr.requests-0])
2025-02-22 14:58:59.502 INFO 56926 --- [ntainer#0-0-C-1] o.a.k.c.c.internals.ConsumerCoordinator : [Consumer clientId=consumer-CMR-1, groupId=CMR] Adding n
ewly assigned partitions: cmr.requests-0
2025-02-22 14:58:59.519 INFO 56926 --- [ntainer#0-0-C-1] o.a.k.c.c.internals.ConsumerCoordinator : [Consumer clientId=consumer-CMR-1, groupId=CMR] Setting
offset for partition cmr.requests-0 to the committed offset FetchPosition{offset=0, offsetEpoch=Optional.empty, currentLeader=LeaderAndEpoch{leader=Optional[
kafka:9092 (id: 1 rack: null)], epoch=0}}
2025-02-22 14:58:59.521 INFO 56926 --- [ntainer#0-0-C-1] o.s.k.l.KafkaMessageListenerContainer : CMR: partitions assigned: [cmr.requests-0]
    
```

Figure 2-3 Screenshot of the current version of the CMR

A programmable API specification, which will help integration, will be provided in the next deliverables.

2.4.7 Future work

As part of future work, the CMR shall be extended to interface and integrate with the remediation recommender and the secure service orchestrator. We aim to complete the remediation workflow of the security orchestrator by selecting security enablers addressing the needs expressed by the remediation manager.

Moreover, the resource generator shall be implemented to permit the inclusion of security enablers in resources needing protection to contribute to implementing the pervasive security programmability model. A catalogue dedicated to storing enablers involved in resource generation shall be integrated from software taken off the shelves.

Finally, a policy format based on TOSCA shall be contemplated, supervising the needs in resource generation. However, this research will not address the use of TOSCA to elicit the remediation procedures.

2.5 Programmable Security Mechanisms

The advancement of Programmable Security Mechanisms is crucial in software-defined and virtualized security infrastructures.

2.5.1 State-of-the-art

This section reviews the current state-of-the-art in this domain, focusing on security supervision, orchestration, programmability, and trust management in security applications.

2.5.1.1 Supervision of security mechanisms in software-defined environments

Dynamically monitoring and adapting security controls is essential for maintaining robust defense mechanisms. Traditional security enforcement relies on monitoring static policies and perimeter-based protections, which are insufficient in software-defined infrastructure (SDI) environments, as those types of environments facilitate the rapid deployment of new services issuing, in return, new requirements for security monitoring.

Gu et al. [9] introduced S2OS, a security operating system for SDI, which abstracts security functions into a programmable control layer. This model enables dynamic security enforcement and fine-grained monitoring of applications. By leveraging SDI, S2OS allows security mechanisms to be deployed, adjusted, and managed centrally across an entire cloud or enterprise system. Similarly, Luo and Salem [10] proposed software-defined security orchestration, where security functions are represented as abstract security services, facilitating service-based security management that can adapt dynamically to changing network conditions.

These approaches demonstrate the importance of decoupling security enforcement from underlying infrastructure constraints, allowing for more adaptive and resilient security mechanisms.

2.5.1.2 Orchestration and programmability of security services

Orchestration frameworks enable automated security policy deployment across diverse environments. The TOSCA-oriented security approach proposed by Compastié et al. [11] integrates unikernel-based security components with programmable security policies. By leveraging TOSCA, security functions can be automatically deployed, modified, and reconfigured in response to evolving threats. This method improves the resilience and adaptability of security enforcement while minimizing attack surfaces.

Furthermore, Software-Defined Security (SDSec) models introduce programmable abstractions that enable

flexible policy enforcement. These models allow security policies to be dynamically adjusted based on threat intelligence and system context, ensuring that protection mechanisms remain effective against emerging attacks.

2.5.1.3 Programmable security mechanisms for trust management

Application security is increasingly being integrated into programmable frameworks to enhance trust management. The SysFlow framework introduced by Hong et al. [12] extends Zero Trust security principles to system-level controls, enabling fine-grained, programmable security enforcement. Unlike traditional Zero-Trust models focusing on network access control, SysFlow introduces system flow-based security policies that continuously monitor, verify, and adjust permissions based on real-time system behaviour.

Additionally, Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs) provide hardware-assisted isolation for security-sensitive applications. Sfyarakis and Gross [13] developed UniGuard, which enhances unikernel security by integrating Intel SGX (Software Guard Extensions). This approach ensures unikernels execute in isolated enclaves, protecting them from privileged attacks and malicious hypervisors. Similarly, Gramine [14] provides a framework for TEE-based execution, enabling applications to operate in a confidential computing environment with strong guarantees against data leaks.

By combining software-defined security orchestration with hardware-based trust mechanisms, these approaches enhance the programmability, adaptability, and integrity of security solutions.

2.5.2 Design challenges

The preparation of the programmable security mechanisms had to address the following design challenges:

- **Compatibility.** The programmable security enablers ensure compatibility for different classes of security enablers with the management layers. This challenge shall be addressed by exposing technical-agnostic interfaces and capability discovery features.
- **Support for synchronous & asynchronous interactions with management layers.** Conformance with security requirements relies on passive interactions from an enforcer (e.g., continuously streaming security metrics), and unitary enforcement actions (e.g., applying a configuration), but can also be active and issued from the mechanism (e.g., issuing request). In this context, a programmable interface should be able to provide different types of protocols exploiting the interfaces.
- **Re-Programmability.** As per the pervasive programmability model, the programmable security mechanism is expected to update its logic at operation time and shall therefore receive new actuators and monitoring capabilities to deploy.
- **Programmability by resource design.** Similarly, as per the pervasive programmability model, the programmable security mechanism is expected to be included at design time. The enforcement capability should, therefore, account for actions that affect the design of the resources themselves.
- **Support for in-situ decision-making.** To benefit from programmability models, mechanisms should be able to issue simple action obtained monitoring information and action capability.

2.5.3 Design approach

In this section, we detail the internal building block of programmable security enablers. Figure 2-4 provides an overview of the functional architecture from the perspective of the resource needing protection (typically, a CNF of a network service in the anticipated 6G environment). The interface between the programmable security enablers and the network service has been voluntarily omitted.

Figure 2-4 Programmable security enabler functional architecture

Several components are identified at play with the programmable security mechanisms listed below:

- **Components part of the resource needing protection**, existing without security programmability as considering hybrid container in virtual machine virtualisation model, the focus is the description on components accessible from the virtualised environment feature in this model:
 - **Running applications and services:** These correspond to running processes in the virtualised environment supporting the intent of the network function or acting as an ancillary subsystem of the runtime (e.g. system service). We assume that those processes produce relevant events and logs containing information relevant to security monitoring. Those processes can be (re-) instantiated with a different parametrisation (e.g. different arguments and environment variable).
 - **Configuration files:** These files constraints the behaviour of different aspect of the network function, from its application and service behaviour. They can be edited according to a certain logic.
 - **Guest operating system kernel:** In the case contemplated in T5.1, this is a lightweight and domain-specific operating system supporting a virtualised environment supported by OS-level virtualisation (i.e. application, service and configuration resources). To limit the scope of this research work, we avoid considering the guest operating system kernel as part of the programmed resource and focus on the two items listed above.
- Internal components of the **programmable security mechanism**, to be deployed in-situ of the instance needing protection:
 - **In-situ monitoring services:** This set of services scrutinises the posture of running applications and services and can issue a set of security metrics useful for security threat detection (security orchestration) and trust evaluation (trust management). These components are expected to be produced by T5.2 and taken off the shelves but need to be interfaced with the programmability interface to be configured and disclose the type of data they generate and the type of source of data they represent.
 - **In-situ actuator services:** This set of services oversees enforcing remediation issued by the

remediation recommender as security controls. In the context of programmable security mechanisms, they seek to alter and/or (re-) instantiate certain applications and configuration files to match the expected goals. Several actuator services are expected to be contributed, but they must be interfaced with the programmability interface to gain compatibility and integration in resource design.

- **Autonomic engine:** The autonomic engine provides a limited self-decision-making capacity to autonomously take decisions from perceived security monitoring information and initiate actuators, with the eventual goal of skipping the regular security loop and obtaining results on quick interaction. The considered design contemplates applying programmable Event-Condition-Action (ECA) rules to define its behaviour.
- **Programmability interface:** This sub-component coordinates and ensures communications between in-situ services and external security management (in iTrust6G architecture, this involves first interacting with the secure service orchestrator). Therefore, its missions include (i) translating incoming technically agnostic configuration for enforcement to a specification understandable by the actuators, (ii) receiving a logic implementing in-situ actuator to be deployed, (iii) facilitating the streaming of selected monitoring data to management, (iv) permitting the advertisement of available monitoring and enforcement capacity. This component shall be instantiated both during the operation phase of the resource to be protected from communication with the orchestration and during the resource-building phase to coordinate the integration of the mechanism in the design.

2.5.4 Protocol description

In Figure 2-4, solely one interface related to programmability is listed:

- **Int-PrSe-So:** The protocol ensures communication between the mechanism and the security orchestration through the service orchestrator. Specifically, the protocol shall permit the solicitation of several features from the security orchestration. The agent shall advertise the capabilities of deployed in-situ services to enact the management layer and understand the type of action that is possible to achieve. Plus, the protocol shall contribute to security monitoring by permitting data streaming to the security detection component. Reciprocally, it shall enforce security configuration issued by the security orchestration and supervise the deployment of an in-situ service it needs. The agent shall be able to receive revised ECA rules in the autonomic engine and issue synchronous requests to the management component (e.g., policy decision point).

2.5.5 Specification alignment

The technical specifications described are aligned as described in Table 2-3.

Table 2-3 Specification Alignment for the Programmable Security Mechanisms

Spec. ID	Description	Alignment
iTrust6G_FU N_GEN_009	Enable programmatic security orchestration across multiple domains in a 6G environment.	The programmable security mechanism achieves programmability by deploying in-situ service and requiring configuration during resource design or operation time.
iTrust6G_NO F_GEN_016	Apply a risk model to manage risks in security domains. Each resource in the network should be mapped into the model according to its characteristics and relation to other resources, pervasively integrating security	The programmable security mechanism permits integration at design time if requested. The Characteristic of in-situ services are mapped to a taxonomy of capability reflecting its characteristics and design.

	mechanisms within the service design	
iTrust6G_NO_F_GEN_018	Apply formal models to describe the automated configuration of networks and security controls	The programmability interfaces receive the formal model specification to conduct the configuration of security controls (here, in-situ actors services)
iTrust6G_FU_N_SP_009	Provide continuous trust evaluation and re-evaluation mechanisms for operational security of network services, computing resources, and users	The programmability interfaces allow the obtention of certain logs that are useful for evaluating the trust posture.
iTrust6G_FU_N_SP_014	Provide secure service design and delivery through smart slice provisioning and network functions placement. Assure application access to them through language-agnostic programmatic interfaces.	The programmability interface design enforces the use of a design technically agnostic interface to conduct the configuration of actuators.

2.5.6 Current implementation

An initial design of the programmable security mechanism has been issued that will act as a blueprint for its implementation, and the main interaction with the components of iTrust6G architecture has been identified. An initial set of endpoints have been defined as follows, to be tentatively accessible through a message-oriented middleware as described in Table 2-4.

Table 2-4 Endpoints for Programmable Security Mechanism

Endpoint name	Argument	Description
capabilities	None	Solicit the current security capabilities implemented by the mechanisms deployed in the resource
enforcement	An in-line security configuration to enforce	Receive a security configuration to enforce via the actuator service
services_deployment	A binary payload of the service to be deployed	Initiate the deployment of a service (monitoring or actuator) to enact a certain capacity needed by the orchestrator.
autonomic_rules_enforcement	A list of ECA rules to be inserted into the autonomic engine, and replacing the previously loaded	Insert ECA rules into the autonomic engine to control locally the decision making.

2.5.7 Future work

During the next period, this line of research will endeavour the following tasks:

- Implementation of the programmability interface with the different features listed. This work depends on the resource generator component from the CMR.
- Integration with the SIEM and vulnerability assessment framework and implementation of the subsequent drivers to make these components programmable.
- Integration with the Remediation Manager and integration of one security control.
- Implementation of the autonomic engine.

3 Service monitoring and security detection

The core objective of line of research focuses on developing a programmability interface to extract relevant security metrics that will identify and classify security events in 6G networks. This objective encompasses several key aspects, including the ability to perform vulnerability scans and identify the threat's surface and the vulnerabilities' severity. The development aims to identify and implement multi-modal metrics to better understand and optimize system components. Also, all these metrics will cover multiple dimensions, including programmability interfaces, compute resource runtime metrics, and other context-specific data points. Additionally, the objective includes the ability to instrument the agents to collect on-demand forensic data alongside other metrics like system vulnerabilities to comprehensively monitor and assess the security context and identify potential risks. The output is a set of specialized modules tailored for service monitoring, host monitoring, container monitoring, and security detection, emphasizing 6G-focused attacks and cloud-first deployments. This module will enable both proactive and reactive security measures through continuous metric analysis.

The objectives are identified to be the following:

- Monitor the status and performance of system services.
- Scan for vulnerabilities in the system and installed applications.
- Generate alerts for identified security threats.
- Collect and store relevant data following security incidents.
- Integrate external cybersecurity information sources to maintain an updated list of known security threats.
- Prioritize vulnerabilities based on severity and potential impact.
- Recommend remediation actions for identified vulnerabilities.
- Generate reports on security incidents and vulnerabilities.
- Implement secure communication protocols and access controls.
- Maintain logs of its activities, including security events.

3.1 Summary of the outcomes

This research activity has produced the following components, which are the major outcomes of this research activity are:

- Vulnerability Assessment Tool:
 - Developed a microservice that monitors the status of system services.
 - Developed a microservice that scans the system for vulnerabilities and prioritizes them
 - Developed a service that integrates and maintains external cybersecurity information from various sources
 - Developed a microservice that generates a STIX v2.1 JSON report
- Developed the initial version of the External Threat Database, which includes CTI from various sources.
- Improved Metadon SIEM, a log management solution designed for handling large volumes of information and implementing security incident handling functionalities at the local/edge level.

During this reporting period, we worked on improving the capability to process large volumes of events, extending the current event collector and storage system to support parquet files with in-memory correlation capabilities using arrow.

- Chimera, a Golang-based security monitoring tool, a comprehensive data collection and processing solution capable of gathering system logs and metrics and transforming them into semi-structured formats. It has been enhanced with advanced features through iTrust6G contributions, including remote orchestration capabilities via a secure API, network flow monitoring (Netflow and sFlow), and efficient Parquet format data exchange. The tool is being extended to support sophisticated system monitoring through eBPF integration, and it can perform on-demand forensic data collection, including memory dumps, logical disk imaging, and raw network packet capture.

3.2 Objectives and expected outcomes for the next reporting period

The objectives for the next reporting period include:

- Generate alerts for identified security threats;
- Implement secure communication protocols and access controls;
- Maintain logs of activities and security events;
- Present suggested actions to assist in mitigation recommendations.

From the SIEM part, we expect to finalize the alternative storage system with Parquet and give it real-time query streaming capabilities with ad-hoc correlations. They will then leverage existing Sigma rules and CTI data from the OpenCTI component to perform signature-based detection. Tighter orchestration capabilities from the SIEM to the Chimera agents allow them to be remotely controlled as they are and from a unifying web interface. Users could leverage AI Chat to interact with the system connection Large Language Model (LLM) with function / API calling capabilities.

On the Chimera agent front, we expect to extend integrations with helper third-party tools to allow for remote forensic artifact capture and expose those actions through the agent API to enable remote programmability and orchestration control. These include support for dynamic application of process memory monitoring through API deployment of Yara rules and API deployment of Snort rules for network traffic monitoring.

3.3 Overall presentation of the achievements

The described achievements involve deploying an integrated cybersecurity monitoring infrastructure with key components:

1. SIEM (Metadon) - Centralized security monitoring system aggregating and analyzing logs/metrics from distributed agents. Capable of real-time threat detection and automated response workflows.
2. Chimera Data Collection Agents - Deployed lightweight agents for multi-source telemetry collection:
 - Logs: System/application event logs from endpoints.
 - Metrics: Performance and security status indicators.
 - Raw Packets: Network traffic capture for deep inspection.
 - Supports hybrid infrastructure monitoring (cloud/on-premises).
3. High-Volume Event Processing Prototype - Achieves million+ events/sec throughput through:
 - Time-based windowing: Arrow-backed temporal buckets for streaming analytics.

- Columnar storage: Parquet formatting enables efficient compression/querying.
- Features API gateway for external access
- Structured query endpoints (SQL-like interfaces)
- Role-based access controls aligned with Zero Trust principles.

3.4 Vulnerability Assessment tool

3.4.1 State-of-the-art

There are several well-known vulnerability assessment tools ranging from open-source to commercial solutions. This section presents the most popular tools available and discusses their benefits and disadvantages.

1. *OpenVAS*: OpenVAS is a free, open-source vulnerability scanner designed to detect vulnerabilities in web applications, networks, and other infrastructure. It leverages a vulnerability database to identify security issues and supports multiple scanning engines, including Nmap and OpenVAS Scanner, for effective analysis.
2. *Qualys*: Qualys is a commercial cloud-based vulnerability management platform that delivers thorough security evaluations, threat identification, and compliance monitoring. It detects vulnerabilities across servers, endpoints, and web applications.
3. *Tenable Nessus*: Nessus is a commercial vulnerability scanner that identifies vulnerabilities in operating systems, applications, and network devices. It contains multiple vulnerability checks and customization options designed for super-users, integrates with threat intelligence sources, and provides detailed reports and remediation actions.
4. *Rapid7 Nexpose*: Nexpose is a commercial vulnerability management tool that assesses security vulnerabilities and risks across on-premises, cloud, and virtual environments. Its key features include asset discovery, vulnerability scans, risk prioritization, and remediation actions.
5. *Nmap*: Nmap is a free and open-source network scanning tool used to discover hosts and services on a network and identify potential vulnerabilities. Its main features include techniques like OS fingerprinting, port scanning, and service detection while supporting custom scripts in its own language.

Commercial vulnerability assessment tools offer comprehensive and well-tested evaluations. These tools typically rely on established threat intelligence regarding vulnerability entries, which might not fit the project's needs regarding 6G-specific vulnerabilities. The project requires various methods of vulnerability assessment, such as scanning the network externally and scanning containers/images, along with specific tests tailored to discover 6G-specific vulnerabilities. This would require using different commercial tools while configuring each one to perform specific actions. This could lead to a resource-heavy solution, compared to developing a tool to satisfy the project's needs. Additionally, a custom solution is easier to modify and extend, while using multiple commercial tools requires knowledge of multiple APIs and custom languages for scripting.

On the other end, open-source tools are accessible and customizable, allowing modifications to meet specific needs. However, open-source solutions can also face integration and interoperability issues similar to commercial tools. Furthermore, beyond-5G networks use Kubernetes as a deployment environment and open-source tools do not offer this as a deployment method. Even though an experienced user can convert

the Docker deployment to Kubernetes, the tool may not function correctly, as Kubernetes networking is often more sophisticated, and these tools rely on classic low-level networking infrastructure. Therefore, even open-source tools can't be used, as they lack Kubernetes as a deployment method.

The VA (Vulnerability Assessment) component of T5.2 addresses these issues by employing state-of-the-art techniques such as microservices architecture, which enables scalability and flexibility. Additionally, the module incorporates comprehensive asset and vulnerability management, which integrates the External Threat Database developed under the project's scope, to provide a complete understanding of a beyond-5G network's security posture. Finally, it supports deployment in a Kubernetes Cluster, which allows it to be more flexible in terms of where it can be deployed within the network.

3.4.2 Design approach and challenges

The VA component aims to provide vulnerability detection and mitigation capabilities tailored to the complex nature of beyond-5G/6G networks. The following principles comprise the design approach.

The tool is implemented using the microservices architecture. Each microservice is designed to perform a specific function, such as service detection and vulnerability scanning. This modular design ensures that components can be independently updated, scaled, or deployed.

All components of the VA tool are containerized using Docker, ensuring consistency and portability across different environments. Therefore, it can be easily deployed and managed in a Kubernetes environment.

The tool is designed to integrate with the 6G network functions, including the Radio Access Network (RAN) and Core Network (CN) nodes if required. It will also communicate with other project components, such as agents, to get device metrics.

The tool output will be a STIX JSON reporting all data discovered during the scanning process, including devices, services, vulnerabilities, and mitigation recommendations. Other components are designed to utilize these reports.

Incorporating vulnerability detection techniques to detect 6G-specific vulnerabilities can be a challenge, as there are not many 6G-specific vulnerabilities, and they may not be service-related. Therefore, in these cases, the approach should have a more targeted discovery process designed to discover these vulnerabilities.

3.4.3 Protocol description

The VA component will communicate with the following components to either receive input or produce output:

- The VA will receive information from the Service Orchestrator about the devices present on the network. This will include asset inventory information, such as IP, Device Hostname, MAC, and Open Ports, that will assist in the vulnerability assessment process.
- The output will be sent to the Security threat detection and classification component (T3.2) and Trust Inference (3.4). The output will be a STIX v2.1 JSON report containing:
 - Detected vulnerabilities and associated remediation recommendations.
 - Threat intelligence reports and indicators of compromise (IoCs).
 - Security posture assessments and risk scores.
 - Compliance and audit reports.

3.4.4 Specification alignment

The technical specifications described are aligned as described in Table 3-1.

Table 3-1 Specification Alignment for the Vulnerability Assessment Tool

Spec. ID	Description	Alignment
iTrust6G_FUN_GEN_003	Apply zero-trust principles by: (i) Continuously monitoring and evaluating the security posture of operated assets. (ii) Regularly assessing the integrity of the underlying infrastructure	The component performs vulnerability assessment scans on the network to identify any issues on the operated assets
iTrust6G_FUN_GEN_001	Support secure communication channels with strong encryption protocols between devices and backend systems to prevent data leakage and protect against eavesdropping and unauthorized access	The component incorporates secure protocols like HTTPS and TLS.
iTrust6G_FUN_SP_017	All interactions will be logged, for further accounting and/or auditing. Log entries will include identity properties used for authorization	The component logs its output and operations

3.4.5 Current implementation

3.4.5.1 Component architecture

The VA follows the microservices architecture chosen for flexibility and modularity. The microservices architecture breaks down the application into smaller, independent services responsible for a specific task and communicate with each other through a message broker (RabbitMQ⁴ in this case).

Figure 3-1 shows the current implementation of the VA component, which consists of the following microservices:

- Network discovery is the process of identifying all the devices on the network, including network functions, UEs, and network infrastructure devices. This procedure is accomplished using network scanning techniques, which can automatically identify devices and collect information about them, such as their IP address, hostname, MAC address, and open ports. This microservice will later be enriched using metrics from the agents deployed in the infrastructure.
- Service discovery is the process of identifying all the services running on open ports in each previously discovered device. This microservice utilizes open-source service fingerprint databases and matches these fingerprints with the responses received from each running service on the devices.
- Vulnerability assessment employs the External Threat Database's vulnerabilities and matches them to the discovered services.

⁴ <https://www.rabbitmq.com/>

Figure 3-1 VA architecture

3.4.5.2 Network discovery

The first step in vulnerability assessment is to identify the network's assets, including information about open ports and services. Therefore, a network discovery process is required to identify the network resources, including UEs, network functions, and their open ports. In the end, since various resources have different discovery procedures, they need diverse identification approaches. Consequently, several discovery components were created to find individual resources. This microservice utilizes `gopacket`⁵, an open-source Go library, which provides packet processing capabilities.

3.4.5.3 Asset discovery

The Asset discovery microservice collects information about devices discovered in the network, including their *IP address*, *MAC address*, and *hostname*. It uses two different techniques to achieve the best results.

- **ICMP Scan:** To find out which hosts are available and active on the network, ICMP Scan sends an Internet Control Message Protocol (ICMP/ICMPv6) echo request to various IP addresses. Depending on the response, the IP can be marked as active or not.
- **ARP Scan:** The process of making Address Resolution Protocol (ARP) queries to a range of IP addresses in order to ascertain which devices are connected to the network is known as "ARP scanning." This method works well and is advised for finding devices on the same subnet.

These two techniques can be combined to ensure all assets are marked correctly, depending on the subnet in which they are located.

⁵ <https://github.com/gopacket/gopacket>

3.4.5.4 Port discovery

After identifying the assets, it's important to find out which ports are open and what services are operating on these devices. Port scanning techniques can be employed to identify whether ports on a device are open. Since it enables the discovery of potential vulnerabilities connected to each service, this information is necessary for vulnerability assessments. A wide range of ports that will thereafter be utilized to identify their service can be scanned by the port discovery microservice. The following port discovery strategies are applied:

- **TCP SYN Scan:** This method sends TCP SYN packets to the most used ports to find out which ports on a device are open or closed. The port is open if a SYN/ACK packet is received in response. Similarly, receiving RST/ACK packet indicates that the port is closed. Since no connection is established, this method is rapid, effective, and stealthy.
- **UDP Scan:** this method sends UDP packets to the most used ports on the device to identify whether ports on a device are open. Finding services that might not react to TCP requests is made easier with the help of UDP scanning. An ICMP packet indicates that the port is closed, while a UDP response packet indicates that the port is open or filtered.

3.4.5.5 Service discovery

The second step in the vulnerability assessment process is service discovery, which makes it possible to identify network services that might be vulnerable. This microservice identifies services that are reachable from outside the machine. It makes use of the open ports that the port discovery procedure found. A port is prepared for connection if it is open. The service discovery microservice uses open-source fingerprint databases to determine which services use a specific port. It starts by sending a specific probe to a port, which, when it receives a response, tries to match that response with the data in the fingerprint database to determine which service is running.

Each service contains its name, version, and Common Platform Enumeration (CPE). CPE is a structured naming scheme provided by NIST's National Vulnerability Database (NVD)⁶, a well-known vulnerability repository. If the CPE does not define the version, the service discovery microservice provides a range of possible versions used during the vulnerability assessment phase.

3.4.5.6 Vulnerability assessment

The last step in creating the component's output is vulnerability assessment. This microservice correlates the vulnerabilities found in the External Threat Database to the services found. A standardized vulnerability presentation format called Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures (CVE) is used to display vulnerabilities. A CVE must have at least one Common Platform Enumeration (CPE) to be evaluated as true. The CPE entries' name, vendor, and version are compared to each CVE's requirements as part of the matching procedure. Then, if any services are vulnerable, they are associated with one or more vulnerabilities. Additionally, this microservice uses methods to find vulnerabilities unique to 6G that were found within the project's scope.

3.4.5.7 Threat intelligence report

The Report Management microservice will produce the output of the VA tool in the form of STIX v2.1 JSON. This report is comprised of multiple objects defined by STIX and referred to as STIX Domain Objects (SDOs). These Objects include:

⁶ <https://nvd.nist.gov/>

- **Bundle:** A Bundle is a collection of STIX Objects grouped together.
- **IPv4 Address:** The IPv4 Address object represents an IPv4 address expressed using CIDR notation
- **MAC Address:** The MAC Address object represents a Media Access Control (MAC) address.
- **Software:** The Software object represents high-level properties associated with software, including software services (name, CPE, version, vendor).
- **Vulnerability:** The Vulnerability object represents vulnerability as a CVE.
- **Attack Pattern:** The Attack Pattern object represents the MITRE tactics and techniques object.
- **Course of Action:** The Course of Action object represents the MITRE mitigation action object.
- **Relationship:** The Relationship object is used to link objects together.

Listing A-0-1 (Appendix A) shows an example of a STIX object produced by the Report Management.

3.4.6 Next Steps

The future work during the project's second year involves the development of the report microservice, which will produce the output of this component and the integration with other components. The report microservice will produce a STIX JSON report, including the other microservices' findings, while utilizing the External Threat Database to recommend mitigation actions and include them in the report. The integration with other components will include getting metrics about the devices, from the agents developed.

3.5 External threat database

The External Threat Database (ETB) aims to collect, correlate, and maintain Threat Intelligence from various sources. Given the nature of this component, which is a database, the design challenges from the research point of view are limited. Performance issues and scalability are the main problems that can be addressed in typical DB management scenarios. Also, the available techniques substitute the state-of-the-art, which are summarized in the next section, without the need for a separate section.

3.5.1 Design approach

The approach to designing the database is the following (and described later in Figure 3-2):

The ETB gathers data from NVD and MITRE and creates relations between them. Subsequently, it stays up-to-date by updating the sources regularly and using cron jobs.

The ETB utilizes ArangoDB, a NoSQL Graph Database with its own Query Language. Graph databases create relations between documents (nodes) using edges, thus making it easy to apply graph algorithms for searching.

All components of the ETB are containerized using Docker, ensuring consistency and portability across different environments. Therefore, it can be easily deployed and managed in a Kubernetes environment.

Components can request data from the ETB through a REST API or RabbitMQ queue. Querying in Arango Query Language (AQL) is, also, supported.

The tool is implemented using the microservices architecture. Each microservice is designed to perform a specific function. This modular design ensures that components can be independently updated, scaled, or deployed.

3.5.2 Specification alignment

The technical specifications alignments are presented in Table 3-2.

Table 3-2 Specification Alignment for the External Threat Database

Spec. ID	Description	Alignment
iTrust6G_FUN_GEN_001	Support secure communication channels with strong encryption protocols between devices and backend systems to prevent data leakage and protect against eavesdropping and unauthorized access	The component incorporates secure protocols like HTTPS and TLS.
iTrust6G_FUN_SP_017	All interactions will be logged, for further accounting and/or auditing. Log entries will include identity properties used for authorization	The component logs its output and operations

3.5.3 Current implementation

3.5.3.1 Component architecture

The ETB follows the microservices architecture, which communicates through RabbitMQ, while also incorporating CRON jobs to keep the database updated.

Figure 3-2 shows the current implementation of the ETB, which consists of the following sub-components:

- **ArangoDB** is a graph database that is used for storing the CTI data
- **Database Manager** is the microservice that handles the CRUD operations performed on the database
- **API** is the microservice that exposes endpoints for interacting with the database through HTTP and RabbitMQ
- **Scrapers** handle the update of the database through CRON jobs

Figure 3-2 External threat database architecture

3.5.3.2 Threat intelligence sources

The graph database currently includes and correlates the following sources:

- **NVD CVE (National Vulnerability Database - Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures):** A database that lists all publicly identified software and hardware vulnerabilities and assigns each one a unique identifier (CVE) along with information like impact and severity.
- **MITRE CWE (Common Weakness Enumeration):** A list of the different kinds of hardware and software weaknesses that can result in vulnerabilities, offering a framework for locating and fixing underlying security issues.
- **MITRE CAPEC (Common Attack Pattern Enumeration and Classification):** A list of typical attack methods that adversaries employ, with structured explanations to assist enterprises in understanding and preventing common exploitation tactics.
- **MITRE ATT&CK (Adversarial Tactics, Techniques, and Common Knowledge):** A knowledge base of cyber adversary behaviours, strategies, and tactics mapped to attack scenarios to assist organizations in improving threat detection and response.

3.5.3.3 Knowledge graph

Figure 3-3 presents the (abstract) connections in the knowledge graph that have been implemented in the graph database. Starting from a CVE, a mitigation action can be reached. CVEs are connected to CWEs by matching the weakness field to a known CWE. Then, CWEs are either connected to another CWE or CAPEC, depending on their abstraction type. Usually, only base abstraction types are allowed to be mapped to vulnerabilities; therefore, a CWE must link to another CWE until a base abstraction type is reached. Then, one or more CAPEC is linked to the CWE. The absorption type works similarly in CAPECs, which can be linked to one another until they are finally linked to an ATT&CK technique. Finally, the MITRE ATT&CK framework is well related on its own, so the relationships between the different ATT&CK objects are used.

Figure 3-3 Knowledge graph

3.5.4 Future work

During the project's second year, future work will include the integration of the MITRE FIGHT framework, which contains 5G-specific tactics, techniques, and mitigations and will also be spread to 6G. This integration will enrich the External Threat Database to better align with the project's scope. Furthermore, the API could be further developed to support more endpoints for querying the knowledge graph, depending on the needs of the other components.

3.6 Metadon – SIEM

3.6.1 State-of-the-art

SIEMs strongly rely on rules that define the inferences among data and the different correlations among data to be identified. Snort rules, YARA rules, and Sigma rules form a powerful triad of detection mechanisms across network, endpoint, and event-log domains. Their combined use covers a wide range of threats, from low-level malware signatures to high-level correlation of security events in SIEM systems. Nonetheless, each rule format has its own uses, strengths, and role in modern Zero-Trust architectures and cloud-native environments.

3.6.1.1 Snort rules

Snort rules are widely used for intrusion detection and prevention at the network level. They specify patterns to be searched in packet headers and payloads, helping detect known threats, scanning activities, or exploits. A core feature of Snort rules is the ability to define both context (e.g., protocol, port, flags) and content (e.g., known signatures). Modern implementations integrate Snort rules into containers or virtualized network functions, letting operators scale detection capacity and handle distributed network topologies. These capabilities align with the goal of continuous detection and mitigation in a zero-trust setting, where network traffic is constantly monitored to identify threats before they proliferate.

Snort rules rely on contextual parameters—such as protocol, port number, or TCP flags—to narrow the inspection scope and specify how each packet should be handled while scanning packet payloads for known signatures or malicious data patterns [15]. This dual focus on context and content allows for flexible rule sets and precise threat detection. Operators can customize these rules to trigger alerts or block hostile traffic in real-time, mitigating threats like DDoS attacks and port scans, and exploit attempts before they escalate [16].

Modern deployments often package Snort within container or microservice environments, which streamlines rule updates, decentralizes the detection process, and easily scales capacity as network traffic fluctuates [17]. Containerized or virtualized network functions are particularly beneficial for distributed topologies, allowing multiple Snort instances to handle different subnet segments or application tiers. These instances can be orchestrated dynamically, making responding to rising threats easier and adjusting resources where intrusion risk is highest. In a zero-trust environment, continuous monitoring across all layers is a necessity since the network is treated as inherently hostile, and each entity must always be re-verified [18].

By combining Snort's fine-grained rule definitions with container-based scaling, administrators can enforce strict segmentation of network resources and apply real-time inspection rules at every hop. This approach helps maintain minimal trust boundaries, ensuring that potential intrusions are discovered and halted as early as possible while preserving the agility needed for ever-evolving infrastructures.

Sample of what a snort rule looks like:

```
alert tcp $EXTERNAL_NET any -> $HOME_NET 3389 (msg:"Potential RDP Brute Force";  
flow:to_server,established; threshold:type threshold, track by_src, count 5, seconds 60; sid:1000004;)
```

This rule detects potential RDP brute force attacks by tracking connection attempts from external sources. The rules consist of:

- *Action (alert, log, drop)* – the action to take when the trigger is activated.
 - *alert*: Generates an alert and logs the packet when rule conditions are met;
 - *log*: Only records the packet to the logging system;
 - *drop*: Blocks the packet and logs it (only in IPS mode).
- *Protocol* – Determines which protocol-specific options are available for inspection.
 - Specifies which protocol to monitor (tcp, udp, icmp, ip).
- *Source IP/Port* - The source IP Address and TCP/UDP port
 - Can be a single IP, CIDR block, or variable (e.g., \$EXTERNAL_NET). The ports can be a specific number such as 80 or a range like 1:1024 which means ports from 1 to 1024.
- *Direction operator* - Helps specify the flow of traffic being monitored.
 - -> indicates unidirectional traffic (source to destination);
 - <> indicates bidirectional traffic monitoring.
- *Destination IP/Port* – The destination IP Address and tcp/udp port
 - Can be a single IP, CIDR block, or variable (e.g., \$EXTERNAL_NET). The ports can be a specific number such as 80 or a range like 1:1024 which means ports from 1 to 1024.
- *Rule options in parentheses* – What is inside parentheses at the end of the rule (`msg:"Web Attack"; content:"exploit"; sid:1000001;`)
 - *msg*: Alert message to display;
 - *content*: Pattern to match in packet payload;
 - *sid*: Unique signature identifier;
 - *flow*: Specifies direction and state of connection;
 - *threshold*: Controls alert frequency.

3.6.1.2 Yara rules

YARA rules still stand as a cornerstone in modern cybersecurity, serving as a powerful pattern-matching framework that continues to evolve with the changing threat landscape. Their enduring relevance stems from their remarkable adaptability and precision in identifying malicious patterns across diverse digital environments. At its core, YARA operates through sophisticated pattern matching, enabling security professionals to create detailed descriptions of malware families based on textual or binary patterns. The framework excels in detecting complex threats, including steganographic malware and sophisticated attack vectors that traditional security tools might miss. The system's architecture allows for granular control over detection parameters. Security teams leverage YARA rules to monitor network traffic, analyse suspicious files, and respond to emerging threats. Security analysts can craft rules that detect sophisticated attack patterns, including those employing steganography to hide malicious payloads within seemingly innocent files. The framework supports complex conditions and pattern matching, enabling the detection of encrypted malware, polymorphic code, and other advanced threats that might evade conventional security measures. Recent developments have focused on enhancing performance in high-speed networks and improving integration

with machine learning systems.

YARA rules follow a clear, logical structure that combines flexibility with precision. Here's an example of a basic rule configuration [19]:

```
rule MalwareExample {
  meta:
    description = "Detects specific malware variant"
    author = "Security Researcher"
    date = "2025-01"
  strings:
    $suspicious_pattern = "malicious_string"
    $hex_pattern = { 4D 5A 90 00 }
  condition:
    $suspicious_pattern or $hex_pattern
}
```

Rules are written with three components:

- *meta*: Contains descriptive information about the rule, such as author, date of creation or last time it was updated;
- *strings*: Defines the patterns to match; Might those be strings or even hexadecimal patterns;
- *condition*: Where the logic for triggering the rule is defined.

3.6.1.3 Sigma rules

"Today, everyone collects log data for analysis. People start working on their own, processing numerous white papers, blog posts and log analysis guidelines, extracting the necessary information and build their own searches and dashboard. Some of their searches and correlations are great and very useful but they lack a standardized format in which they can share their work with others." (From the main repository of Sigma Rules⁷).

Sigma is a community-driven, open-ended format for creating detection rules that can be used across diverse Security Information and Event Management (SIEM) systems. These rules take a human-readable approach to describing log patterns, enabling security analysts to develop and share threat detection signatures independent of any specific SIEM vendor. This portability makes them highly effective in modern environments where logs originate from myriad systems and network infrastructures.

The code presented below provides an overview of the Sigma rule format and its application in security monitoring systems. Here's an explanation of the elements:

Sigma Format:

- *detection_rule.yml*: Represents a file containing detection rules in the Sigma format, which is a generic, shareable format for defining rules to detect security threats;
- Sigma rules are YAML-based, making them readable and portable across different tools and platforms.

Rule Packs:

- These are collections of Sigma rules created by the community. They are reusable and designed to be platform-agnostic, enabling widespread adoption.

⁷ <https://github.com/SigmaHQ/sigma>

Sigma Converter:

- A tool or component that converts Sigma rules into queries compatible with specific Security Information and Event Management (SIEM) tools. This ensures that Sigma rules can be applied in diverse environments.

Below is a concise example of a Sigma rule in YAML, demonstrating typical fields and a short annotation for each:

```
title: Suspicious Process Creation
id: f2a2b9308493-11ec-a8a30242ac120002
description: Detects a process launching with uncommon command-line parameters
status: experimental
author: Security Analyst
date: 2023/01/15
logsource:
  product: windows
  service: security
detection:
  selection:
    - EventID: 4688
      CommandLine: contains
        - "-encodedcommand"
  condition: selection
level: high
tags:
  - attack.execution
  - attack.t1059
```

This Sigma rule, titled "Suspicious Process Creation" detects processes launched with uncommon command-line parameters. The ID f2a2b930-8493-11ec-a8a3-0242ac120002 uniquely identifies it and is currently marked as being experimental, denoting it is still in the stage of development.

It monitors logs from Windows Security for Event ID 4688, which records details about newly created processes. Specifically, it looks for instances where the command line includes the string-encoded command, often indicative of malicious or obfuscated commands.

The rule is categorized with a high severity level, signalling a significant threat if triggered. It is also tagged with MITRE ATT&CK techniques, including *attack.execution* and *attack.t1059*, which relate to execution techniques used by attackers.

3.6.2 Design challenges

3.6.2.1 6G networks log collection

The huge velocity and volume of network-generated data can overwhelm traditional log collection systems, especially when dealing with terabytes of new entries each day. Maintaining near real-time insights under these conditions requires cost-effective solutions that balance speedy ingestion with efficient storage. The challenge becomes even more complex when logs must be gathered from edge devices, intermediate platforms such as Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC), and centralized clouds. Ensuring consistency and reliability in this distributed world demands flexible log collection frameworks to unify diverse data sources while adapting to variable network conditions.

3.6.2.2 Real-time analytics

Real-time analytics imposes further demands. Logs need on-the-fly processing that supports immediate detection of security issues, out-of-baseline anomalies and predictive capabilities. This sort of instant responsiveness calls for systems capable of scaling up and down quickly to handle unpredictable surges in log volume. Moreover, seamless data interoperability grows increasingly essential, as logs often feed AI/ML pipelines for specialized tasks like network optimization. The ability to adapt to changing data schemas while preserving existing workflows helps guarantee that critical analytics initiatives continue functioning without interruption.

3.6.3 Design approach

3.6.3.1 Parquet for disk storage in distributed systems

Using Parquet as the disk storage format in highly distributed log collection addresses the need for both efficient storage and analytics. Columnar storage supports heavy compression, reducing storage overhead for massive log datasets and speeding up analytical queries by reading only necessary columns. This aligns with the frequent schema changes in 5G/6G logs, as Parquet can adapt to new fields without breaking existing data. It also integrates well with distributed storage systems, making it feasible for large-scale deployments across private and public clouds. A typical scenario involves a 6G log collection system capturing RAN and Core logs from multiple sources, batching them into Parquet files in an object store, and using distributed query engines for analysis.

3.6.3.2 Apache arrow for in-memory processing

Apache Arrow complements Parquet by specifying an in-memory columnar format, eliminating serialization overhead and enhancing CPU efficiency during log processing. Because Arrow provides zero-copy interoperability among different analytics frameworks, data can be transferred directly without costly format conversions. Its optimization for CPU cache locality further boosts performance, which is especially important for near real-time analytics in 6G environments. AI/ML models for anomaly detection, predictive maintenance, and traffic classification benefit from this in-memory speedup. An example use case at the edge might see logs streamed from base stations into an Arrow-based buffer, then processed immediately by AI models looking for performance anomalies.

3.6.3.3 Agent-based collection

Chimera serves as a versatile log collection agent designed to operate across diverse infrastructure environments, from traditional VMs and bare metal servers to containerized workloads in Docker and Kubernetes. Its lightweight and modular architecture makes it particularly suitable for 6G network environments where logs must be collected from heterogeneous sources.

The Agent Architecture supports the following features:

- The core collector is written in Golang to provide a minimal resource footprint and high performance⁸.
- Pluggable input modules support various log sources and formats.
- Pluggable extensions are used to perform disk, memory, and network data acquisition when deployed with root privileges or the right security capabilities.

⁸ <https://gitlab.pdmfc.com/chimera/metago>

- Buffer management for efficient memory utilization.
- Parquet writer for local caching when network connectivity is intermittent and retry systems to seamless (without human intervention) reconnection.
- Direct file system access for reading log files
- System metrics collection through native OS APIs
- Support for standard logging protocols (syslog, journald)

3.6.3.4 eBPF collection for Kubernetes

eBPF technology revolutionizes Kubernetes monitoring by enabling deep system observability directly at the kernel level. Through Cilium's⁹ implementation, we can capture detailed system call information and network behaviour without modifying application code or compromising performance. This kernel-level instrumentation provides visibility into container workloads while maintaining minimal overhead. The core strength of eBPF-based monitoring lies in its ability to intercept and analyse system calls efficiently. Using BPF CO-RE (Compile Once, Run Everywhere) technology, the monitoring system attaches to kernel hooks to capture system calls in real time. This approach enables the collection of both L7 and L4 layer protocol interactions, supporting throughputs exceeding 10 million operations per second. The eBPF monitoring system maintains full awareness of container contexts in Kubernetes environments. It monitors pod-level virtual ethernet interfaces and correlates network packets with specific cluster workloads, independent of the chosen Container Network Interface (CNI).

Cilium is open-source software for transparently securing the network connectivity between application services deployed using Linux container management platforms like Docker and Kubernetes.

For eBPF collection on pods, we leverage cilium capabilities and control them through the chimera agent. When deploying the kernel probes, we make it so they log the information back to chimera. There, we can transform and normalize fields, tag them with timestamps if needed and forward the data to the SIEM collector.

3.6.3.1 Time-based chunks

Since the collected data and metrics are all time-sensitive, and since the source datetime was captured or generated if of the utmost relevance for determining the incidents, we leverage this to split the data into buckets at the SIEM collector. It will split data by source, sourcetype, time window and filesize. The collector will store the records in memory using the arrow format and create a set of buckets per source that will immediately have a start and end time (normally 1d later from start time) considered *hot* (that is, very relevant for the analysis). When new events arrive at the collector, they are written in an available hot bucket (a bucket containing relevant events) whose time windows contain the event time; if the event has no time the ingestion time will be used instead. If no hot bucket exists, we open a new bucket with a start time equal to the event time minus a predefined small delta (for tolerance purposes), assuming logs and events are mostly received in order. If more than three hot buckets are open for a given source and index, the oldest (meaning the one we wrote to longer ago) is closed for a new open to be opened.

This technique performs well when processing in-order events but might create bucket trashing if too many out-of-order events are received. We have explored multiple possibilities for fixing it that will be implemented in the next versions of the tool. First, we can start by tweaking the tolerance, meaning we can increase the delta for bucket start time by configuration. This would make the bucket start much earlier than

⁹ <https://docs.cilium.io/en/stable/>

a received out-of-order event, causing it to be able to accommodate more events. Secondly, we can change the number of max open buckets per source and increase it to a higher value, which would theoretically reduce trashing. Thirdly, we can make an exponential delta in scenarios where trashing is detected, allowing the problem to be half-fixed. The latter option has the downside that it could excessively increase the bucket time window.

As a mitigation strategy, a make-it-compact phase is offered, where multiple buckets are merged into a single bucket. Experimentally the max size an on-disk parquet bucket compress with snappy or lz should be around 100MB up to 1GB. If the size is too small, too many buckets will be generated causing performance problems later when querying them for statistics or data. For example, on a recent Zen 4 Epyc server with NVME disks, the cost of opening 1200 buckets and just read their metadata to count the number of records comes to around 0.45 seconds. When said buckets are merged at 20-1 the time it takes to count reduces to less than 0.02 seconds. If the size is too big, we consume too much memory to query the data.

Figure 3-4 Time-based chunks flow

Figure 3-5 Compaction phase

When performing compaction, we measured the performance of doing it in memory using the same server, and it came down to about 1GB/s of processed data. This is limited by the disk speed, which clocks around 2.6GB/s. We pay the disk tax when reading (once per bucket) and when writing (once per merged bucket). But at the expense of memory, which balloons up to 115% of the size of the data processed. Alternatively, we can perform the merge in chunks; this is a lot slower experimentally; we find it to be around 4 times slower, or about 250MB/s. But the memory requirements are kept low to around 500 MB no matter the size of the bucket involved.

3.6.4 Protocol description

3.6.4.1 Protocol-optimised data ingestion

The protocol enforces strict schema-first ingestion, requiring all incoming logs to conform to predefined Apache Arrow schemas within a few ms of entry being created. Each RecordBatch undergoes automated metadata tagging (source IP, timestamp, source type) and other metadata provided by the agents that collect them. Invalid records trigger real-time quarantine workflows while maintaining high ingestion uptime via disc-mapped failover buffers.

3.6.4.2 Vectorized processing core

Leveraging Arrow's SIMD-enabled kernels, the protocol executes multiple parallel operations for field transformations (regex extraction, type casting). A just-in-time compiler converts filtering rules into

optimized stack-based bytecode, achieving 1 million events/sec throughput on x86 architectures.

3.6.4.3 Adaptive storage tiering

Local persistence follows a tiered Parquet strategy:

- Hot data (last 60 min): Uncompressed in-memory row groups for instant querying
- Warm data (by default 30 days): Zstandard compression (level 3) with dictionary encoding, or snappy
- Cold data (30+ days): Zstandard compression + column delta encoding
- A background compactor reorganizes files into optimal 128 MB chunks, reducing small-file overhead

3.6.5 Specification alignment

The technical specifications alignments are presented in Table 3-3.

Table 3-3 Specification Alignment for the Metadon SIEM

Spec. ID	Description	Alignment
iTrust6G_FUN_GEN_001	Support secure communication channels with strong encryption protocols between devices and backend systems to prevent data leakage and protect against eavesdropping and unauthorized access	TLS and SSL used for communication between components
iTrust6G_FUN_GEN_003	(i) Continuously monitoring and evaluating the security posture of operated assets.	Collects metrics, logs, and network data from the multiple devices deployed in the network
iTrust6G_FUN_GEN_004	Apply strong encryption in all management and orchestration channels, and any other side channel in use	TLS and SSL used for orchestration communication
iTrust6G_FUN_GEN_006	Provide near real-time alerts for critical threats and potential security incidents	Performs real-time detection and provides the basis for incident response
iTrust6G_FUN_GEN_007	Support interactive and dynamic visualization of the generated timelines, allowing correlation between events, zoom into specific time periods, and directly link each event to its source	Provides GUI capabilities for humans to analysis incident artifact data, such as logs and alerts
iTrust6G_FUN_GEN_008	Support the processing of large volumes of diverse digital evidence data	Processes millions of events per second
iTRUST6G_FUN_SP_011	Collected data shall be properly managed through cleaning, normalisation and transformation techniques.	Provides a set of functions to parse and normalize data, while keeping the identities in check
iTrust6G_FUN_SP_017	All interactions will be logged for further accounting and/or auditing. Log entries will include identity properties used for authorisation	Keeps audit records for all identity based accesses

3.6.6 Current implementation

Chimera's integration with Parquet and Arrow creates an efficient data pipeline:

1. **Log Collection:** Raw logs are parsed directly into Arrow Record Batches, enabling efficient in-memory processing. Metadata enrichment occurs dynamically within Arrow's columnar format, eliminating serialization overhead. Strict schema validation is applied at this stage to enforce data consistency before further processing.
2. **Local Processing:** Arrow's zero-copy transformations allow lightning-fast manipulations without data duplication. On-device aggregations reduce dataset sizes by up to 70% before transmission, while real-time filters and pattern-matching engines scan logs at wire speed using vectorized operations.

3. **Storage and Forwarding:** Processed data leverages **Parquet** for compressed columnar local caching (achieving ~90% storage savings). For live systems, records stream in Arrow's binary format with sub-millisecond serialization. Adaptive batching dynamically adjusts payload sizes (1–100 MB) based on real-time network latency and throughput metrics.

3.6.7 Next Steps

Future work integrating Zero Trust Architecture (ZTA) principles with real-time security detection systems in 6G environments, will be focused on following main areas, namely:

1. **Unified threat detection:** Create a dynamic rule orchestration system integrating Sigma/YARA/Snort rules with streaming analytics. Develop ML models that automatically generate composite detection rules by correlating Sigma (log patterns), YARA (binary patterns), and Snort (network patterns) signatures. Implement a feedback loop where detected threat patterns automatically refine rule thresholds and weights using streaming query. Containerized detection modules that automatically deploy rules at network edges when ZTA device posture changes.
2. **Dynamic Monitoring:** We aim to automate dynamic remote monitoring through the existing orchestration layers. But to better clarify what we expect to be possible, we present a tentative workflow instead of a high-level description, which we believe can leave too much room for interpretation and not present a clear picture.
 - a. SIEM detects suspicious login patterns (Sigma rule match) or via existing eBPF probes, like unusual process trees or excessive network flows detected.
 - b. Triggers YARA memory scan on affected endpoints via Chimera API.
 - c. Simultaneously deploys temporary Snort rules to monitor traffic.
 - d. All actions logged as verifiable transactions that can later be auditable.
 - e. Indicators forwarded to other components to revise trust scores and general security posture.

Figure 3-6 Unified threat detection

3. 6G Enhancements: Specific improvements should be available to 6G networks when the integration with other iTrust6G modules is complete, noteworthy:
 - a. Integrate Trusted Platform Module (TPM)-based attestation to validate the integrity of network functions (e.g., CU/DU components).
 - b. Leverage Snort rule profiles tailored per network slice to optimize threat detection.
 - c. Embed YARA scanners within Distributed Unit (DU) and Centralized Unit (CU) architectures using eBPF to inspect kernel/network activity without kernel module dependencies.
 - d. Implement auto-adjusting Sigma rule thresholds based on slice criticality.

4 AI Involvement in Security Orchestration

One of the primary objectives of the research in iTrust6G is to advance AI-driven security orchestration by integrating automation, Graph Neural Networks (GNNs), and real-time threat correlation techniques to improve threat intelligence analysis, classification, and mitigation. This research activities focuses on enhancing cybersecurity workflows by leveraging the Orchestrator Engine and the AI Correlation Engine, which facilitates OpenCTI playbooks and advanced AI methodologies for more effective threat detection and response.

Key objectives include:

- *Automation and Orchestration*: Implementing AI-powered automation in security workflows to reduce manual intervention and increase incident response efficiency.
- *Threat Correlation and Analysis*: Developing an advanced threat intelligence correlation model using GNNs to discover hidden attack patterns and identify relationships between cyber entities such as IoCs, vulnerabilities, and threat actors.
- *Automated Reporting*: Generating structured security reports in STIX format, integrating AI-driven insights to provide actionable intelligence to security analysts.
- *Forwarding to the Remediation Manager*: Ensuring that detected threats are forwarded with prioritized risk assessments and mitigation strategies, facilitating automated security enforcement.

4.1 Summary of the outcomes

The following outcomes have been achieved, aligning with the objectives:

- Development of an engine for the correlation of various cyber threat data (IoCs, vulnerabilities, and malware) and the improved detection of attack patterns and relationships among threat actors, leveraging advanced AI techniques.
- Automated STIX-Based Reports: The system generates structured reports enriched with threat actor relationships and attack techniques, facilitating proactive threat mitigation.
- Seamless Integration with OpenCTI: The framework is fully integrated with OpenCTI, leveraging STIX/TAXII standards for structured threat intelligence exchange.
- Real-Time Threat Intelligence Processing: Implemented workflows to dynamically query and update threat intelligence using automated playbooks.

4.2 Objectives and expected outcomes for the next reporting period

The next phase will further refine AI-based threat correlation and improve orchestration scalability. The key objectives include:

- Integration of AI Models for Threat Correlation: Implement GNNs (e.g. GCN, GAT, GraphSAGE) to analyse relationships between cybersecurity entities, improving cyber situational awareness. Different GNN architectures, such as heterogeneous GNNs and Graph Transformers, will be investigated for more advanced cyber-attack path analysis and link prediction, to identify potential attack vectors before they materialize.
- Develop seamless integrations with other cybersecurity tools and platforms through standardized protocols (e.g., STIX, TAXII, RESTful APIs).
- Scalability Improvements: Optimize the security orchestrator's architecture to handle large-scale

threat intelligence processing efficiently.

- Investigation of Lightweight LLMs (FLAN-T5): Evaluate using lightweight LLMs for extracting actionable insights from unstructured security data.
- Graph Database Integration as a Knowledge Graph: Explore graph databases to efficiently store and retrieve threat intelligence correlations for improved querying performance.

4.3 Achievements

4.3.1 Data ingestion from CTI platform via Webhooks

The CTI platform created within WP3 is our primary source of CTI data. It sends real-time notifications through webhooks when new suspicious observables, threats or IoCs are ingested or updated. T5.3 listens to these webhooks and fetches the corresponding data from OpenCTI's API using custom Python scripts. This continuous ingestion of CTI data ensures rapid awareness of evolving threats, which is crucial for detecting and mitigating back-to-back distributed attacks targeting operational services.

4.3.2 Data preprocessing

Once the webhook data is received, it goes through data parsing and transformation, if necessary. This might involve:

- extracting key information like IoCs;
- validating the data (e.g., checking the format of indicators);
- parsing the IoCs (like IP addresses, URLs, domains, file hashes);
- normalization of the data (standardizing formats, removing duplicates); and
- tagging the data (e.g., classifying threats, associating indicators with specific threat actors or campaigns) with ad hoc models.

4.3.3 AI correlation engine

The core of our system is the AI Correlation Engine. This is where the ingested CTI data is ingested to detect patterns, classify threats, and apply ML algorithms for deeper insights.

Figure 4-1 High-level architecture of the messaging broker

4.3.3.1 OpenCTI's automated playbooks

This implementation aims to leverage OpenCTI's playbooks functionality to automate the correlation of CTI data when new IoCs, malware, Tactics, Techniques, and Procedures (TTPs), CVEs and threat actors are created or updated. This process ensures enriched intelligence, enabling faster detection and response. The correlation logic with playbooks is to resolve first-degree relationships between entities using predefined rules. When an entity such as an IoC, malware, TTP, or CVE is created or updated, the playbooks trigger automated actions, including the generation of reports with enriched intelligence and the dispatch of webhook notifications to external systems

4.3.4 Graph-based neural networks (GNNs)

GNNs are well suited for threat correlation because CTI data is often interrelated. For example, a malicious IP might be linked to a particular domain, which in turn is associated with a specific campaign. GNNs can learn from these interconnections and classify new threats, going beyond OpenCTI's correlation capabilities. CTI data can be represented as a graph, where nodes represent entities (e.g., IoCs, threat actors, campaigns), and edges represent relationships (e.g., "connected to" or "used by"). For example, if a new IoC is detected (e.g., a malicious IP), GNNs can help predict its relationship to existing threats, alerting you to previously unknown connections or risks. Feature engineering is also considered for GNNs; node features could include properties of the IoCs (e.g., IP address, type, associated report), and edge features might include metadata about relationships (e.g., "communication", "delivery method"). GNNs can classify threat types, predict the severity of IoCs, or identify emerging campaigns based on the data. Once the data is processed through these models, you could classify threats into categories like malware families (e.g., Lumma Stealer); exploit types (e.g., remote code execution); tactics, techniques, and procedures (TTPs) following the MITRE ATT&CK framework. This classification aids in recognizing and mitigating repeated attack attempts in real time.

The ability of GNNs to learn directly from the graph-structured nature of STIX data allows us to move beyond simple feature-based correlations. While other methods, such as Bayesian Networks and traditional machine learning algorithms, offer certain advantages, GNNs' scalability and robustness to noise, make them well-suited for handling the large and often inconsistent datasets typical of collaborative threat intelligence environments. Additionally, we recognize the potential of Reinforcement Learning (RL) in dynamically optimizing correlation strategies and adapting to evolving threat landscapes. As part of our future work, we intend to explore integrating GNNs with ensemble techniques and RL approaches to enhance predictive accuracy and robustness by combining insights from multiple models and perspectives, leveraging both structured data analysis and adaptive decision-making capabilities.

4.3.5 Forwarding to message broker

The next step is to promote the findings to other components for further processing, like reporting systems, other security tools, or incident response platforms. This is where RabbitMQ comes in. Our system that performs the CTI analysis acts as the producer of messages. After analysing the data, the results (e.g., the new threat data, identified relationships, and IoC details) will be published in a RabbitMQ queue. Other systems (such as the Remediation Manager) act as consumers, consuming messages from RabbitMQ for further action.

4.3.6 CTI data ingestion

We have designed an automation solution to handle and process incoming threat intelligence data from OpenCTI, including indicators such as IPs, malware, CVEs, TTPs, and reports. The solution involves setting up a webhook listener using FastAPI, querying OpenCTI's API to fetch detailed data, and subsequently publishing the results to RabbitMQ for further processing. In Appendix B, we provide an overview of each step involved

in this automation flow in Listing A-0-2.

4.4 AI correlation engine

The AI Correlation Engine integrates OpenCTI’s automated playbooks with GNNs to streamline threat intelligence processing and enhance cyber defence. Automated playbooks leverage STIX/TAXII and MITRE ATT&CK frameworks to process and correlate threat data autonomously, facilitating quick detection and response. The playbooks enable real-time analysis and action by linking threat entities such as IoCs, malware, CVEs, and attack techniques. GNNs improve the correlation by analysing the complex relationships between entities. GNNs will be used to detect indirect connections, assign threat risk scores, and predict future attack patterns, providing deeper insights into ongoing and emerging threats.

4.4.1 State-of-the-art

4.4.1.1 Automated playbooks

Automated threat intelligence workflows have become essential in modern cybersecurity operations. OpenCTI’s approach aligns with industry’s best practices, leveraging STIX/TAXII, MITRE ATT&CK, and other frameworks for structured intelligence sharing. Playbooks and automation are becoming standard in security orchestration and CTI platforms, allowing organizations to process vast amounts of threat data efficiently.

Compared to traditional threat intelligence platforms, OpenCTI provides:

- More structured intelligence sharing with STIX/TAXII.
- Stronger automation capabilities through its playbooks.

4.4.1.2 Graph neural networks (GNNs)

For further analysis and advanced correlation of CTI and automation, our solution plans to leverage GNNs. GNNs have emerged as a powerful tool for analyzing CTI data, enabling deeper insights into structured cybersecurity datasets such as STIX-formatted threat reports. Cybersecurity datasets are inherently relational, where various threat entities (e.g., malware, IP addresses, CVEs, TTPs) form interconnected networks of attack behaviors. Conventional correlation methods rely on rule-based detection or statistical analysis, which can be inflexible and unable to generalize to unseen threats. GNNs overcome these limitations by learning latent representations of cyber entities and their relationships, improving automated threat detection, adversarial behaviour modelling, and risk assessment [20].

PyTorch Geometric (PyG), a widely adopted deep learning framework for modelling and analysing graph-based data, is explored to implement graph-based cyber threat correlation. PyG provides a comprehensive suite of GNN models, enabling the system to identify, predict, and correlate complex attack patterns based on real-world threat intelligence.

Once STIX data is converted into a graph representation, GNNs are applied to analyse relationships, infer new threat associations, and enhance cyber situational awareness. Various GNN architectures are considered based on their unique advantages in processing cybersecurity intelligence.

Table 4-1 GNN Architectures for Cyber Threat Intelligence

GNN Architecture	Purpose	Use Case	Considerations
Graph Convolutional Networks (GCN)	Aggregate node and edge relationships using localized convolution on graph structure	Mapping indirect connections between malware variants and campaigns in a relatively static network	Works best when your data set is relatively stable; can be resource-intensive for very large or rapidly changing graphs

Graph Attention Networks (GAT)	Assign different weights (attention) to node relationships, highlighting the most critical links	Prioritizing high-risk adversaries or suspicious edges (e.g., repeated malicious connections) for deeper investigations	More flexible than GCN, but can be slower; interpretability improves with attention visualizations
GraphSAGE	Perform inductive learning to handle real-time or batch arrival of new graph nodes	Quickly integrate newly discovered IoCs, vulnerabilities, or malicious domains without retraining the entire model	Scales better for dynamically growing graphs; selection of aggregator (mean, pooling, LSTM) affects performance
Temporal GNNs (TGNNs)	Capture temporal or dynamic aspects of graph data to predict future states or link formations over time	Forecasting the progression of multi-stage attacks (e.g., APT kill chains) by analyzing evolving relationships	Many variants exist; careful engineering of time windows and historical data is crucial for accuracy

By leveraging GNNs for advanced correlation, one can:

- Identify attack patterns earlier by linking related IoCs across multiple attack campaigns.
- Prioritize threats more effectively by assigning risk scores to correlated entities.
- Predict future threats by analysing historical attack paths and discovering previously unknown relationships (link prediction). Recently, GNNs can be used to predict attack targets in Advanced Persistent Threats (APTs) by reconstructing attack scenario graphs and applying graph-based link prediction to anticipate future attack step [21]
- Detect and correlate APT behaviours from multi-step attack sequences, even when provenance data is incomplete [22]
- Optimize security responses by providing security analysts with clear, explainable correlations between different cyber threats.

4.4.2 Design challenges

While OpenCTI provides a robust framework for automated intelligence processing, several challenges arise in implementing effective playbooks:

1. High volumes of observables can lead to an overwhelming number of IoCs. Effective scoring mechanisms and correlation rules must be in place.
2. Connecting new observables with existing TTPs, malware, and CVEs in real time requires efficient data processing.
3. Monitoring evolving adversary tactics is challenging due to the complexity of linking TTPs and campaigns dynamically.
4. The playbook system must handle an increasing volume of threat data without performance degradation.
5. GNNs can struggle with large-scale graph data, which is common in cybersecurity environments. Efficiently training and applying GNNs to large graphs containing millions of nodes (IoCs, malware, CVEs, etc.) while maintaining performance is a critical challenge
6. GNNs, particularly those highly complex (like GATs or Temporal GNNs), can act as "black boxes", making it difficult to explain the reasoning behind a prediction or correlation. This lack of

interpretability can hinder decision-making and trust in automated threat intelligence systems.

7. GNNs require significant computational resources, especially when processing large amounts of graph data. This can be a challenge when integrating them into a real-time cybersecurity system with limited processing power. We are monitoring this risk and we will take proper actions to limit the impact of computational issues.

4.4.3 Design approach

To address these challenges, the playbooks are designed with the following principles:

- IoCs and observables are assessed based on scores, ensuring that only critical threats trigger actions.
- When a new IoC or report is created, related entities (TTPs, malware, threat actors) are automatically linked.
- STIX reports are automatically generated and shared to maintain structured intelligence.
- Security tools receive notifications to trigger real-time mitigation efforts.

GNNs have been explored as a promising approach for enhancing threat correlation. While GNNs are not yet implemented, they are actively being investigated for future integration. Their potential application could improve the identification of complex relationships, threat prediction, and risk prioritization, particularly in large-scale, dynamic cybersecurity graphs.

4.4.4 Specification alignment

The technical specifications alignments are presented in Table 4-2.

Table 4-2 Specification Alignment for the AI Correlation Engine

Spec ID	Description	Alignment
iTrust6G_FUN_SP_005	Automatically aggregate and correlate disparate sources of temporal data and digital traces	The system automatically aggregates and correlates threat intelligence by processing observables (IPs, domains, file hashes) and promoting them to IoCs based on threat scores. Relationships between IoCs, malware, TTPs, CVEs, and threat actors are identified and structured using STIX reporting. Advanced analytics, including GNNs, are leveraged to analyse relationships, detect hidden patterns, and enhance situational awareness for improved threat mitigation.
iTrust6G_FUN_GEN_006	Provide near real-time alerts for critical threats and potential security incidents	OpenCTI's automated playbooks ensure real-time detection of cyber threats by continuously processing incoming threat data and correlating it with existing intelligence. As soon as a new IoC/ threat is detected or whenever an IoC surpasses a critical threshold, it is linked with related entities, and the system automatically triggers actions or alerts for further investigation or mitigation. This way near real-time alerts is provided and rapid incident response for the most pressing threats is facilitated.
iTrust6G_FUN_SP_007	Integrate threat intelligence into the zero-trust architecture. Gather data from deployed ML models to improve threat detection and remediation approaches.	GNNs are being explored for future integration to enhance the prediction of future cyberattacks. By analysing relationships between threat entities (e.g., IoCs, malware, attack techniques), GNNs can help predict future attack patterns and vulnerabilities, enabling proactive threat mitigation based on existing threat data.

	Correlate detected threats with widely known vulnerabilities (e.g.: CVEs)	
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4.4.5 Current implementation

The current implementation includes four playbooks for handling observables (IPs, domain names, and files) and prioritizing IoCs based on their threat scores.

1. Observable Promotion to IoC (IPs, Domains, Files)

For new observables (IP addresses, domain names, and file hashes), their threat score is checked. If the score exceeds 80, the observed is promoted to an IoC. The playbook then gathers relationships between the IoC and other entities (e.g., malware, TTPs, CVEs, and threat actors), generates a STIX report, and sends a notification to an external endpoint. This process ensures that high-risk indicators are quickly integrated into threat intelligence workflows.

2. IoC Prioritization and Risk Labeling

Existing IoCs are continuously monitored, and their threat scores are evaluated. Based on predefined thresholds, IoCs are categorized as:

- Very High Priority (>90)
- High Priority (70-90)
- Medium Priority (40-70)
- Low Priority (<40)

Once labelled, the playbook retrieves their relationships, generates a STIX report, and sends a notification. This helps security teams focus on the most critical threats first.

Figure 4-2 Visual representation of the STIX bundle of the report

4.4.6 Future work

Future work will focus on the implementation of GNNs, such as GCNs, GAT, GraphSAGE, and Temporal GNNs, to analyse and uncover complex relationships between cybersecurity entities (e.g., IoCs, malware, threat actors, vulnerabilities). This will improve the overall cyber situational awareness by enabling the detection of indirect correlations and enhancing the prediction of potential threats across evolving attack patterns.

Additionally, we will explore the integration of RL techniques to dynamically optimize correlation strategies and adapt to new threat landscapes.

The potential of implementing lightweight large language models (LLMs), such as FLAN-T5 will also be explored, to extract actionable insights from unstructured CTI data. By applying LLMs, we aim to enhance the extraction and interpretation of unstructured threat intelligence (e.g., reports, alerts, and logs) and convert it into structured data that can be used for further analysis and decision-making.

4.5 Orchestration engine

The Orchestration Engine serves as the core of the security automation framework, integrating OpenCTI, GNNs, and external threat intelligence sources. Its primary function is to automate the correlation of threat intelligence, ensuring that cybersecurity entities such as IoCs, vulnerabilities, threat actors, and attack techniques are efficiently analysed and linked.

Key Capabilities:

- **Workflow Automation:** This workflow automation capability significantly enhances incident response efficiency by automating security enforcement and minimizing manual intervention.
- **Seamless Integration:** The middleware is designed to be fully interoperable with CTI platforms (OpenCTI) and widely accepted cybersecurity frameworks such as MITRE ATT&CK, STIX/TAXII, and RESTful APIs. This ensures compatibility with existing security operations and facilitates efficient threat intelligence sharing.

Figure 4-3 Automation playbook for prioritising IoCs

4.5.1 State-of-the-art

4.5.1.1 STIX and TAXII for standardized threat intelligence sharing

STIX and Trusted Automated Exchange of Intelligence Information (TAXII) are widely recognized standards for cyber threat intelligence sharing. STIX provides a structured format for representing adversary tactics, techniques, and procedures (TTPs), while TAXII enables automated threat intelligence exchange. The Orchestration Engine fully adopts STIX/TAXII to:

- Standardize threat intelligence ingestion from OpenCTI, external feeds, and vulnerability scanners.
- Facilitate interoperability with third-party security solutions and incident response platforms.
- Ensure machine-readable representation of threat relationships, enabling automated security operations.

By leveraging STIX/TAXII, the engine ensures that cybersecurity teams can efficiently consume, analyse, and act upon threat intelligence within a structured and automated framework.

4.5.1.2 Asynchronous event-driven architecture for scalable security automation

The Orchestration Engine utilizes an event-driven architecture based on RabbitMQ for asynchronous message queuing to support large-scale threat intelligence processing. This architecture enables:

- Scalable security event ingestion, where high-throughput data streams from multiple sources can be processed in real-time.
- Decoupling of security workflows, ensuring that different components (threat intelligence correlation, incident response, and reporting) can operate independently without bottlenecks.
- High resilience and fault tolerance, as messages are queued and processed asynchronously, preventing data loss during high-load security events.

The asynchronous processing model ensures that the system remains responsive and scalable, even when handling vast amounts of cybersecurity data.

4.5.2 Design challenges

- Managing and accurately correlating a large number of entities, observables, and indicators in real-time.
- Ensuring that all input data is properly enriched and standardized for reliable analysis.
- Addressing compatibility issues when connecting with third-party tools and platforms.
- Balancing accuracy and performance in real-time applications.
- Automating workflows without manual intervention.
- Fine-tuning thresholds for threat scoring and prioritization to ensure meaningful results.

4.5.3 Design approach

The design approach of the Orchestration Engine ensures modular scalability and enables seamless interoperability with existing cybersecurity ecosystems. This approach ensures that threat intelligence can be efficiently processed, correlated, and acted upon in real-time through automated workflows and AI-driven security orchestration.

4.5.3.1 Modular architecture

The middleware is designed with a modular architecture, allowing for scalability, flexibility, and interoperability. Each functional component is decoupled, ensuring that updates and enhancements can be applied independently without disrupting the entire system. The modular approach supports:

- Scalable threat intelligence processing, allowing the system to ingest, analyse and correlate large volumes of real-time CTI data.
- Seamless integration with existing cybersecurity platforms, ensuring compatibility with OpenCTI, external threat databases, and SOC operations.

4.5.3.2 RESTful APIs for integration

The middleware provides a set of RESTful API endpoints to facilitate seamless communication between cybersecurity components. These APIs allow:

- Threat intelligence ingestion from multiple sources.
- Querying correlated threat intelligence for SOC teams, allowing analysts to retrieve structured attack patterns, IoC relationships, and risk assessments.
- Automated remediation and enforcement by forwarding deviation reports to security enforcement layers, ensuring proactive defence mechanisms.

This API-driven approach enables security teams to access, interact with, and contribute to the evolving threat intelligence knowledge base, enhancing collaborative cybersecurity defence.

4.5.3.3 Leveraged OpenCTI APIs

To maximize interoperability, the middleware leverages OpenCTI APIs to:

- Retrieve threat intelligence data, ensuring that cybersecurity events are contextualized with historical attack patterns and adversary tactics.
- Store correlated intelligence in a structured format, allowing for efficient querying and visualization of attack graphs.
- Automate playbook execution, enabling security workflows that dynamically analyse, classify, and escalate threats based on AI-driven correlation models.

By integrating OpenCTI APIs, the middleware seamlessly aligns with existing threat intelligence platforms, reducing the need for manual correlation efforts while improving threat visibility and response efficiency.

4.5.4 Protocol description

The middleware communicates with multiple cybersecurity platforms through standardized data exchange protocols, ensuring compatibility with industry security frameworks. This communication is facilitated using:

- STIX/TAXII Protocols: For structured threat intelligence sharing, allowing entities such as IoCs, attack techniques, and threat actors to be represented in a machine-readable format.
- RESTful APIs: For real-time data exchange between the middleware and external systems, including CTI platforms, SIEM solutions, and automated enforcement engines.
- Asynchronous messaging (RabbitMQ) is used to orchestrate event-driven workflows.

By adhering to standard communication protocols, the middleware ensures interoperability, scalability, and

ease of integration with modern cybersecurity infrastructures.

4.5.5 Specification alignment

The technical specifications alignments are presented in Table 4-3.

Table 4-3 Specification Alignment for the Orchestration Engine

Spec ID	Description	Alignment
iTrust6G_FUN_SP_013	Support the application of intent-based security policies, applied by means of explainable and automated end-to-end security orchestration.	The Orchestration Engine automates security workflows by executing predefined remediation actions, dynamic policy-driven responses, and AI-assisted threat correlation processes. This significantly reduces manual intervention and enables faster security incident resolution. The system aggregates cybersecurity intelligence from multiple sources, including OpenCTI for structured threat intelligence, RabbitMQ for event-driven data processing, and external threat feeds. By harmonizing intelligence from diverse cybersecurity ecosystems, the component ensures continuous data enrichment and contextual analysis.
iTrust6G_FUN_SP_014	Provide secure service design and delivery through smart slice provisioning and network functions placement. Assure application access to them through language agnostic programmatic interfaces.	The Orchestration Engine ensures seamless coordination across multiple cybersecurity components. It manages and correlates security events and facilitates intelligence-sharing across platforms. The component is highly flexible, supporting integration with third-party security tools, custom scripts, and automation plugins. This ensures that users can adapt and extend the orchestrator to meet specific cybersecurity requirements, enhancing long-term scalability and operational effectiveness.

4.5.6 Current implementation

The Orchestration Engine is designed to provide real-time cyber threat intelligence processing, enabling automated detection, correlation, and response to security incidents.

At its core, the Orchestration Engine is built upon FastAPI, a modern web framework optimized for high-performance API handling and asynchronous processing. FastAPI ensures that the system maintains low-latency communication between security components, allowing for rapid ingestion and processing of security data. The use of asynchronous execution ensures that multiple operations—such as data collection, AI inference, and response automation—can run concurrently without performance bottlenecks. To facilitate seamless threat intelligence ingestion and correlation, the Orchestration engine leverages multiple specialized libraries and frameworks, each serving a distinct purpose in the system’s architecture.

FastAPI core component takes over the communication between threat intelligence sources, AI models, and cybersecurity tools. Exposing a RESTful API layer enables security components to exchange structured data securely and efficiently. One of the key benefits of using FastAPI is its asynchronous processing capabilities, which support high-throughput threat intelligence ingestion and response automation. Additionally, the framework provides automatic data validation, leveraging Python-type hints to enforce data integrity while processing STIX/TAXII-formatted intelligence feeds.

The PyCTI library, the official Python client for OpenCTI, is responsible for seamless interaction with threat intelligence databases. This integration enables the security orchestrator to fetch structured threat intelligence in STIX format, ensuring that all security events, IoCs, and adversary techniques are standardised.

PyCTI also facilitates bidirectional data flow, allowing the Orchestration Engine to ingest correlated intelligence back into OpenCTI for enrichment and further analysis. Additionally, it enables automated execution of security playbooks, ensuring that threat intelligence models remain continuously updated and refined in real time.

To handle large volumes of security events, the Orchestration Engine relies on Pika, a RabbitMQ client, for message queuing and asynchronous event processing. RabbitMQ ensures that data ingestion, correlation, and response tasks remain decoupled, improving the system's overall reliability and performance. Pika allows the security orchestrator to efficiently stream real-time cybersecurity events, ensuring that high-priority security alerts are processed without delay. Furthermore, load balancing mechanisms within RabbitMQ help distribute processing loads across multiple instances, allowing the system to scale horizontally to accommodate increasing security intelligence data.

By combining FastAPI, PyCTI, and Pika, the Orchestration Engine achieves a highly efficient, scalable, and interoperable security automation solution, capable of handling large-scale cybersecurity data processing and orchestration in real-time.

4.5.7 Future work

- Develop seamless integrations with other cybersecurity tools and platforms through standardized protocols (e.g., STIX, TAXII, RESTful APIs).
- Scalability Improvements: Optimize the security orchestrator's architecture to handle large-scale threat intelligence processing efficiently.
- Evaluation of workflow automation tools such as Apache Airflow and Dagster to enhance security orchestration capabilities. These tools will be assessed for automating incident response workflows, optimizing threat intelligence data ingestion, and improving event-driven security operations.
- Graph Database Integration as a Knowledge Graph: Explore graph databases to efficiently store and retrieve threat intelligence correlations for improved querying performance.

5 Security Decision Response and Pervasive Enforcement

iTrust6G will develop the framework for improving the security posture of the managed network via both proactive measures and reactive responses. For this purpose, we will develop formats, models, and tools for mitigating risks and reacting to security events and incidents. The focus is mitigating risks in software networks, which cover most of the scenarios we are considering in iTrust6G.

Securing the networking environment is typically performed by humans with the following operations:

- Selecting and configuring security controls for implementing security requirements, or
- Intervening on the network components (adding, removing, moving hosts, servers, network elements, security controls) and the network layout (e.g., the connectivity graph, subnetting) to improve the level of protection of specific network elements, rearrange the network topology or to isolate compromised machines.

To mimic the behaviour of expert administrators (or entire Security Operation Centres), iTrust6G will develop:

- a model able to abstractly describe security controls, i.e., the NSFs (the name of security controls in virtual environments) and
- a model able to abstractly describe the network to protect, the network layout, and individual components.

Aiming to automate these manually performed tasks, we expect to improve reaction time and effectiveness. By coupling these tasks with risk assessment evaluations, we aim to select the best mitigations and reactions.

With these inputs, implementing "security decision response and pervasive enforcement" requires a simple yet precise way to specify security requirements. In iTrust6G, these requirements will be represented as Network Security Intents (NSI), (almost) natural language sentences expressing the desired network and security goals.

However, since intents may lack precision, they will be translated into statements that follow a more precise authorization policy language, named High-Level Security Policies Language (HSPL).

Since NSFs only understand directives expressed in their configuration language, high-level security policies, which will also be named HSPL statements, must be translated into low-level configuration settings. To this purpose, the translation will use another intermediate representation, the Medium-Level Policy (MLP) format, an abstract representation of the configuration for target NSFs expressed (semantically equivalent to the configuration the NSF will enforce but with an abstract language).

Therefore, this line of research aims to implement, as a set of components, the following features:

- **Security Intent Interpreter:** refines NSI into security statements expressed in the high-level security policy language;
- **Refinement Engine:** refines security requirements expressed in the high-level security policy language into abstract configurations for the target NSF. When trying to enforce security policies, this component may propose changes to the network environment (moving nodes, adding security controls) to remediate non-enforceability scenarios;
- **Translator:** translates abstract configurations expressed in the Medium-Level Policy format into configurations for the target NSF in the NSF-specific language.

Figure 5-1 iTrust6G architecture for security decision response

With these helper components, it is possible to support the enforcement of the remediations, which is the final goal of this research activity. This operation will be performed by an ad hoc tool:

- **Remediation manager:** starting from Cyber Threat Intelligence (CTI) information, enriched by iTrust6G tools, will identify suitable remediation strategies expressed as CACAO playbooks (named *recipes*), interpret how these strategies could be implemented in the network to protect, decide the best one to enforce (also using WP3 for risk assessment), and exploit the Intent processor and the Refinement Engine and WP5 tools for actually implementing the remediation.

Moreover, it will produce the tools for properly managing the models the easing the management of the security capabilities and supporting abstract representation of the target networks:

- **Network Description Manager:** a tool (that will be optionally developed) for managing the models and instances (representations) of the network to protect. The need for an explicit component will be evaluated in case managing network descriptions as files will not be deemed appropriate for integration purposes.
- **Security Capability Manager:** this tool exposes all the features related to the management of the Security Capability Model (SCM). It performs the formats adjustments (the model is designed in UML then used as XSD to validate instances), it makes accessible through queries the data about NSFs stored in the NSF Catalogue to other policy refinement tools.

5.1 Summary of the outcomes

The first outcome of this activity is the architecture of the T5.4 components, their relations with other WP5 tools and other tools for risk assessment and CTI management, which was also reported in iTrust6G D2.2.

During the reporting period of this deliverable, the following tools and data formats have been designed, implemented or adapted to the new iTrust6G scenarios and requirements. Currently, all the components are

still being tested in isolation, with synthetic inputs that, whenever possible, approximate well the real inputs these tools will receive during the rest of the project. These inputs have been derived from discussions in the project and assumptions on the use cases.

We report here, for each of them, the current status:

- *Security Capability Model*: the information model is stable, and the data model supports several types of security NSFs; more NSFs may need to be supported for the use cases (at least support for ModSecurity or another sophisticated application layer filter / WAF needs to be granted).
- *High-level Security Policy Language*: the language is stable, extensions are expected when the use cases will be considered in more details. Some details will be presented later in Section 5.3.2.
- *Network Security Intents*: an initial set of network security intents has been selected for the initial testing; these intents describe technical security goals, they will be made more abstract and at a higher level in the next months;
- *Security Capability Manager*: this tool is in a stable form, after it underwent major restructuring to include iTrust6G inputs. Requires more testing but it (almost) independent on use cases and further development of the models expected in iTrust6G. It also produces the abstract specification of the Medium-Level Policy format for all the NSFs that are described in the model.
- *Translator*: this tool is in a stable form, after it underwent major restructuring to include iTrust6G requirements obtained from discussions and use cases. More testing is required to consider whether the new features are completed and mature enough for integration. It may require significant changes depending on the next family of security controls (NSFs) that we may have to consider in the project. This is a risk we are constantly monitoring. However, from the discussions in the WP and at an overall project level, this risk should not manifest during the project.
- *Software Network Model*: the first draft of the model has been designed for internal validation; it is in its early stages; it is undergoing the first validation steps to prove it is able to represent Kubernetes environments also with the support of several Kubernetes plugin types.
- *Software Network Manager*: its implementation is suspended trying to evaluate if it needed for integration purposes. It would require manageable effort for its implementation. It is considered a very minor risk.
- *Refinement engine*: the initial version of this tool has been released in iTrust6G. Even if it is based on a background POLITICO tool, it has been severely restructured to support more advanced refinement strategies that render it able to enforce more sophisticated policies and, also, it is implementing the first features to reason about modifying the landscape for enforcing security policies. More testing is required to consider it stable.
- *Remediation manager*: the preliminary version of this tool has been released. It is based on a background POLITICO tool, a preliminary form of this tool was indeed used for both the PALANTIR and FISHY projects¹⁰. Changes affect the playbooks, which were represented in an internal proprietary format, improvements and proposal of new playbooks, adaptations required to process the type of Cyber Threat Information that will be provided by other project's asks.

¹⁰ <https://fishy-project.eu/>

5.2 Objectives and expected outcomes for the next reporting period

During the next reporting period, we will continue to improve individual tools. The focus will be on extensively supporting the project's use cases and scenarios. Indeed, changes and adaptations will be needed to properly process the concrete inputs that will emerge from the use cases when they are up and running. Other improvements are expected to support results that may deserve publication.

Moreover, we will start with the integration of individual components. We expect to release components as containerized (web) services (dockers) to this purpose. Moreover, we will define and share API specifications for all components that need to be invoked by other *iTrust6G* elements in this Task, WP, or at the project level.

One important integration is the one with the Risk Assessment Component (T3.3), which allows for the estimation of the impact, in terms of mitigation, of candidate recipes to make decisions about the optimal one.

Another important aspect that will be investigated and incorporated as future work is an increased application of AI-driven methods. With the rise of the efficiency and usefulness of LLMs, most security tasks could be automated:

- AI-driven remediations generator: which proposes (semi-)autonomously recipes for remediating security-relevant events, like finding strategies to counter incidents' consequences;
- AI-based processing of Network Security Intents, AI will be used to improve the expressiveness of Network Security Intents as more, these tools are able to capture more precisely semantics in natural language sentences, being able to simplify the development of complex parsers;
- AI-based refinement and non-enforceability remediation, having explained at a high-level what enforcing security requirements means, we will investigate how to take advantage of AI to ease the development of more advanced strategies without having to code strategies at a low level;

5.3 Formats used by the remediation, refinement, and translation tools

This section presents the initial versions of the independent formats that are needed for the

- Description the networking environment;
- Specification of the intents for specifying network intents; and
- Specification of the security policies, at different levels of abstraction.

In the *iTrust6G* view, intents and high-level security policies statements should be interchangeable, but intents should be more user friendly. However, HSPL statements can be considered a more precise format to map security intents.

Since the Medium-Level Policy format is not an independent set of specification languages, but it is automatically derived from the specification of the NSFs as in the Catalogue of the Security Capability Model, it will not be described here, it is referred to Section 5.4 for further details.

5.3.1 Network description model

iTrust6G uses TOSCA YAML¹¹ to represent the network environment. The decision to adopt TOSCA YAML as the standard for describing the network layout was based on its ability to address the tool's specific

¹¹ <https://docs.oasis-open.org/tosca/TOSCA-Simple-Profile-YAML/v1.3/os/TOSCA-Simple-Profile-YAML-v1.3-os.html>

requirements. After evaluating multiple alternatives, including YANG¹² and other network topology description models, both proprietary and internal representations used in common software network tools like Mininet, TOSCA YAML was selected for its strengths in representing network topologies and associated component information in a clear and structured manner:

- *Detailed modelling*: TOSCA provides a framework for accurately describing network components, their relationships, and configurations. This ensures that the layout and associated information can be gathered comprehensively;
- *Interoperability*: as a vendor-neutral specification, TOSCA supports integration with diverse tools and platforms, an essential feature for environments involving multiple technologies and providers;
- *Extensibility*: the modular nature of TOSCA allows for customization to include specific network elements and relationships as needed, guaranteeing the tool can adapt to future requirements;
- *Validation*: the schema-based structure enables validation of the network description, both assuring consistency and reducing the risk of errors;
- *Cloud-native orientation*: by design, TOSCA is suitable for describing dynamic and cloud environments, making it compatible with modern deployment platforms, e.g. Kubernetes.

The use of YAML as the underlying format further boosts its applicability for describing the network layout:

- *Simplicity*: the human-readable syntax simplifies the creation and understanding of network descriptions, minimizing errors and reducing the effort required to manage configurations;
- *Compactness*: its lightweight structure avoids the verbosity of formats like XML, making it more suitable to represent, for example, complex hierarchies;
- *Tool compatibility*: YAML is widely supported by modern tools and frameworks, including Python, which ensures uniform integration with the HSPL refinement tool.

5.3.1.1 TOSCA type definitions for iTrust6G

The TOSCA Simple Profile in YAML Version 1.2 was adopted as a base to standardize the representation of network layouts. Together with the standard TOSCA entities, our model has been extended to include:

- *NetworkDevice*: an intermediate network device capable of implementing security functions, e.g. firewalls or VPN gateways;
- *CustomSubnet*: a basic subnet with a customizable attribute for marking IP ranges as "negated", useful for determining (good or malicious) users that come from outside a certain network;
- *NetworkUser*: a regular network user or endpoint within a subnet;
- *MaliciousUser*: potential threats or adversarial entities, derived from the Custom-Subnet type to reuse its negation feature;
- *Service*: hosted applications and services within the network;
- *Traffic*: specific types of network traffic.

If needed by the project, further entities can be easily added to this model due to its innate extensibility.

¹² <https://www.rfc-editor.org/info/rfc6020>

5.3.1.2 Support for TOSCA in iTrust6G

Every new TOSCA type is included in the system by adding a dedicated file that defines custom node and capability types. These types extend the standard TOSCA definitions, matching them to meet the requirements of the refinement tool.

Moreover, an additional YAML file is needed to complement the abstract type definitions by describing the actual instances of nodes within the network. Each instance is based on the types defined as a custom YAML file, with attributes and relationships suitable for reflecting the specific components and topology of the network.

This preliminary part of the model is under validation, but the development effort has not yet been terminated. More details on this topic and more extensive documentation remains for future reports.

5.3.1.3 Abstract model of software networks

We have started a more granular definition of software networks, from Kubernetes, to allow the Remediation Manager to reason about the remediation strategies to propose instead of remaining limited to the hard-coded recipes.

In recent years, Kubernetes has established itself as a dominant platform for container orchestration, becoming an integral component of numerous cloud infrastructures. A significant portion of Kubernetes' popularity stems from its ecosystem of external components, including operators, network plugins, and various other tools. The proliferation of these components, each tailored to specific use cases, has resulted in a diverse and often overlapping landscape of solutions.

We are comprehensively analyzing several prominent Kubernetes network plugins, operators, and tools, encompassing popular solutions such as Flannel¹³, Calico¹⁴, Cilium¹⁵, Network Service Mesh¹⁶, and Kube-router¹⁷. The analysis delves into their respective features, performance characteristics, and security implications, enabling a comparative evaluation.

The purpose is to develop an abstract model that encapsulates the diverse resource types within Kubernetes. The name we are currently giving to this model is **Software Networks Model**. Designed to encompass a broad spectrum of Kubernetes resources, the model has been validated against real-world deployments, including Google Boutique, IBM Java microservices, and practical applications powered by Kubernetes, Cilium, and KubeArmor. This structured representation offers a foundation for automated processing by software tools.

During the plenary meetings, we checked the compatibility of this approach with the infrastructure that will be considered in iTrust6G, which will be based on NFV. No significant issues have emerged. However, the integration with NFV should be monitored to mitigate the risk of limited usability in the project.

The Software Networks Model is under development. More details on this topic will be provided in the next deliverables.

5.3.2 High-Level Security Policy Language

The High-Level Security Policy Language (HSPL) is the language specified to express security requirements

¹³ <https://github.com/flannel-io/flannel>

¹⁴ <https://docs.tigera.io/calico/latest/about/>

¹⁵ <https://cilium.io/>

¹⁶ <https://networkservicemesh.io/>

¹⁷ <https://github.com/cloudnativelabs/kube-router>

that administrators want enforced in their network.

The HSPL adopts a policy model based on authorization statements, one of the most used approaches for describing high-level policies, which has already been favourably used in another EC-funded project named SECURED [23] and FISHY [24].

An HSPL statement is a triple *subject-action-object* with the following structure:

```
[subject] action object [ (field_type,value) ... (field_type,value) ]
```

Where:

- *subject* is the entity (e.g., username, IP address, wallet ID) that needs to access or perform some operation on an object and may be omitted if the policy is applied to the user that defines the HSPL.
- *action* is the operation to be performed on the object (e.g., allow access, notify).
- *object* is the entity (e.g., Internet traffic, all the traffic) target of the action.
- *(field_type,value)* is an optional condition that adds specific constraints to the action (e.g., time, content type, traffic type). The value part is a string with a specific format depending on the field type.

HSPL statements are written in XML. This format allows an exhaustive validation of the high-level policies via an ad-hoc XML Schema. For instance, an HSPL statement used to ban the IP address 1.2.3.4 is:

```
<hspl>
<subject type="ip_address">1.2.3.4</subject>
<action>no_authorise_access</action>
<object>all_traffic</object>
</hspl>
```

The current HSPL model supports reactive policies. These policies are characterized by one or more enabling conditions that trigger their execution. This mechanism allows the tools to implement dynamic configurations that are executed only when a specific change in the network occurs. The actual scenario of reactive policies being applied in *iTrust6G* has not yet been investigated, as this project aims to express reactions and remediations at a higher level.

For instance, the following reactive HSPL can be used to ban a wallet ID *wallet1* when it establishes more than ten connections in 30 seconds:

```
<reaction id="reaction1">
<enabling-conditions>
<threshold>
<subject type="wallet_id">wallet1</subject>
<value>10</value>
<period>30</period>
<time>second</time>
</threshold>
...
</enabling-conditions>
<hspl>
<subject type="wallet_id">wallet1</subject>
<action>no_authorise_access</action>
<object>all_traffic</object>
</hspl>
</reaction>
```

5.3.3 Network security intents

The initial version of the Network Security Intents (NSI) is expressed with a structured high-level language whose format is heavily inspired by the Nile model [25], developed for composing chains of NSFs that must satisfy network security requirements. These NSIs have been used to perform refinement and realignment. The results have been published in a recent conference paper [26].

To achieve our goal, we have extended the Nile model to support the additional features of our framework. An NSI reports the two endpoints where the chain will be connected using the keywords:

- *from* endpointA
- *to* endpointB

From the security point of view, the *to* will typically indicate a service or a resource to protect.

Optionally, the intent may indicate the action to perform (e.g., allow or deny) and include a matching condition section, which reports additional fields to characterize better the security requirements the chain has to enforce, like network flows (*flow*) and other management fields, like the duration of validity of an intent.

The intent may explicitly report a chain of NSFs (*chain middlebox*). In this case, the intent may refer to specific NSFs whose version and image files can be defined with the *declare* statement:

```
declare security intent ('Protect_service')
declare middlebox([name: 'Suricata', image:'Suricata4.3'])
  from endpoint('load-balancer')
  to endpoint('serviceA')
  chain middlebox('Suricata')
  allow flow([dst_port: '443'])
  event_condition:
    type: unauthorized-access
    deny event.traffic
    duration: time(1, 'hour')
```

However, if the intent does not list all the needed middleboxes, the missing ones are selected from a catalogue where NSFs are associated with the security capabilities, they own [27]. Suitable NSFs are selected by matching their capabilities against the parsed intent details.

The *event condition* section in the NSI allows constraining and refining the enforcement strategy adopted in response to specific events. This section enables the selection of the event types to which react and additional event details (e.g., the reliability of the prediction by the monitoring system). The reaction reports the changes to the original chain (e.g., adding or removing middleboxes) and the specific actions to apply, which may refer to information available at the event. The need to react to events is something an administrator may need to enforce for compliance reasons. It is worth noting that intents expressed in natural language can be easily mapped to our intent format using Large Language Models, as confirmed by ongoing research effort.

Note that these reactions are different from the ones that we aim at enforcing with the Remediation Manager. These are well known and foreseen policy-driven functional behavior, while the other ones are reactions to unknown events like attacks, for which the most appropriate must be identified depending on the specific circumstances (described by CTI and additional context information added by iTrust6G tools).

A Parser component is involved in the intent profiling stage. It first validates the NSI's syntax correctness. Then, it checks if its specification contains the minimum information necessary to correctly process and

manage the intent and its corresponding services and security requirements. Next, it collects and interprets the data in the intent, passing them as instances of an ad hoc Python class.

For parsing and interpreting, we repurposed an engine developed during the FISHY project, which has proven effective for prototyping and can be easily extended with an ad hoc grammar for NSI description [28]. Its grammar represents the concepts used in expressing intents and defines the rules for parsing and interpreting these expressions. A meta-model of intent rules was built on top of this grammar, specifying how the interpreter converts textual descriptions into processable data. The interpreter takes the textual representation as input and produces a model, specifically the data class of the intent.

5.4 Security capability model and the security capability manager

An essential architecture component is the Security Capability Manager (SecMan), which is responsible for providing an abstract representation of the Security Controls involved in the remediation process. The Security Capability Manager is built upon the Security Capability Model (SCM), a layer of abstraction that represents security controls using Security Capabilities, a set of abstract concepts that indicate what actions, conditions, and events they can handle. The capability model is used by the other components of the architecture to automate the translation of abstract configurations represented with a high level of formalism into the low-level configuration settings for specific security controls.

5.4.1 State-of-the-art

The earlier mentions of the modelling of Security Controls can be found in Basile et al., where an ontology-based approach to abstractly translate policies into low-level configurations was presented [29]. This approach exploited ontology as a tool for formally modelling knowledge about security controls. In this research, the security controls' features were coarse-grained due to the severe limitations posed by ontology-based reasoning, which imposed limited usability. The work evolved into a more coherent framework for supporting refinement in software networks and NSFs [30]. Still, instead of modelling individual capabilities, this work used more general classes to implicitly determine a standard set of features they exposed. Hence, it could not capture the differences between security controls belonging to the same category.

A model of individual capabilities offered by NSFs was CapIM [31], an information model developed by the I2NSF WG to provide a standard interface for the control and management of NSFs.

The model we will use in iTrust6G derives from another work by Basile et al. [27]. This paper defined the structure of the information model and presented the idea of applying the concept of security capabilities to represent the features of network security functions.

The initial version of the tools presented here for managing the Security Capability Model for iTrust6G has been developed and used in the FISHY¹⁸ project based on the models described in [27]. Concerning the previous, the model presented here has been further enhanced and upgraded to support better implementation via a more coherent design.

The changes to the model and tools, which were part of the background for this project, were driven by the new requirements that we have received in the iTrust6G, considering the discussed use cases and the potential applications. In particular, we had to support channel protection NSFs and application layer filters. These types of security controls have more sophisticated configuration languages and mechanisms for deciding the actions to be enforced.

Specifically, the information model remained unchanged. However, the subclasses of the Details classes

¹⁸ <https://fishy-project.eu/>

(according to the decorator pattern) have been severely renewed.

- The *LanguageGeneratorDetails* classes have been completely deprecated due to a change in the approach for the specification for improved flexibility and more generality at the middle level of abstraction.
- The *NSFPolicyDetails* have been enriched with subclasses that allow supporting languages requiring the configuration parameters to be grouped into more sophisticated statements.
- New *HasSecurityCapabilityDetails* subclasses classes have been added to describe how to correctly translate capabilities for the newly supported devices.

The changes in these classes also increase the model-driven translator's sophistication.

It is outside the scope of this deliverable, presenting too many details about the latest version of the Security Capability Model. Only the essential details for understanding the iTrust6G design and development effort will be reported. Interested readers can find more information on the models in additional sources:

- information about the current implementation of the Security Capability Model, focusing on packet filters, and its initial validation is reported in a publicly available paper, which has been submitted to a high-impact journal [32];
- information about the support for channel protection NSFs is explained in a thesis [33];
- Information about the support for NSFs for application layer filtering is explained in a thesis [34].

5.4.2 Design challenges

The biggest complexities faced during the design of this component are related to the modelling of the NSFs: since modern security software consists of a vast number of features whose documentation may be poorly written, a significant amount of human effort is required to express each of these features to the appropriate capabilities. Furthermore, features that may appear "atomic" in a specific security control may be further decomposed in others; therefore, careful considerations must be taken when defining new security capabilities.

To address these challenges in the context of the iTrust6G project, we plan to use either all or a subset of the currently modelled security controls in the operational environment, as they are sufficient to provide significant diversity in security functions. However, modelling and testing of all of them is not yet finished.

5.4.3 Specification alignment

The technical specifications described are aligned as described in Table 5-1.

Table 5-1 Specification Alignment for the Security Capability Model and Manager

Spec. ID	Description	Alignment
iTrust6G_NOF_GEN_018	Apply formal models to describe the automated configuration of networks and security controls.	The Security Capability Manager and the underlying Security Capability Model define abstract representation for the security policies and configuration of the networks. These abstractions are represented via HSPL.

5.4.4 Design approach

As already stated, the capability model the Security Capability Manager uses utilizes security capabilities to represent the different features that a security control can offer. Specifically, the capability model focuses on six main concepts derived from analysing the generic features security controls offer to specify

configurations, as already proposed in the I2NSF WG draft. The first four concepts describe the creation of a rule:

- The **conditions** are the information used to describe the features available at the NSF to identify the policy target (e.g., conditions on the IP addresses or regex on the HTTP MIME type).
- The **actions** are the operations an NSF can perform on individual elements (e.g., deny packets or encrypt flows).
- Finally, the model describes the **events** that trigger the evaluation of the rules for specific classes of security controls. The need for events has not been highlighted in the ITRUST6G use cases.
- The last field is related to the **condition clause**. It serves to express that a rule is activated when all the conditions evaluate to true (DNF, Disjunctive Normal Form) or just one condition is satisfied (CNF, Conjunctive Normal Form).

The following two concepts also explain how to build the desired security policy from individual rules.

- The **resolution strategies** describe how the control behaves when multiple rules apply to the same entity. For instance, the first matching rule applies the rule's action at the highest priority when more rules apply.
- Support for **default actions** allows for determining how the control behaves when no rule matches the element. For instance, it is essential to know if the control allows specifying the "deny all" default action, as implemented by most firewalls.

These elements represent the 6-tuple needed for describing the security capability of an NSF.

5.4.5 Current implementation

5.4.5.1 The Security Capability Model

The current implementation of the Security Capability Model is described in more detail in the previously mentioned paper [32].

Figure 5-2 describes the status of the security capability model's design, particularly the underlying information model. The security capability model comprises two classes (NSF and SecurityCapability), which abstract respectively Network Security Function and a generic security capability, and an association class (HasSecurityCapabilityDetail) that links them according to the decorator pattern. The model also contains the NSFCatalogue class, which acts as the aggregator of NSF instances while also being the root element of the capability part of the repository.

Figure 5-2 Information model of the security capability model

The decorator pattern provides additional information (as an association class) when capabilities are "attached" to the decorated objects. This pattern is important for this model to define how capabilities map to device-specific settings to be used by the translator. This pattern may be used to add capabilities both statically, when an NSF is described, and dynamically, during network operations. Thanks to the decorator pattern, the model will ease the description of the capabilities by supporting templates, allowing merging them and individually adding and subtracting features from a previous description. For instance, the description of the capabilities of iptables can be determined by extending the description of a generic packet filter and a generic filter on TCP states, i.e., by adding more features to these generic templates. Furthermore, the v2.0 of an NSF can be obtained starting from the description of the v1.0 of the NSF by adding or removing individual capabilities.

As an additional requirement, the design choices aim to minimize the semantics required by the refinement and translation processes to work with NSF capabilities. In particular, the only hardcoded semantics must be associated with the previously mentioned 6-tuple. The internal implementations of the Refinement Engine and Remediation Manager must only be aware of the six categories of capabilities inherited from the I2NSF WG approach to provide refinement and translation services.

Capabilities are used to describe the functionalities of NSFs, corresponding to features enabled through their configuration languages. These capabilities can be linked to abstract language constructs. NSF Abstract Languages are derived from NSF instances through an automated language generation process. The NSF Abstract Language serves to specify configurations for a particular NSF, referred to as Middle-Level Policy (MLP). MLPs use a syntax independent of the NSF from which they are derived. However, since they are validated against the NSF Abstract Language, they are ensured to contain only instructions corresponding to capabilities supported by the NSF.

Since MLPs cannot directly be used to configure NSFs, they must be translated into appropriate low-level settings. A key design requirement for this translation process was minimizing the need to update the translator code frequently. To achieve this, the decorator pattern was utilized, enabling the addition of extra information when capabilities are "attached" to decorated objects. This approach incorporates the `HasSecurityCapabilityDetails` association class, which is linked to both NSF and `SecurityCapability` in the implementation. This association class facilitates mapping abstract capabilities to device-specific settings at the model level, enabling the creation of a model-driven translator. As a result, the translator can perform translations without requiring NSF-specific code, as translation directives are encapsulated within the association classes.

Additionally, the information model also considers different types of "details" that were needed to support the translation process as well as the logic with which security policies are applied:

- *NSFPolicyDetails* class conveys information on how to translate policy-related information for a target NSF; it has been implemented as an inner attribute of the NSF class. It reports:
 - strings and formats needed to generate valid rules and policies (with the attributes *ruleStart*, *ruleEnd*, *policyTrailer*, and *policyEncoding*);
 - the capabilities that need to mandatorily be present for a valid policy, which may vary depending on the NSF (*defaultSecurityCapability*);
 - other parameters to be given to the Translator for a correct generation that cannot be obtained otherwise (e.g., *policyAttribute*).
- *CapabilityTranslationDetails* class conveys data needed to translate individual capabilities to form correct NSF-specific rules. In other words, the attribute values reported with this class specify the low-level policy rule semantics and syntax and are crucial for the model-driven translation.

- *ResolutionStrategyDetails* class characterises the external data that a Resolution Strategy uses so those values are properly generated during translation (e.g., *requiredExternalData*). For example, the First Matching Rule resolution strategy, i.e., the default one for IpTables, associates rules to integers to express the priority. Based on priorities, the Translator will append rules to the selected chain in the proper order.

5.4.5.2 Architecture of the Security Capability Manager

The Security Capability Model is represented with the UML dialect of Modelio¹⁹, an open-source modelling environment for UML. However, for practical usability and to be applied to our use cases, the XML technology is required. The Security Capability Model Manager tool is used to generate the Security Capability XSD Model automatically, that is, the schema describing the UML classes of the model and their features. This file contains all the data types needed to model the security controls. The Security Controls are described in separate XML files and validated against this schema. These XML files, rooted in the NSF class, consist of a list of all the security capabilities, the associated policy details, and all the translation instructions, expressed as *CapabilityTranslationDetails* instances.

The Catalogue is an XML file that includes the NSF files to be used. Given an NSF name and its corresponding XML modelling, the Security Capability Manager is also responsible for generating the NSF Abstract Language, which is an XSD file containing the abstract language used to validate MLP policies for that NSF. The tool is implemented in Java and is designed for occasional execution, such as when the model is updated, or new security controls are added to the catalogue.

The model instances are managed and accessed via a web service called NSF Catalogue Service, which provides access to a user-selected NSF Catalogue stored in an XML database. The service relies on BaseX²⁰, which offers interactive data visualizations and implements a RESTXQ service, facilitating the development of web applications using XQuery. A collection of endpoints, implemented as XQuery scripts, is exposed to support essential functions and workflows:

- Comparison: searches in the catalogue and compares two NSFs whose names are provided as input, outputting the set of shared capabilities.

Figure 5-3 Architecture of the tools used for managing the security capability model

¹⁹ <https://www.modelio.org>

²⁰ <https://basex.org/>

- *Substitution*: proposes other security controls in the catalogue that could be employed instead of the NSF queried.
- *Policy enforcement*: identifies the security controls that support the capabilities required to enforce the MLP received as input.
- *NSF search*: returns the list of NSFs supporting all of the capabilities received as input.

Lastly, the Translator is a sophisticated Java-based application that interprets the Medium-Level Policy and transforms the abstract configuration settings into the NSF-specific Low-Level Configuration (LLC).

Given the adherence to a model-driven approach during the design of the Security Capability Model, all the translation rules that are required for the MLP to LLC conversion process are included in the description of the NSF (which is stored in the NSF Catalogue). Therefore, the translator is an interpreter of the *CapabilityTranslationDetails* classes, instances of the previously mentioned association classes between a *SecurityCapability* and an NSF. These classes determine how to translate individual capabilities for a given NSF. Moreover, the translator also processes policy or rule-level translation instructions specified by the *NSFPolicyDetails* class's attributes.

The Translator accepts several inputs: the XML Schema defining the NSF Catalogue, the Security Capability XSD Model, the name of an NSF within the Catalogue, and an XML file describing a valid policy for the NSF. Its output is the low-level configuration specific to the input NSF.

5.4.5.3 Supported NSFs

Here is the list of the NSFs that can be supported with the current model and the development status:

- Iptables (supported and tested)²¹;
- pfsense (the most important options are supported, partially tested)²²;
- Squid (fully supported and partially tested)²³;
- XFRM (supported and tested)²⁴;
- Strongswan (supported, partially tested)²⁵;
- OpenVPN (initial support, to be completed and then tested)²⁶;
- ModSecurity (initial support of the filtering-only instructions; more tests needed to check full expressiveness)²⁷.

Moreover, it is possible to support generic security controls, which do not correspond to specific NSF instances but are useful for defining abstract security controls to be later instantiated to real devices.

5.4.6 Next steps

The work expected to be carried out in the future mainly focuses on the extensions and improvements of the Security Capability Manager features. In particular, we aim to increase the number of NSFs modelled through the capability model. One of these NSFs is ModSecurity, an open-source web application firewall

²¹ <https://www.netfilter.org/documentation/>

²² <https://www.pfsense.org/>

²³ <https://www.squid-cache.org/>

²⁴ https://docs.kernel.org/networking/xfrm_device.html

²⁵ <https://strongswan.org/>

²⁶ <https://openvpn.net/>

²⁷ <https://modsecurity.org/>

currently partially supported and with ongoing full integration. Analogously, full support of OpenVPN is planned as future work.

Another fundamental enhancement planned for future work is the containerization (via Docker) of the Security Capability Manager tool to make it available as a web service. At the current state of development, the tool requires significant effort for its configuration due to the system's complexity and the number of dependencies. Therefore, streamlining the deployment of this component is one of the top priorities when speaking of future work.

The different components and tools are now available as Python scripts. The features these tools provide for managing the model, the catalogue and the translator will be made available as a web service delivered as a Docker.

5.5 Components for refining policies and network security intents

As presented before, the part of the iTrust6G infrastructure that manages and refines policies is composed of two main tools, the Security Intents Interpreter and the Refinement Engine.

5.5.1 State-of-the-art

A key area of research focuses on security orchestration in next-generation networks. It includes ensuring compliance with security requirements driven by business needs or regulatory obligations and providing flexible mechanisms to respond to emerging threats in diverse and evolving operational environments [35].

Intent-Based Networking (IBN) is a framework designed to enable automated management of the entire network lifecycle, reducing the need for human intervention and minimizing the risk of misconfigurations. It represents an evolution from traditional policy-based management by prioritizing simplicity in network operations, focusing on service-level outcomes instead of the specific configurations required to achieve them. However, integrating IBN into existing infrastructures poses several challenges, particularly in implementing and orchestrating intents across diverse network environments [36] [37] [38].

Despite working at a lower level than needed by this project and despite not being focused on security, the NILE (Network Intent LanguageE) model defines a model for representing network intents [39]. Moreover, in the same paper, the authors presented Lumi, a system allowing operators to express intents in natural language and then translate them into network directives.

Figure 5-4 Proposed architecture on policy enforcement

Enterprise security requirements are typically expressed as abstract, high-level [39] statements highlighting a system's protection objectives, such as preventing unauthorized access or maintaining data privacy. These requirements often focus on broader security attributes like confidentiality, integrity, availability, or privacy. Frameworks and models commonly used to articulate these policies play a crucial role in defining the boundaries between authorized and unauthorized actions and distinguishing secure from insecure states within a system.

However, statements can only be enforced after a security policy refinement process [40]. Security Policy Refinement represents the process of translating high-level security policies into enforceable rules within the actual environment. The process of refining these abstract concepts into concrete security mechanisms without losing their intended purpose is critical. First, one must determine the resources, i.e., the NSFs, that may be used to enforce the desired requirements. Then, requirements are translated into the low-level settings for the identified NSFs.

Refinement is a complex problem that security architects face regularly, and complexity increases with the size and heterogeneity of the target infrastructure. Currently, this process is mainly conducted by network and security administrators, a human-driven approach that has been linked to misconfigurations and conflicts [41], [42]. Automatic policy refinement has been proposed in the literature; however, previous works focus on vertical areas (i.e., access control [43], channel protection [44]) rather than analysing the problem from the perspective of what the generic NSFs can do and the entities they interact with. Hence, automating the refinement in real contexts is still an open problem.

The Security Intents Interpreter is a novel component that is not based on the backgrounds of other project partners. Instead, the Refinement Engine and its principles are part of the background. They have already been used in the FISHY project, where a similar component was named Controller [24]. Based on those results and validation, in *iTrust6G*, we will develop a component that follows the same design principles. However, it will be able to implement more sophisticated decisions when refining policies. In particular, the effort will be focused on improving the cases where more NSFs need to be involved for implementing a requirement (e.g., filtering IPs with packet filters and adding a local WAF for allowing traffic flows based on application layer data as well as repelling attacks).

5.5.2 Design challenges

The most complex and research-intensive tasks for implementing such a system are associating the proper semantics to the high-level security requirements and then interpreting them correctly before deciding how to enforce them in a target network.

The Security Intents Interpreter must give semantics to close-to-natural language sentences that provide indications for enforcing network security requirements and information on the network security requirements. Understanding security requirements in a close-to-natural language format, relating them with the information about the network to protect is not a trivial task. However, limiting hallucination and focusing the answers on the network security domain is another key challenge to solve within the project. Since these challenges require intense research effort, we planned to work them stepwise. Starting from fixed-structure intents, we will enrich them with a more flexible way to express a fixed set of policies inspired by the HSPL statements. This approach will ensure that risks are managed and that the project will produce valid outcomes. On top of these stable and feasible results, we will build a complete approach based on natural language and involve LLMs, which have proved very effective in interpreting texts.

Another challenge is the proper way to represent the policy refinement strategies. When enforcing policies, security administrators make sophisticated decisions and adopt complex enforcement strategies when doing their job. Capturing the criteria for considering a requirement satisfied in a complex networked infrastructure is challenging, especially when multiple (possibly different) NSFs should collaborate for their enforcement.

Another challenge is the selection of the devices, as the rules distribution should also be balanced to avoid overloading NSFs. Indeed, in most cases, more than a device can implement the rules needed to enforce the policy. Hence, deciding which one to configure becomes crucial for the performance of the entire traffic. Moreover, there is room for implementing more complex strategies, like edge-based or central approaches to policy enforcement and different types of implementations of the defense in-depth paradigm.

Finally, understanding how to mitigate the scenarios, which may stem from applying remediation strategies where requested security policies are not enforceable, is also a very complex issue we must address in this project. In particular, the open issue is understanding how to work at the network level to render policies enforceable, e.g. by proposing changes to the components, rearranging the network elements, and changing the subnetting.

Finally, even if translation logically pertains to these refinement tasks, since we rely on the Security Capability Model, the complexity of modelling abstractly the NSFs to configure and obtain the Medium-Level policies languages is included in the effort spent on defining that model.

5.5.3 Design approach

Concerning the Security Intents Interpreter, in the reporting period of this deliverable, the work focused on finding more concrete and structured intents taken from the literature, like the ones following the Nile model. Experiments have been performed using sentences that express free language security policies, such as the ones that can be written with HSPL. The purpose is to have a working tool with minimum intent understanding capability to mitigate the risks of not properly processing natural language sentences expressing requirements and directives for network security management.

Then, the Refinement Engine is the component that refines high-level policies into medium-level policies. The purpose of this component is to mimic the process of security administrators when interpreting high-level security policies, analyzing the current network infrastructure, identifying solutions for implementing the security requirements, and then deciding on the best solution (which meets security and cost requirements). The process we have adopted consists of the following:

- Giving semantics to HSPL statements by analyzing all the subjects, objects, and optional fields.
- Determining the capability that an NSF should own to enforce what the HSPL statement analysis implies.
- Identifying the NSFs in the landscape that can enforce the required policy.
- Selecting the NSFs to configure according to a refinement strategy (e.g., defence in depth, minimization of the security control processing times) or proposing the addition of new NSFs (taken from the NSF Catalogue) to remediate non-enforceable policies.
- Deriving the Medium-Level policy of all the selected NSFs.

This approach has proven valid in previous implementations of the component, e.g., the one used in FISHY, hence it will be followed. Minor risks of changes in this high-level approach have been foreseen, due the need for restructuring the approach due to more sophisticated decision making. Nonetheless, this risk has been evaluated as negligible.

5.5.4 Specification alignment

The technical specifications described are aligned as described in Table 5-2.

Table 5-2 Specification Alignment for the Security Intents Interpreter, Refinement Engine and Translator

Spec. ID	Description	Alignment
iTrust6G_NOF_GEN_017	Apply formal models to describe the managed networks and their automated configuration.	The Refinement Engine utilizes the TOSCA YAML framework for representing the network infrastructure. The base model has been additionally extended to support the application in the iTrust6G project.
iTrust6G_FUN_SP_013	Support the application of intent-based security policies, applied by means of explainable and automated end-to-end security orchestration	The Security Intents Interpreter processes intent-based security policies by converting them into HSPL statements. The Refinement Engine processes these statements into MLP that can be translated in Low-Level Configurations for the security controls. These configurations implement the security requirements specified by the original intents.

5.5.5 Current implementation

The Refinement Engine completes its refinement tasks by performing an enrichment process as a forward reasoning task. To this purpose, a forward reasoning engine is at the component's core. In particular, we preferred the CLIPS forward reasoning because it is open source, efficient, and implements the RETE algorithm [45]. Other open-source forward reasoners have been considered; however, with its ClipsPyPython porting²⁸, CLIPS has been proven more effective and easier to integrate into our design. CLIPS supports and transparently manages a Knowledge Base where all the facts are stored.

The reasonings (inferences) are modelled as template rules. Template rules are formed by preconditions, which are expressions to be evaluated on the data on the knowledge base. If the preconditions are met, the template rules perform operations defined in the body of a template rule. The operations that can be performed are directly inserting facts into the knowledge base in the form of assertions or, since we use ClipsPY, as invocations of Python functions. The possibility of calling Python functions extends the features of the forward reasoner as a whole programming language, and all the Python libraries can be used. In the end, the function called will store data in the knowledge base.

Template rules are called as soon as their preconditions are met and optimally. Indeed, for this purpose, CLIPS implements the RETE algorithm, which ensures excellent performance compared to ad hoc solutions.

5.5.6 Next steps

As indicated before, future work sees the need for implementing a more complex Security Intents Interpreter, associated with a more expressive intents format, trying to arrive at sentences in natural languages with the help of LLM. Indeed, the project will address this research topic by adding better and more extensive support for AI methods.

The refinement Engine needs to be improved with more sophisticated strategies that more precisely mimic expert security administrators' problem-solving abilities. We will evaluate the possibility of adding an optimization layer in identifying the NSFs to configure, by importing results from current research efforts in this field. However, how to extend the optimization process to include

Finally, we will add support for other categories of NSFs, depending on the need for the project's use cases, particularly application layer filters and WAFs.

²⁸ <https://clipspy.readthedocs.io/en/latest>

5.6 Remediation manager

This component is responsible for identifying the remediation measures to enforce when security-relevant information (e.g., incidents, suspicious activities, new vulnerabilities) is detected by other components while managing and enriching CTI.

It processes the security-relevant information, possibly collects additional data to support decision-making, and identifies suitable remediation strategies. Initially, these strategies will be evaluated for their effectiveness through expert judgments. In later versions of the iTrust6G framework, this component will interact with the Risk Assessment module to assess the impact of the proposed strategies and obtain additional information related to the risk associated to the protected assets.

Once a remediation strategy is decided, this component transforms the generic strategies into actionable playbooks that can be applied to enforce remediation in the target environment.

The operation of these playbooks will be supported by specialized security enablers, selected and deployed from a repository, based on the remediation's requirements and the current posture of the resources needing protection.

5.6.1 State-of-the-art

Regarding security enforcement and incident response processing, i.e. remediation processes, especially in the incident management and response realm, initiatives have been historically highly fragmented. There were several attempts to find a commonly accepted format and schema for the exchange and enforcement of remediation procedures. Large vendors, competing through proprietary solutions in the field of incident response such as SOAR solutions, have little motivation to adopt a unified approach. Meanwhile, numerous smaller-scale initiatives are emerging, advocating for standardized methods to facilitate the sharing and using such information. Several proposals have been introduced to effectively document, process, share, and operationalize security pipelines and incident response strategies.

One notable approach is the use of Playbooks [46]. As noted by Koulouris et al. [47], playbooks offer a systematic means to formalize incident response procedures, reducing uncertainty even for experienced analysts. They provide a structured way to document, communicate, and share strategies across teams and individual analysts, enhancing knowledge evaluation, development, and transfer. Shaked et al. proposed a formal, model-based framework for designing cybersecurity incident response playbooks [48] and developed a prototype tool to effectively model and analyse security playbooks.

Figure 5-5 Architecture of the remediation manager

In this context, Settanni et al., introduced an architecture model later validated as a prototype which goes in the direction of facilitating the crafting of playbooks starting from a high-level description of their objectives, sharing of the playbooks through CTI platforms, and the enforcement of remediation procedures through an abstract capability catalogue, which allows interfacing with diverse operational environments and their respective security controls. They chose the CACAO Security Playbook standard as the base for the playbook description and modelling, which appears promising to standardize the playbook landscape [28].

5.6.2 Design challenges

As mentioned, the lack of commonly agreed formats and schemas for the sharing and actual actionability of the remediation information is particularly relevant in this field and has stifled the introduction of novel solutions. Big vendors compete on closed solutions in incident response and have no incentive to stick to a commonly agreed approach. Many smaller-scale and open-source or collaborative solutions are beginning to appear, pushing for standardized methods for the sharing and use of such information.

The heterogeneity of enforcement mechanisms is particularly challenging in remediation frameworks. To address this, we plan to define an essential subset of actions to implement in the operational environment, which will serve as a testbed for validating the iTrust6G project.

The main challenges concerning the Remediation Manager at this stage of the development are hereby mentioned. Many of them are strictly correlated to the development of interfaces with other WP5 and WP3 components. Moreover, we need to consider the 6G-specific enablers, like implementing quantum-resistant cryptography.

The current development challenges primarily revolve around several key aspects. A major issue is how to infer and enforce effective strategies based on Cyber Threat Intelligence (CTI) information, ensuring they address the evolving threat landscape. To this end, establishing a common protocol for exchanges, along with a corresponding data model, is essential. Another challenge lies in contextualizing abstract recipes for strategy enforcement, progressing beyond simple responses to basic threats and enabling the development of sophisticated reactions to advanced and complex threats, as outlined in the future work section. Additionally, evaluating and assessing remediation strategies before enforcement is critical, requiring decision-making processes grounded in risk analysis and risk profiles. This will be addressed in collaboration with components in T3.3. Finally, ensuring the confident qualification and selection of security enablers needed to enact these remediation strategies remains a significant hurdle. On this matter, we anticipate coordinating efforts with T5.1.

5.6.3 Design approach

The Remediation Manager oversees the following activities:

- Recommend countermeasures or reactions to mitigate or remediate risks detected or highlighted by the project architecture's Collaborative Risk and Threat Intelligence components. This operation will be performed in this way.
 - Information about the risks to mitigate will be received as a Cyber Threat Intelligence Report from the CTI pipeline or pulled from the CTI platform.
 - The solutions that the Remediation Manager identifies will be bundled in the form of a playbook, a self-contained data structure also shareable as CTI. These will contain the actions to be executed as part of the mitigation or remediation.
 - Both CTI and available playbook templates will be analysed (also with AI-driven techniques) to match the most suitable recipe to enforce.

- Evaluate the most suitable remediation/recipe:
 - The Risk Assessment Component will be invoked to estimate the mitigation impact of the selected recipes.
 - Other functional parameters will be computed to complete the information needed to select the most suitable recipe, like costs, time to deploy, and impact on network and service operation (theoretically, these are SLAs, but they are outside the scope of iTrust6G).
 - Make decisions with an ad hoc yet customizable algorithm.
- Deploy the remediation based on the chosen prioritization mechanism, which involves propagating the necessary set of changes across the landscape to the appropriate enforcement mechanisms (e.g., configuring security controls). This process needs to perform the following steps:
 - Invoke or require management actions or changes to the landscape through other interfaces, such as adding new security controls or configuring existing ones.
 - Contact other components within the architecture to request optimizations in the enforcement strategy.

5.6.4 Specification alignment

The technical specifications described are aligned as described in Table 5-3.

Table 5-3 Specification Alignment for the Remediation Manager

Spec. ID	Description	Alignment
iTrust6G_FUN_GEN_005	Provide collaborative risk management, threat detection, and cyber threat intelligence generation across multi-tenant environments.	The component can enrich CTI reports by attaching information regarding the remediation and mitigation measures that have been used to respond to the security event contained in the CTI report. The new information will be aggregated in a Course of Action STIX Domain object.
iTrust6G_FUN_SP_002	Provide means to quarantine compromised devices, network infrastructures and functions.	The component can enforce mitigation measures in the form of quarantine for target hosts, or other functional units via the orchestrator.
iTrust6G_FUN_SP_006	Define a framework for sharing remediation playbooks in a standard format, enabling proactive threat mitigation among tenants and with external platforms.	The component can craft and handle remediation playbooks compliant with the CACAO Security Playbook standard.
iTrust6G_FUN_SP_008	Proactively propose remediations to improve the security posture of the managed network.	The component can propose remediation procedures based on the evidence that is fed into it and on the risk state of the assets.

5.6.5 Current implementation

An overview of the technical architecture of the remediation manager is presented. This provides detailed insights into the framework, building on what was described in iTrust6G D2.2 and shedding light on its internal workings. While this section offers more detail, the main functionalities remain consistent with those specified in the previous document.

Figure 5-6 Details about the architecture of the remediation manager

Within the Remediation Manager, playbooks can be currently crafted through a high-level representation we call a Recipe, which is then refined into actionable playbooks. Recipes are meant to be used by practitioners to manually document the security procedures to be used and then orchestrated as playbooks by the Remediation Manager, while structured playbooks (either as templates or as directly enforceable ones) compliant with the CACAO standard will come from the Playbook repository. Here, we report the current architecture implementation.

Three types of information characterize recipes.

- A set of labels indicates the threat scenario for which they have been developed.
- A set of enabling constraints allows an understanding of their applicability. For instance, recipes report all the information necessary for their correct deployment and the security capabilities they need to enforce (e.g., an application layer filter), which may not be available in the network.
- The set of remediation deployment instructions, written in an abstract language, programmatically states all the steps needed to remediate the identified risks.

Recipe can document the programmatic actions which may be taken as part of a remediation routine for an ongoing attack on a specific host in the network. An instance of this may be a workflow mandating the insertion of a filtering policy on a specific payload in the network path between an attacker and the target host. For example, this can be useful if the impacted host has become part of a botnet, and the Command-and-Control messages between them exhibit a specific string that can be filtered to disrupt the communication between the bot and the botnet master.

The semantics of the recipe allow for the description and representation of different concepts, each one relevant to the actionability of the remediation in the form of a playbook and provides ease in sharing the remediation content with non-technical staff.

- Adding security controls
- Modifying the configuration of specific security controls
- Modification to the network layout or flows
- Results from past computations (language-specific concepts introduced to satisfy required features)
- Placeholders for predefined concepts
- Inputs from the threat intelligence findings

The operational level targeted by the recipe description ultimately depends on the set of actions it specifies. Expanding this allows for creating recipes tailored to different contexts, including management scenarios, particularly when addressing risks associated with less technical features in a remediation process.

Moreover, we support directly ingesting structured playbooks that are compliant with the CACAO Security Playbook format. Although this format lacks widespread adoption, it sets minimum requirements for standardized playbook descriptions. However, its limited support for enforcement mechanisms led us to introduce foundational support, which we plan to expand in the future by tailoring the playbook model to the specific use cases of the project. The CACAO interpreter component complements the Recipe interpreter by constructing an internal representation of the playbook, which the framework uses for subsequent processing.

Remediation and mitigation strategies, along with their corresponding playbooks, will be stored in the Playbook Repository. The implementation of this repository will be further refined based on integration requirements. Currently, it operates as a non-relational database. However, more advanced data models are being evaluated. Efforts are focused on enriching playbook artifacts with additional metadata to support AI-based tools (LLM+RAG) for the semantic interpretation of playbooks based on their defensive capabilities.

In this architecture, the Playbook Enforcer manages the injection of configurations into the operational environment. For example, it can add policies to security controls or implement changes to the network topology. Regarding network topology, the service graph component maintains an internal representation that mirrors the actual operational environment. This internal representation assists the Playbook Enforcer when network snapshots are needed for coordination or procedural purposes. It may also support other sections within the management layer.

The current architecture includes a central coordination layer, not a single module, but a set of software connectors enabling interaction among different components with distinct functionalities. Among these functionalities is the input analyzer, which interprets asynchronous inputs, such as cyber threat intelligence from external sources outside the Remediation Manager. Additionally, we support extension mechanisms, such as enrichment modules. These modules enhance the capabilities of the Playbook Enforcer by providing advanced features like SSH connection handling and low-level configuration crafting through the Security Capability Manager. Other components may also utilize the enrichment modules. For example, this is a planned development regarding adding reasoning functionalities to the Remediation Manager.

5.6.6 Next steps

As mentioned in the previous sections, we plan to expand the reach of the remediation management framework by integrating reasoning functionalities. These may be supported by additional AI-driven components, which could function as standalone modules or be part of the extension mechanism established

through the enrichment modules. Specifically, we are currently developing the first iteration of a recommender system that leverages an automated heatmap analyzer. This system exploits the new MITRE D3FEND taxonomy to describe and select the most suitable remediation procedures and actions in response to some situations highlighted by CTI reports or alerts. This will be strictly intertwined with the Risk Assessment capabilities to enhance the reasoning system by also incorporating risk-related metrics.

Additionally, we are expanding the set of supported enforcer mechanisms to accommodate cloud-native environments, addressing their unique requirements and toolsets.

Finally, our ongoing technological endeavor involves introducing generative AI to craft new remediation procedures. This will include refining natural language instructions and suggesting actionable steps based on the mechanism catalogue.

6 Secured E2E Service Orchestration

The objective of the Secured E2E Service Orchestration is to design and develop a functional Service Orchestrator responsible for managing, coordinating and automating the deployment, configuration, and operation of network services and resources securely across the entire network, from edge to cloud. This objective involves ensuring that services are delivered efficiently, reliably, and in compliance with the current security posture with the key aspects, which in iTrust6G means providing:

- *Multi-level orchestration* to operate an adequate programmed version of a service, considering the current security posture of the network.
- *Secure placement* based on trust requirements for secure placement of network functions and services and the exploitation of resources permitting hardware root of trust.
- *Secure deployment* methods for service images, i.e., to develop secure deployment methods for service images.
- Isolation of resources via suited virtualization models and network slicing to ensure that services and data are protected from unauthorized access and interference.

The overall objective is to extend a service orchestrator to support trustable placement of services, slice management and cooperation with the security orchestrator. Extension of current state-of-the-art service orchestrator with Policy Verification Module as a way forward for trustable placement of services aligned with Zero Trust Management principles.

6.1 Summary of the outcomes

The outcome of this line of research can be summarized as:

- Complete Internal design and interaction analysis of the components of the Secure Service Orchestrator aligned with OSM MANO²⁹.
- The high-level design of Interfaces used to communicate with the other components in the iTrust6G framework, such as Remediation Manager, Programmable Security Mechanisms, Policy Decision Point, Infrastructure orchestrator, AI Trust Evaluator, Security Monitoring and pre-detection, Static Trust Assessment and RA Engine.
- Logical design of a novel functionality related to Policy Verification Function and implementation of the ML pipeline with synthetic data, choice of ML algorithm as One-Class Support Vector Machine for policy-based anomaly detection with a weighted precision score of 0.7.

6.2 Objectives and expected outcomes for the next reporting period

The Objectives and the expected outcomes for this research activity can be summarized as:

- Integration of the Policy Verification Module with OSM MANO along with training data from a mobile network Operator or based on mobility patterns.
- Development of Authentication/ Authorization Module along with Policy Enforcement Point (PEP) for OSM MANO.
- Development of OSM MANO-based parser for playbook translation for Programmable Security Mechanisms and Remediation Manager.

²⁹ <https://osm.etsi.org/>

- Development of Alert Manager along with Metric Collection Methodologies and reporting module for OSM MANO.

6.3 Overall presentation of the achievements

iTrust6G chooses the ETSI OSM MANO³⁰ as the service orchestrator and enhance it with additional functionalities for a robust and secure orchestration process. To this end, aligned with the objectives of this research activity and the overall architecture of the project, the identified components for research and development are as follows:

- Life Cycle Manager;
- Policy Verification Function;
- Authorization and Authentication Function / PEP Module;
- Monitoring and Reporting Module.

Figure 6-1 Service orchestrator architecture and interactions

³⁰ "SNS-JU BeGREEN Project," 2016. [Online]. Available: www.sns-begreen.com.

Figure 6-1 reports the interaction of the internal modules of the secure service orchestrator as well as the external components of the iTrust6G framework:

- **OSM-related communications**
 1. **Remediation Manager (RM) – OSM Client:** The RM sends high-level security mechanisms/remediation actions related to policy to the OSM Client that represents the mitigation actions or configuration changes to be taken for the Virtualized Network Functions or Network Services in CACAO format (or any other format).
 2. **OSM Client – North Bound Interface (NBI):** The remediation action is interpreted from the CACAO playbook; the OSM database is checked to see if the action is already available as YANG descriptors. If not, this step involves interpretation and translation of the CACAO playbooks to virtualized network function descriptors (VNFD) and network service descriptors (NSD) for further processing and is saved in the database.
 3. **North Bound Interface (NBI) – Life Cycle Manager (LCM):** This step represents a trigger call to the Life Cycle Manager (LCM) to initiate the remediation action as notified by the RM.
- **Trust evaluation**
 4. **Life Cycle Manager (LCM) – AI Trust Evaluator:** The Life Cycle Manager requests trust scores of the *domain, repository and service image* from the AI Trust Evaluator before initiating the deployment.
 5. **AI Trust Evaluator – Life Cycle Manager (LCM):** The tuple of the trust score is calculated by the AI Trust Evaluator and is sent to the LCM, and if the trust score is within a threshold, the LCM proceeds with **Step 6**, otherwise **Step 18** is executed.
 6. **Life Cycle Manager (LCM) – Programmable Security Mechanism (PSM):** Based on the remediation action, the LCM sends a request for the programmable security template to the Programmable Security Mechanism tool.
- **Policy-related communications**
 7. **Programmable Security Mechanism (PSM) – Policy Enforcement Point (PEP) Module:** The programmable Security Mechanism tool follows an intent-based policy deployment request to access the resource where the configuration changes or any security mechanism is to be deployed.
 8. **Policy Enforcement Point (PEP) Module – Policy Decision Point (PDP):** To validate the policy and the requester of the domain and services for service authentication and authorization, the PEP module sends a request to the PDP for Policy Check along with the requester's identity, policy and intent.
 9. **Policy Decision Point (PDP) – Policy Enforcement Point (PEP) Module:** Based on the parameters sent in **Step 8**, the PDP send a decision to the PEP module in the service orchestrator, providing information if the request is valid.
 10. **Policy Enforcement Point (PEP) Module – Life Cycle Manager (LCM):** The PEP grants or denies access to the requested resource to the LCM for further processing based on the policy decision sent from the PDP. In case access to the resources is denied, Step 18 is executed, and in case of a positive response, the LCM proceeds with **Step 11**.
 11. **Life Cycle Manager (LCM) – Policy Verification Function (PVF):** The LCM sends policy verification requests to the PVF along the intermediate level policy for configuration changes or deployment

of security mechanisms or CRUD operations of the VNFs or NS. Regarding security-related metrics, the PVF interacts with the PSM as in **Step 12** and **Step 13** to fetch the low-level metrics for security configuration, whereas for other requests like CRUD operations, it executes **Step 14**.

12. **Policy Verification Function (PVF) – Programmable Security Mechanism (PSM):** The PVF sends high-level security configurations to the Programmable Security Mechanism tool, requesting low-level policy generation.
 13. **Programmable Security Mechanism (PSM) – Policy Verification Function (PVF):** Analysing the high-level security metrics requirements, the PSM generates low-level policies consisting of exact security metrics or configurations for the VNFs or for the creation of security-aware VNFs like Firewalls and sends it to the PVF.
 14. **Policy Verification Function (PVF):** PVF, in this step, verifies the policies and their parameter values, runs a base inference, and generates a granular report of the policies.
 15. **Policy Verification Function (PVF) – Life Cycle Manager (LCM):** The inference report indicates that either an anomaly or normal is sent to the LCM as a decision for resource deployment. With any anomaly, the LCM executes **Step 16**; otherwise, **Step 18** is executed.
- **Helm EE**
 16. **Life Cycle Manager (LCM) – Helm EE Pods:** Based on a positive decision from the PVF, the LCM sends the deployment primitives consisting of the helm charts to the API Front End (FE) EE Primitive for processing.
 17. **Helm EE Pods – Cloud Infrastructure:** The Helm EE Pods connect to the cloud infrastructure or Kubernetes cluster through SSH or API endpoints, deploy VNFs or change the security configurations of VNFs or NS based on the helm charts from the LCM.
 - **Monitoring and alerting**
 18. **Life Cycle Manager (LCM) - Alert Manager/Monitoring Agents (AM/MA):** If a trust score is below the threshold or an anomaly is detected in policies, the LCM generates an anomaly alert and triggers the Alert Manager / Monitoring Agents module.
 19. **Alert Manager/Monitoring Agents - Cloud Infrastructure:** The monitoring agents deployed at the infrastructure level fetch metrics continuously and store them, which can also be added to the reports sent from **Steps 20 - 22**.
 20. **Alert Manager/Monitoring Agents – Remote Attestation (RA) Engine:** On any changes in the NFVI level ranging from deployment, deletion or modification, this module sends the asset listing along with reference measurements like hash value to the RA Engine.
 21. **Alert Manager/Monitoring Agents - Security Monitoring and Pre-detection (SMPD):** The AM/MA sends anomaly data, metrics, and monitoring data to the SMPD.
 22. **Alert Manager/Monitoring Agents – Remediation Manager and Static Trust Assessment Component:** The AM/MA sends the current Network Landscape/ Topology, Services and Security Controls for the current security posture to the RM and Static Trust Assessment Module.

It is important to note here that there are several other components or modules in the ESTI OSM MANO which are involved in the process of orchestration, like the North Bound Interface (NBI), CommonDB, Object Storage, VNF configuration and abstraction (VCA) tool and other Kubernetes control plane components like Helm EE (Execution environment) pods, but based on the objectives of this research activity, we keep their functionality as they are and have excluded them from the following sections. For the PEP Module and the

Alert Manager and Monitoring Agents, we design the interactions as in Figure 6-2 and to further configure in the next deliverables.

6.4 Life cycle manager

The Life Cycle Manager (LCM) is one of the key components in any orchestration process, and from the perspective of OSM MANO, the LCM is a Lightweight Build Life Cycle Management for OSM, and it interacts with Resource Orchestrator (RO) module for resource orchestration and Network Service to Virtualization Container) N2VC for VNF configuration. In this project, as we focus on the Day 1 and Day 2 operations as a part of secure service orchestration and the infrastructure for managing the resources as Kubernetes cluster, automating the interactions with the N2VC module and the LCM is our major task.

6.4.1 State-of-the-art

The OSM MANO currently has a mature LCM, and the user can interact with the LCM commands through the North Bound Interfaces (NBI) using the OSM Client or the GUI itself. The OSM MANO supports Day-0, Day-1, and Day-2 operations, including self-healing of the VNFs; the authorized users control all these operations, as shown in Figure 6-2:

- Day-0: The machine gets ready to be managed (e.g. import ssh-keys, create users/pass, network configuration, etc.)
- Day-1: The machine gets configured to provide services (e.g., install packages, edit config files, execute commands, etc.)
- Day-2: The machine configuration and management are updated (e.g., Do on-demand actions, like dump logs, backup databases, update users etc.)

6.4.2 Design challenges

The LCM performs the Day1 and Day2 operations using the Network Service to Virtualization Container (N2VC) tool and the Virtual Infrastructure Manager (VIM) like OpenStack or Azure Cloud or AWS on either and the VNFI as Virtual Machine, docker containers or Kubernetes Clusters. To understand and design the interaction and computation enhancement of the LCM, it was important to understand and streamline the processes with custom iterations and interactions. The LCM is at the centre of the coordination, and the interfaces and the expected input/output are defined, as can be seen in Figure 6-2.

Figure 6-2 Interaction of the components when launching day1 and day2 operations in OSM MANO³¹

³¹ "SNS-JU BeGREEN Project," 2016. [Online]. Available: www.sns-begreen.com.

6.4.3 Design approach

Based on the caveats of the current state-of-the-art and the project requirements, we identified the major enhancements of the LCM as shown in Figure 6-2 and can be listed as follows:

- Capability to interact with the Programmability Security Metrics and enable the PEP for access decisions.
- Capability to interact with the AI Trust Evaluator for sourcing the trust score of the domain, service image and the repository.
- Capability to ensure policy verification as part of secure service orchestrator.
- Automation of the NS and VNF life cycle management functionalities.
- Generate Anomaly Data for the Trust management functionalities to consume.

6.4.4 Protocol description

Although the internal components of the OSM MANO interact with each other using a KAFKA bus and corresponding Kafka topics following a publish-subscribe protocol, for the first iteration of the enhancements, we defined the interaction with new components PVF, PEP and Alert Manager using REST APIs.

6.4.5 Specification alignment

The technical specifications described are aligned as described in Figure 6-1.

Table 6-1 Specification Alignment for the Life Cycle Manager

Spec. ID	Description	Alignment
iTrust6G_FUN_GEN_002	Integrate authentication, monitoring and attestation methods for devices to ensure only authorized users and devices can access the network.	The LCM interacts with the PEP module in OSM MANO to authenticate any service requests in the network

6.4.6 Current implementation

The current implementation is limited to the LCM actions' design phase with the other Service orchestration components.

6.4.7 Future work

For the future work of these components, we plan to set up the triggers for policy verification, automation, monitoring and reporting for the LCM.

6.5 Policy verification function

The Policy Verification Function (PVF) enhances the OSM MANO, where the policies are verified based on the parameters using a Machine Learning (ML) approach to detect anomalous policies. This is a module triggered for any CRUD operation or security configurations and mechanism, as shown in Figure 2.

6.5.1 State-of-the-art

To our knowledge, the policy verification function is not currently being implemented. The closest functionality from the orchestrator's perspective is the policy conflict detector (PCD). In a situation where two policies have the same triggering condition but different actions, the policy conflict is caused. After the VNFM receives the newly created scaling policy, it compares the newly created scaling policy with the

existing policies and detects that there is a conflict in the enforcement of both policies. The information on conflicted policies is further reported to the PAP (e.g. NFVO).

The NFVO may analyse various information. The NFVO makes a decision regarding the policy conflict. Possible results might be:

- the NFVO decides to keep the newly created VNF scaling policy: Therefore, the NFVO activates the newly created VNF scaling policy while deactivating the existing VNF scaling policy; or
- the NFVO decides to keep the existing scaling policy, and then the newly created VNF scaling policy is not activated by the NFVO.

However, those functions are significantly different from the policy verification function in the scenarios where the policy is anomalous.

6.5.2 Design challenges

To integrate the PVF, it was important to align the functionalities, avoiding overlap with the LCM in the OSM MANO. The PVF also communicates with the PSM for the generation of security metrics and mechanisms, for which there was a need for fine-grained communication between the different components.

6.5.3 Design approach

We designed the PVF as a separate functional block that interacts with the LCM and PSM for policy verification, which is shown in Figure 6-3:

Step 0: The LCM receives a policy or playbook from the remediation manager.

Step 1: The LCM send the playbook to the Policy Verifier Function (PVF) for verification of the Policies.

Step 2: The Policy Verifier send requests for the Security metrics (if any) from the Programable Security Mechanism (PSM).

Step 3: The PVF receives a security capability-aware playbook from the PSM.

Step 4: The PVF runs inference on the data collected from the Playbook (either from the PSM for security or directly from the LCM) and determines if the policy is genuine or anomalous.

Step 5: The LCM receives the Verification decision based on which the policy is accepted or discarded.

Step 6: On receiving a positive response from the PVF, the LCM interacts with the HELM Execution Environment Pods to perform CRUD operation on the VNFs on the Kubernetes infrastructure.

Step 7: The Helm EE Pods deploy or change the configurations of the based on the helm charts on the VNFs or NS in the cloud infrastructure or Kubernetes cluster through SSH or API endpoints.

Figure 6-3 Interaction of the PVF with the other internal and external components

6.5.4 Protocol description

The protocol used in the communication of the PVF with the LCM and PSM uses REST, which can be later switched to an MQTT-based protocol using KAFKA or Rabbit MQ.

6.5.5 Specification alignment

The technical specifications described are aligned as described in Table 5-3.

Table 6-2 Specification Alignment for the Policy Verification Function

Spec ID	Description	Alignment
iTrust6G_FUN_GEN_003	Apply zero-trust principles by: (i) Continuously monitoring and evaluating the security posture of operated assets. (ii) Regularly assessing the integrity of the underlying infrastructure.	The PVF module monitors and verifies the policies aligned to the Zero Trust principles.

6.5.6 Current implementation

As shown in Figure 6-4, we implement the PVF as a Python flask server that receives POST requests from the LCM with the input as policies needed for verifications, and in response, the PVF sends the decision based on each VNF to the LCM with decisions if the policy is anomalous. The PVF has mainly four stages of operation:

- The Policy Translation module, based on the received request, formulates a low-level policy description from the received CACAO or TOSCA playbooks.
- Data is extracted from these policies for input into the pre-trained ML model.
- The ML model generates inference on the received data in the form of vectors for every input from the bundles of policies.
- The Classification Result is generated in the form of JSON with the inputs from the ML model and wraps with the granular report of each VNF.
- A scenario is envisaged where the LCM receives a scaling request for a telco Core Network in the form of a playbook due to a detected DOS attack that has already been mitigated. The request consists of scaling three network functions: AMF, SMF and PCF. For the ML model as an unsupervised learning problem, One Class SVM is used for training, and synthetic data is generated using a Gaussian distribution with the following criteria and graphs: Table 6-3 and Figure 6-5. It is possible to see that this data set is complex enough to be usable for the tasks we aim to achieve in this project.

Figure 6-4 Visualization of the pipeline for PVF

Table 6-3 Parameter for the Network Function Based on Their Properties

Network Function	AMF	SMF	PCF
<i>replica_count</i>	3±1	4±2	2±1
<i>cpu_limit</i>	300±100	350±150	280±80
<i>memory_limit</i>	120±40	150±50	100±30

Figure 6-5 Diagram representing the distribution of synthetic data

The input to the PVF playbooks is in the form of helm charts and contains the feature values for the ML model to predict with a pre-trained OC-SVM model. The preprocessor has been used with training from the dataset described above. The PVF flask server response as the playbook name, the input data and predicted label: 1 for Normal and 0 for Anomalous, as shown in Figure 6-6.

```
spau15@SPAUL5-PF421YY0:/mnt/c/Users/spau15/policy_verifier/testing$ python send_helm.py
{
  "helm_file": "example-helm-chart-1.0.0.tgz",
  "predictions": [
```

```

{
  "cpu_limit": 305,
  "memory_limit": 120,
  "network_function": "AMF",
  "predicted_label": 1,
  "replica_count": 3
},
{
  "cpu_limit": 1000,
  "memory_limit": 512,
  "network_function": "SMF",
  "predicted_label": 0,
  "replica_count": 3
},
{
  "cpu_limit": 2000,
  "memory_limit": 1024,
  "network_function": "PCF",
  "predicted_label": 0,
  "replica_count": 4
}
]
}
    
```

Figure 6-6 Output generated by the PVF after policy verification

Figure 6-7 Preliminary results of the ML model for policy verification

To evaluate the classification accuracy of the ML model, we generate data based on the same Gaussian distribution with randomized means and variances for the replica count, CPU limit and Memory limit. The performance is presented in Figure 6-7.

6.5.7 Future work

In terms of future work of PVF, we plan to follow the action items as:

- Building this module will involve incremental updates and integration along with the generation of training and testing data.

- Generalized parsing of the policies - NSD, VNFD, and Security Policies- and fetching parameters for inference.
- Finalize the interaction with the Programmable Security Mechanism (ex. Configuration of the VFW or VGW) as well as integrate micro-segmentation update procedure as security mechanism.

7 Conclusions

This document, iTrust6G D5.1, presents iTrust6G solutions for maintaining risks at an acceptable level and the infrastructure supporting this crucial goal. The discussions include models, methods, and tools for monitoring and detecting anomalies within the infrastructure. Anomalies were classified, and Cyber Threat Intelligence (CTI) data were enriched using AI techniques based on algorithms from iTrust6G WP3 and WP4. The enriched CTI data facilitated effective remediation strategies, leading to configurations for security controls and network proposals.

The Vulnerability Assessment Tool, designed for vulnerability detection and mitigation in beyond-5G/6G networks is the tool that produces STIX JSON outputs detailing devices, services, vulnerabilities, and recommendations. Additionally, it has presented an Improved Metadon-based SIEM for local log management and Chimera, completing the set of monitoring tools for data collection and processing.

Concerning the aggregation and enrichment of CTI data, the AI Correlation Engine supports enhanced real-time threat detection by integrating various frameworks for autonomous threat analysis. The Security Orchestration Engine was also developed, serving as the core of the security automation framework.

The architecture for managing security incident remediation was established and centred around the Remediation Manager, which uses AI-enhanced CTI data to identify and enforce remediation strategies. A Policy Tool allows the enforcement of security requirements using models of network functions.

Finally, iTrust6G developed an enhanced version of the ETSI OSM MANO service orchestrator, developing the Life Cycle Manager for orchestration processes and the Policy Verification Function to ensure secure operations.

Overall, these efforts contributed to a robust framework for managing security risks in the iTrust6G ecosystem. Several future steps have been highlighted which will be addressed in the next reporting periods.

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Appendix: Listings

The example reported in Listing A-0-1 describes a dummy version of the STIX report produced showcasing all objects described above along with their relationships and the types of their relationships.

```
{
  "type": "bundle",
  "id": "bundle--5d0092c5-5f74-4287-9642-33f4c354e56d",
  "objects": [
    {
      "type": "ipv4-addr",
      "spec_version": "2.1",
      "id": "ipv4-addr--ff26c055-6336-5bc5-b98d-13d6226742dd",
      "value": "198.51.100.3"
    },
    {
      "type": "mac-addr",
      "spec_version": "2.1",
      "id": "mac-addr--65cfcf98-8a6e-5a1b-8f61-379ac4f92d00",
      "value": "d2:fb:49:24:37:18"
    },
    {
      "type": "relationship",
      "spec_version": "2.1",
      "id": "relationship--fc82707d-b4bb-4dbe-ba0c-f479f1c9c74e",
      "created": "2023-07-17T06:48:00.345901Z",
      "modified": "2023-07-17T06:48:00.345901Z",
      "relationship_type": "resolves-to",
      "source_ref": "ipv4-addr--ff26c055-6336-5bc5-b98d-13d6226742dd",
      "target_ref": "mac-addr--65cfcf98-8a6e-5a1b-8f61-379ac4f92d00"
    },
    {
      "type": "software",
      "spec_version": "2.1",
      "id": "software--a1827f6d-ca53-5605-9e93-4316cd22a00a",
      "name": "Word",
      "cpe": "cpe:2.3:a:microsoft:word:2000:*:*:*:*:*:*:*",
      "version": "2002",
      "vendor": "Microsoft"
    },
    {
      "type": "relationship",
      "spec_version": "2.1",
      "id": "relationship--fc82707d-b4bb-4dce-ba0c-f479f1c9c74e",
      "created": "2023-07-17T06:48:00.345901Z",
      "modified": "2023-07-17T06:48:00.345901Z",
      "relationship_type": "related-to",
      "source_ref": "ipv4-addr--ff26c055-6336-5bc5-b98d-13d6226742dd",
      "target_ref": "software--a1827f6d-ca53-5605-9e93-4316cd22a00a"
    },
    {
      "type": "vulnerability",
      "spec_version": "2.1",

```

```

    "id": "vulnerability--0c7b5b88-8ff7-4a4d-aa9d-feb398cd0061",
    "created": "2016-05-12T08:17:27.000Z",
    "modified": "2016-05-12T08:17:27.000Z",
    "created_by_ref": "identity--f431f809-377b-45e0-aa1c-6a4751cae5ff",
    "name": "CVE-2016-1234",
    "external_references": [
      {
        "source_name": "cve",
        "external_id": "CVE-2016-1234"
      }
    ]
  },
  {
    "x_mitre_platforms": [
      "Windows",
      "IaaS",
      "Linux",
      "macOS"
    ],
    "x_mitre_domains": [
      "enterprise-attack"
    ],
    "object_marking_refs": [
      "marking-definition--fa42a846-8d90-4e51-bc29-71d5b4802168"
    ],
    "id": "attack-pattern--5909f20f-3c39-4795-be06-ef1ea40d350b",
    "type": "attack-pattern",
    "created": "2019-04-08T17:51:41.390Z",
    "created_by_ref": "identity--c78cb6e5-0c4b-4611-8297-d1b8b55e40b5",
    "external_references": [
      {
        "source_name": "mitre-attack",
        "external_id": "T1491",
        "url": "https://attack.mitre.org/techniques/T1491"
      }
    ],
    "modified": "2022-05-11T14:00:00.188Z",
    "name": "Defacement",
    "description": "Adversaries may modify visual content available internally or externally to an enterprise network, thus affecting the integrity of the original content. Reasons for [Defacement](https://attack.mitre.org/techniques/T1491) include delivering messaging, intimidation, or claiming (possibly false) credit for an intrusion. Disturbing or offensive images may be used as a part of [Defacement](https://attack.mitre.org/techniques/T1491) to cause user discomfort or pressure compliance with accompanying messages. \n",
    "kill_chain_phases": [
      {
        "kill_chain_name": "mitre-attack",
        "phase_name": "impact"
      }
    ],
    "x_mitre_detection": "Monitor internal and external websites for unplanned content changes. Monitor application logs for abnormal behavior that may indicate attempted or successful exploitation. Use deep packet inspection to look for artifacts of common exploit traffic, such as SQL injection. Web Application Firewalls may detect

```

```

improper inputs attempting exploitation.\n\n",
  "x_mitre_version": "1.3",
  "x_mitre_modified_by_ref": "identity--c78cb6e5-0c4b-4611-8297-d1b8b55e40b5",
  "x_mitre_data_sources": [
    "Network Traffic: Network Traffic Content",
    "File: File Creation",
    "Application Log: Application Log Content",
    "File: File Modification"
  ],
  "x_mitre_impact_type": [
    "Integrity"
  ],
  "x_mitre_is_subtechnique": false,
  "spec_version": "2.1",
  "x_mitre_attack_spec_version": "2.1.0"
},
{
  "type": "relationship",
  "spec_version": "2.1",
  "id": "relationship--199a96bf-bb1a-4cac-976c-a4fda972e315",
  "created": "2023-07-17T06:48:00.342907Z",
  "modified": "2023-07-17T06:48:00.342907Z",
  "relationship_type": "related-to",
  "source_ref": "software--a1827f6d-ca53-5605-9e93-4316cd22a00a",
  "target_ref": "vulnerability--0c7b5b88-8ff7-4a4d-aa9d-feb398cd0061"
},
{
  "type": "course-of-action",
  "spec_version": "2.1",
  "id": "course-of-action--8e2e2d2b-17d4-4cbf-938f-98ee46b3cd3f",
  "created_by_ref": "identity--f431f809-377b-45e0-aa1c-6a4751cae5ff",
  "created": "2016-04-06T20:03:48.000Z",
  "modified": "2016-04-06T20:03:48.000Z",
  "name": "Add TCP port 80 Filter Rule to the existing Block UDP 1434 Filter",
  "description": "This is how to add a filter rule to block inbound access to TCP port 80 to ..."
},
{
  "type": "relationship",
  "id": "relationship--0005fb3b-274a-4ac1-8fb2-51366fcd1a6b",
  "created": "2023-09-01T21:33:59.394Z",
  "revoked": false,
  "object_marking_refs": [
    "marking-definition--fa42a846-8d90-4e51-bc29-71d5b4802168"
  ],
  "modified": "2023-09-01T21:33:59.394Z",
  "description": "Consider blocking download/transfer and execution of potentially uncommon file types known
to be used in adversary campaigns.",
  "relationship_type": "mitigates",
  "source_ref": "course-of-action--8e2e2d2b-17d4-4cbf-938f-98ee46b3cd3f",
  "target_ref": "attack-pattern--5909f20f-3c39-4795-be06-ef1ea40d350b",
  "x_mitre_deprecated": false,
  "x_mitre_version": "0.1",
  "x_mitre_attack_spec_version": "3.1.0",

```

```

    "created_by_ref": "identity--c78cb6e5-0c4b-4611-8297-d1b8b55e40b5",
    "x_mitre_modified_by_ref": "identity--c78cb6e5-0c4b-4611-8297-d1b8b55e40b5",
    "spec_version": "2.1",
    "x_mitre_domains": [
      "enterprise-attack"
    ]
  },
  {
    "type": "relationship",
    "spec_version": "2.1",
    "id": "relationship--198a96bf-bb1a-4cac-976c-a4fda972e315",
    "created": "2023-07-17T06:48:00.342907Z",
    "modified": "2023-07-17T06:48:00.342907Z",
    "relationship_type": "related-to",
    "source_ref": "vulnerability--0c7b5b88-8ff7-4a4d-aa9d-feb398cd0061",
    "target_ref": "attack-pattern--5909f20f-3c39-4795-be06-ef1ea40d350b"
  }
]
}

```

Listing A-0-1 VA STIX v2.1 report

The automation process begins with the webhook listener, which is implemented as a FastAPI application. This app listens for incoming HTTP POST requests on the /webhook endpoint. OpenCTI sends webhooks to this endpoint whenever an object—such as a report, indicator, or malware—is created or updated in the OpenCTI platform and relevant automation playbooks are triggered. Once the webhook is received, the FastAPI application processes the data automatically, extracting the relevant information for further analysis.

```

openapi: 3.0.3
info:
  title: OpenCTI Webhook
  version: "1.0.0"
  description: "API spec for a webhook that receives notifications from OpenCTI."
paths:
  /webhook:
    post:
      summary: "Receive a webhook notification from OpenCTI"
      requestBody:
        required: true
        content:
          application/json:
            schema:
              type: object
              properties:
                type:
                  type: string
                  example: "message"
                attachments:
                  type: array
                  items:

```

```

    type: object
    properties:
      contentType:
        type: string
        example: "application/vnd.microsoft.card.adaptive"
      content:
        type: object
        properties:
          body:
            type: array
            items:
              type: object
              properties:
                items:
                  type: array
                  items:
                    type: object
                    properties:
                      text:
                        type: string
                        example: "[creates a
Report](https://localhost:3000/dashboard/id/report--example)"
    dataString:
      type: object
      properties:
        name:
          type: string
          example: "Prioritizing indicators"
        trigger_type:
          type: string
          example: "digest"
  examples:
    samplePayload:
      value:
        type: "message"
        attachments:
          - contentType: "application/vnd.microsoft.card.adaptive"
            content:
              body:
                - items:
                    - text: "[creates a
Indicator](https://localhost:3000/dashboard/id/indicator--example)"
                    - text: "[creates a
Report](https://localhost:3000/dashboard/id/report--example)"
                    - text: "[related to Threat Actor
`APT28`](https://localhost:3000/dashboard/id/threat-actor--example)"
            dataString:
              name: "Prioritizing indicators"
              trigger_type: "digest"

```

```
responses:
  '200':
    description: "Success"
    content:
      application/json:
        schema:
          type: object
          properties:
            status:
              type: string
              example: "success"
            report_id:
              type: string
              example: "7abdd3f1-f53b-5444-a99e-45f84a153963"
  '400':
    description: "Bad request or invalid payload."
    content:
      application/json:
        schema:
          type: object
          properties:
            error:
              type: string
              example: "Report ID not found in the webhook data"
  '500':
    description: "Internal server error."
    content:
      application/json:
        schema:
          type: object
          properties:
            error:
              type: string
              example: "Internal server error"
```

Listing A-0-2 Example of the webhook handler

In the webhook handler, the system first checks if the data is received successfully. If no data is found, an error response is returned. The data is parsed and logged for further inspection if it is valid. The webhook handler specifically looks for the creation or modification of a STIX report, and it extracts the report ID from the incoming JSON payload for the next steps in the process.

In STIX, each report (referred to as a bundle in STIX terminology) represents a knowledge graph—a collection of nodes and relationships that describe a security incident or a relevant event. It includes key entities such as Threat Actor, Malware, Vulnerability, Attack Pattern, and Indicator, along with relationships like "uses" and "targets" to represent their interactions.

After receiving the webhook data, the application proceeds to extract the report ID from the payload. This is achieved by parsing through the webhook's attachments section and looking for specific content items that contain a reference to a "Report" creation. Once the report is identified, the system extracts the unique report ID from the URL and prepares it for querying OpenCTI.

This process ensures that the system knows exactly which report or object has been created or updated, allowing it to fetch the relevant details from OpenCTI. The report ID is extracted by splitting the text content to isolate the unique identifier.

Once the report ID has been successfully extracted, the application proceeds to query OpenCTI's API to retrieve the full details of the report. Using the PyCTI client, a Python wrapper for the OpenCTI API, the application constructs a request to fetch the full STIX bundle associated with the given report ID. This bundle contains a wealth of information, such as related indicators, TTPs, CVEs, and associated threat intelligence data.

The report is fetched by calling the *get_stix_bundle_or_object_from_entity_id* method, which queries OpenCTI for a specific report entity. Once the bundle is fetched, the system saves it as a JSON file for later use or processing.

After retrieving the full report and its associated details, the system publishes the data to RabbitMQ for further processing. RabbitMQ serves as a message broker, allowing other systems to consume the data (e.g. the remediation manager).

The report data is serialized into JSON format and sent to a designated RabbitMQ queue, where downstream systems can process it. The message is marked as persistent to ensure that it is not lost in case of a system failure. By using RabbitMQ, the solution ensures that the data is decoupled from the processing application, enabling other systems to act on the data in real-time.